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**STEM STUDENTS' DIRECT AND DEFERRED CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING
AND SELF- EFFICACY USING THE INVERTED LEARNING APPROACH IN
BIOLOGY: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY**

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26 May 2023

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This paper prepared by **ROLLY JAMES F. CHENG** with the title: “**STEM STUDENTS’ DIRECT AND DEFERRED CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING AND SELF- EFFICACY USING THE INVERTED LEARNING APPROACH IN BIOLOGY: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Doctor of Philosophy in Education.

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Biographical Sketch

Rolly James F. Cheng has a Bachelor's degree in Education, major in Biological Science, *Cum Laude* and a Master's degree in Science Education. As a licensed professional and practicing teacher since 2011, he has received a volume of recognition for his work. He served as science club moderator of the school and had been a winning coach in various Science Quiz and SIP competitions at the Division, Regional, and National levels. He has been teaching science and practical research courses in the Senior High School and has mentored students in conducting qualitative and quantitative research for school-based research colloquium, capstone projects, and culminating activities. His areas of strength include Biology Education, Inverted Teaching and Learning, Pedagogy and Andragogy, Practical Research, Organic Chemistry, Science Investigatory Project, and Extension Education.

He has also been involved in several research and community engagement/extension services. He attended as a presenter and delegate to the 2-week ASEAN Future Leaders Summit (AFLES) 2018 in Malaysia and Thailand; and was designated as the Philippine Ambassador of the same program in 2020. He also successfully completed the e-ASEAN Youth Volunteer Program (e-AYVP)- Philippines 2021 organized by the University of the Philippines and Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.

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To God be the glory!

Dedication

I dedicate this dissertation to my ever supportive family

Felix and Forcefin Alma

Kuya Richard, Ronald, Rosemarie, and Richie Smith

Inerbie Jane, Gabriel John, and Andrei

To my relatives, ASEAN friends, colleagues, and students who have been there for me day in and day out, as well as to everyone who listened and believed and even did not.

PhD journey is not a walk in the park. It is only for those who have confidence in their hopes and prayers, carry well their insecurities, and genuinely love their own scars and imperfections.

To all the dreamers, weave your visions high and deep. It does take time, but the end results are always worth the wait.

Padayon!

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Abstract

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. It explored how an inverted learning approach affected the direct and deferred conceptual understanding, as well as self-efficacy of STEM students enrolled in a biology course. It also sought to understand the experiences of students who were taught using the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA). A total of 225 STEM students were involved in the study. Findings revealed that students who were exposed to ILA had higher normalized gains in both posttest and retention test scores than those who were taught using the expository online teaching (EOT). Likewise, there was also a significant difference on the self-efficacy level between ILA and EOT groups. It therefore showed that ILA improved students' direct and deferred conceptual understanding, and self-efficacy levels than their counterparts. Reflexive thematic analysis was applied to elucidate the qualitative information gathered. Four (4) themes emerged from the researcher's engagement with the participants exposed to ILA, which include: 1) Developing into active and reflective learners; 2) Enabling students to engage and collaborate more freely; 3) Establishing a flexible, seamless, and nonpressuring space for learning; and, 4) Becoming disciplined and responsible for one's own learning. Even though there was a significant increment in the levels of direct and deferred conceptual understanding and self-efficacy among students taught using ILA, it was indicated that conceptual understanding is not highly related or associated with self-efficacy. Given the paucity of research in this area, further study is still needed to elucidate the complex relationships between self-efficacy, and direct and deferred conceptual understanding.

Keywords: Inverted Learning Approach, Conceptual Understanding, Self-Efficacy, STEM, Biology Education, Mixed-Methods Study

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The COVID-19 pandemic has already had a significant disruptive impact on society, posing challenges to educational policies and systems worldwide (Anthony & Noel, 2021). That is why various educational institutions transitioned their face-to-face teaching modality to a virtual or an online platform (Jiménez et al., 2021; Gopalan et al., 2021), hybrid, or blended modality. Necessarily, classes have shifted to online learning (Won et al., 2020; Mittal et al., 2021; Srivastava et al., 2021); where digital technologies (Anthony & Noel, 2021) and innovative emergency remote teaching (Parker et al., 2021) were adopted.

Working from home digitally has been considered during the state of emergency (Carvalho et al., 2022); and the application of distance learning is essential to maintain the continuity of education after the physical shutdown of schools. Thus, remote emergency activities using Information and Communication Technologies were required in education to allow students to continue their studies as pointed out by Cara et al. (2022) and Martins et al. (2022). This new normal set-up as described by Lal (2020) has become a challenge for teachers to deliver instruction outside of the norm, such as shifting from face-to-face to face-to-screen interaction (Jeong & González-Gómez, 2021; Nair, 2020). Inevitably, online learning has now become a more embraced learning modality, which is an integration of technology into education (Tang et al., 2020).

Technological advancement is an ongoing and increasing trend, however, the pressure on teachers to adapt to the virtual model of teaching has been extensive. While Lal (2020) believes that traditional teaching is much convenient because doing online lectures requires time, effort, and preparation affecting the roles of teachers and students, Sharma (2020) deems online classes as better learning platform during these unprecedented times by allowing them to stay at home and study without fear of contracting the virus. In the twenty-first-century education, the concept of teachers as experts who impart wisdom to their students is no longer appropriate (Nair, 2020). Thus, everyone is now on social media and attempting to share information on social media platforms because access to knowledge and technological skill is possible with a few clicks on their phones, tablets, and computers (Tehelka, 2020).

Learners acquire information that may or may not be integrated with learning and experience. This is referred to as the direct conceptual understanding. They can use these directly acquired concepts to solve issues more systematically (procedural knowledge); and eventually, become independent and create skill-based behavior (skill tuning of procedural knowledge). Because learning gains may be forgotten, it is crucial to focus on efficient teaching strategies that encourage students to learn and form meaningful associations, resulting in learning that lasts longer (Al-Balushi & Al-Balushi, 2018).

Tests not only measure stored information, but they can also improve learning and long-term retention (Karpicke & Roediger, 2007). This retentive learning is described in the study as deferred conceptual understanding. A lack of continued practice (Ritter et al., 2013) degrades performance. That is why, by providing alternative learning activities and environments (such as games, activities, and simulations) with meaningful repetition (Chow et al., 2011), repeated retrieval of information (Karpicke

& Roediger, 2007), and studying information on multiple occasions (Cepeda et al., 2008), student direct conceptual understanding, and long-term retention can be enhanced or improved.

In most learning processes, assessing the retention of information is considered (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Nurisya et al., 2016; Talar & Gozaly, 2020). The ability to still remember concepts, and details in memory (Tapilow & Wawan, 2008) for a particular timeframe is referred to as retention, and this is crucial in the teaching and learning process (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). Retention is not only limited to recalling facts and information, but also a way in developing critical thinking, creativity, relationship between concepts, and transfer of understanding (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Haniah et al., 2020; Sholihah & Lastariwati, 2020).

Related to learning performance is the students' ability to accomplish school works. This is self-efficacy, which includes internal behaviors such as judgments about one's capacity to finish a task or goal (Harsch, 2008; Schunk & Miller, 2002; Riskiningtyas & Wangid, 2019) and confidence in one's performance and abilities (Pintrich et al., 1991; Grabau, 2015). When faced with a problem, students who have a strong belief in their ability to learn would participate more readily, work more, and stay longer than students who have low self-efficacy (Riskiningtyas, & Wangid, 2019). In this context, a student's self-efficacy while learning online is influenced by their confidence in their ability to interact in an online environment (Code et al., 2021).

Traditionally, teachers during class provide learning opportunities and deliver instructions. After that, students do tasks or exercises outside of class to reinforce the teacher's explanations and improve retention of learning in the subject (Romero-García et al., 2018). In the new normal, as the Department of Education (DepEd) has been making all necessary improvements and working on advancing the processes

for the various platforms (MENA Report, 2021), classes under its developed Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) would take the form of online learning, distance learning, homeschooling, limited face-to-face interactions, virtual classes, the use of radio and television, or any of their combinations as platforms for continuing education.

Biology Education aims to provide learners with practical understanding, interests, and appreciation of life sciences. To improve the quality of Biology teaching and learning experience, it is necessary to embrace innovations, upgrade programs and curriculum, and create responsive and appropriate instructional materials and pedagogy. Citing Bond (2020), the inverted or flipped learning approach is gaining popularity in both higher education and K-12, owing to its potential to increase active learning and student engagement. It is a relatively new pedagogical method at the secondary level (OffermanCelentano, 2017), and it is gaining traction among researchers and educators (Evseeva & Solozhenko, 2015), especially in the new normal. The Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) aims to increase in-class time for activities that improve student learning while moving some content delivery outside the classroom using short instructional videos, including doing practical tasks through learning and teaching discussion/peer collaborative work (Barral et al., 2018; González-Gómez et al., 2016; Chang & Hwang, 2018). Even though this has been implemented in a variety of educational settings (Kim et al., 2014; Christiansen et al., 2017; Rossi, 2015; Lee, & Park, 2018; Burkhart et al., 2020), many variables related to inverted learning remain unknown (Strohmyer, 2016). Similarly, there is limited evidence supporting the efficacy of this approach in an online or a virtual environment among high school biology students.

There is still paucity of information regarding the role of Inverted Learning Approach

(ILA) in the improvement of one's efficacy, motivation, self-regulation, and retention (Chickering & Gamson, 1987; Grabau, 2015). As it is now, it seems that there is already information that ILA is not at all effective in improving these variables as there is only less scientific proof that tells this. Thus, this study has investigated how students could successfully examine whether the new norm of learning such as the use of ILA is working for them (Pintrich, 2004; Sletten, 2015; Grabau, 2015).

Therefore, this study was focused on how Inverted (or Flipped) Learning Approach, as a relatively new pedagogical approach at the secondary level (Offerman-Celentano, 2017), was relevant for application affecting how students gain conceptual understanding and learning retention in this time of changing educational landscape. It further delved into how the approach could affect learners' self-efficacy, which indicates how they feel about themselves, their firsthand experience and as well as their drive and level of confidence in learning quarter-long topics in Biology. Finally, the it developed a comprehensive instructional improvement for the implementation of the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) in Biology. The framework is based on the experiences of students who were exposed to ILA. As a result, this data can have an impact on instructional design by providing evidence-based recommendations for educators looking to improve their instructional practices.

Statement of the Problem

The study zeroed in on the effect of inverted learning approach on students' self-efficacy, as well as direct and deferred conceptual understanding in Biology. It sought to address the following queries:

1. How is the conceptual understanding in Biology of students exposed to the inverted learning approach (intervention) and expository online teaching (conventional) comparable in terms of their pretest, posttest, and retention test scores?
2. How is the conceptual understanding in Biology of students exposed to inverted learning approach improved in terms of their pretest, posttest, and retention test scores?
3. What is the level of students' self-efficacy as exposed to:
 - a. expository online teaching (EOT)?
 - b. inverted learning approach (ILA)?
4. Is there a difference in the self-efficacy levels between intervention and conventional groups?
5. How are the direct and the deferred conceptual understanding of ILA students related to their level of self-efficacy?
6. Why would the inverted learning approach be adopted in teaching Biology based on the lived experiences of STEM Students?

Significance of the study

The use of the inverted learning approach has a greater impact on improving the quality of science education in the country. It proposes a relevant and technology-driven way of viewing the teaching-learning landscape. It flips the roles of teachers

and students, making students active learners rather than passive ones. Through inverted learning, students' critical thinking, confidence, and higher order thinking skills will be developed because of having enough time and space to explore, practice, and understand the subject matter. Teachers, on the other hand, will be viewed as facilitators of learning among 21st century learners rather than as a source of information.

Furthermore, teachers can use this approach to address congested learning competencies that are supposed to be covered in a given time in the curriculum guide, freeing up more time for teachers to create more student-centered activities without having to practically repeat the same topic if they handle more classes. The approach is based on the most convenient learning environment for Generation Z students, which is virtual or cyberspace. These learners are already accustomed to this type of environment and were even born with this technological advantage; thus, ILA regards one factor that allows them to be more motivated and comfortable while learning.

Fundamentally, the results of this study can help the curriculum developers and designers to create a more technology-based instructional program/ intervention in the transition to online learning as a new normal learning set-up and partner with professional teachers and experts to effectively implement inverted learning approach as one 21st century learning approach critical for carrying out the competencies and standards. This proposes an innovative instructional paradigm to both teachers and students make the best use of the available low and high technology for teaching and learning. It likewise helps leverage teachers' differential knowledge and skills, such as technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge, as well as varying levels of students' achievements, motivation, and learning preferences.

This study will also furnish relevant information to the top and middle administrators of the school who are pushing through the utilization of technology-based approaches in teaching considering the different ways students learn under this new normal set-up; they may consider offering different modes of learning where learners have the option to choose from, be it blended, fully online, or hybridized; to the academic and subject area coordinators of the school who are leading their respective members of the department to look for better and relevant new normal pedagogies.

The science teachers, most especially, will also benefit from the study as they will be adding more research-based teaching methods to improve the teaching-learning experience in their science classes. They will be helped in carrying out activities in seamless ways and enabled to show more and process deeply students' questions and teach the subject matter beyond traditional; to the teachers in different learning areas will also be able to consider Inverted Learning Approach to address their problems on how to maximize learning time and meet the required learning competencies in the new normal set-up and to make use of this approach whenever applicable, possible, and appropriate.

Moreover, this will furnish the pre-service teachers in science education to regard the evidence of the benefits of this approach and to consider as one of their approaches in dealing with blended, flexible, and online and distance learning. Given enough preparation time, they will see how this can improve the teaching-learning experience.

The findings can assist the implementers of the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) in exploring social media platforms where the approach can be most advantageous. It can be an innovative pedagogy for new normal educational set-up. They will be informed how to improve the development of learning materials, how to use high and

low technology, how to improve learning experiences and engagement, and how to integrate other pedagogies for adoption.

Finally, future researchers on the use of ILA will be able to consider various research designs that will be appropriate while providing them with richer information and experiences to better appreciate the approach.

Scope and Delimitation of Study

Even though inverted (also known as flipped) learning is increasingly becoming popular in education, there is still a gap in research on this method at secondary or basic education level. The paper focused on determining whether inverted learning approach has an effect on the self-efficacy of students, their lived experiences having taught by this kind of teaching-learning approach, as well as their conceptual understanding in terms of the direct and deferred learning in the Senior High School Biology Topics, which are covered fully during the second quarter of the First Semester for the S.Y. 2022-2023 as prescribed from the K to 12 curriculum guide of the Department of Education, revised in August 2016. One quarter lasted for 10 weeks or 40 class hours, excluding the examination days and holidays. It took place from October to December 2022.

Thus, the researcher purposely chose the topic of Bioenergetics, which includes Photosynthesis and Cellular Respiration, being among the most difficult to learn content in General Biology. The thrust of biology education has changed from memorization to depth of understanding of core biological concepts such as matter and energy relationships (Uhl et al., 2021), particularly in learning the intricate nature of metabolic pathways that are difficult to understand (Jain et al., 2021), such as

photosynthesis, cellular respiration (Çingil Barış, 2022; Atilla (2012), ATP as the energy currency of the cell (Fontecilla-Camps, 2022), and energy transfer in an ecosystem (Yoon & Karpudewan, 2022).

The study utilized the quasi-experimental setup but the assignment of participants to the intervention and conventional groups was done randomly. To reduce differential selection, the equivalence of groups was determined using their Pretest scores. This ensures that the subjects' levels of achievement are homogenized from the start of the study, allowing any performance result to be attributed to the instructional approach used.

The teacher-researcher was assigned to teach the subject so that students would not be sensitized that they are used for an experiment. This also kept them from acting differently or faking their responses. The students' retention of the concepts was measured by administering the retention test a month after they took the post test. The one-month gap was consulted with an expert to ensure that the gap period is neither too short nor too long for such a measurement.

Inverted learning approach (ILA) is the instructional intervention used in the study which allows students learn new material outside of class by accessing the lesson content ahead of time and then use class time for discussion, collaboration, and activities. This is compared with Expository Online Teaching (EOT) as the conventional teaching approach. While ILA can be an effective way to interact with students and promote active learning, there are several drawbacks to adopt this method, including: a) access to technology, which students must connect to the internet to be able to interact with the learning resources. If students do not have gadgets or computers, they may be at a disadvantage; b) challenging part on the students to self-pace their learning and always sustain their motivation; c) Learning

can be affected by some educational inequities, such as technology divide and lack of materials; and d) Face-to-face interaction between teachers and students may be limited to none. While these limitations must be considered when implementing ILA, they can be mitigated with careful planning and consideration of students' needs and resources and teacher's preparation.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter presents a systematic review of related studies and literature obtained from up-to-date e-books, current journal articles, published research, and web links. The research hypotheses, definition of terms, and theoretical and conceptual frameworks are also presented.

STEM Education: Global, Regional, and the Philippines

STEM Education: State and Challenges

Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math (STEM) education has grown in importance in many countries around the world in recent years (Thao et al., 2020). There has been a global shift toward STEM, as detailed by government efforts around the world to develop STEM policies governing school science and mathematics, as well as tertiary level education and research in STEM disciplines (Freeman et al., 2019). This is consistent with the findings of Bacovic et al. (2021), who found a strong linear relationship between the country's science and technical education, output structure, income per person, and productivity growth, and that STEM-educated workers contribute significantly to output growth. As a result, appropriate avenues for faculty training, upskilling, and initiatives to improve STEM education and promote STEM careers should be available, taking into account students' self-efficacy, self-determination, and career path (Razali et al., 2020).

STEM education and research are ever more being recognized throughout the world as critical to national growth and advancement, competitiveness, and

broader social well-being (Freeman et al., 2019). Indeed, countries ranging from the Anglosphere to East Asia, Western Europe, and Latin America to the Middle East have identified noticeable trends and correlations in government STEM policy, projects, and structural responses, school and higher education level STEM education involvement, performance information measured by international studies such as PISA and TIMSS, STEM research and innovation, and gender and under-represented groups concerns (Freeman et al., 2019).

Conferring to Bacovic et al. (2021), STEM skills and commitment to innovation have a positive effect on GDP per person growth and productivity, and its growth is crucial to encourage economic progress. Thus, there is a need to showcase various programs and solutions, such as school-level curriculum and pedagogy restructure to improve science and mathematics involvement and participation, teaching-related programs, and tertiary-level efforts to address current systemic inequities (Freeman et al., 2019). Thao et al. (2020) investigated the scientific results of STEM education in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) region, which were indexed in the Scopus database from 2000 to 2019 and reported that the trend of research in this field has shown a marked increase in research publications in the last three years, with diverse studies on basic and cross-cutting topics focusing on STEM education. Singapore can serve as an inspiration by observing its education system, the teaching method, the STEM approach, the use of diverse and student-centered learning models, an effective and efficient information management system, and STEM products (Kristien, 2019).

Along with the importance of the content and analysis of the preparatory course for teachers in the field of STEM education, identifying the most appropriate STEM education concepts, and developing better training courses to enhance

STEM qualifications of secondary school teachers (Torop et al., 2021), the knowledge and skills involving the arts that are required to work in STEM education are introduced. In addition, the attitude, motivation, and career outcome expectancy are positive and significant predictors of STEM self-efficacy, whereas gender and teacher stereotypes are negative predictors, highlighting self-efficacy as a strong predictor of decision to pursue STEM education citing Alam et al. (2021).

In 1995, the Science Education Institute (SEI) of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) led the largest educational revolution in Philippine history by steering the Department of Education, Culture, and Sports (DECS) to mold young citizens who are scientifically and technologically keen into the best manpower for the country's socioeconomic development. As the country embraces K to 12 education system, part of this revolution entails providing special science classes with a curriculum that includes more science, mathematics, and scientific research subjects than the basic education curriculum (Aron, 2020). Thus, some of the requirements of the K-12 science curriculum include science inquiry skills, localization, and contextualization (Gonzaga-Leong-on, 2020).

A common impediment to effective science education in schools is the lack of teaching materials. For meaningful learning to occur in the twenty-first century, direct visualization and manipulation with effective use and implementation are required, thus students can unlock their potential towards the learning experience, bolster their engagement in learning, and apply their knowledge into abilities (Gamale et al., 2020). As technology advances, so does the growth of digital instructional materials (Funa & Ricafort, 2019). Therefore, the Department of Education (DepEd) now encourages educators to create and innovate instructional materials. However, following Landicho (2020), the quality of education is primarily

determined by the quality of teachers. This is especially true in the case of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education. That means to say that quality education rely not only on the learning materials but also on the preparation of the teachers.

STEM education stresses research content in instruction delivery (Nozaleda, 2021), while also providing opportunities for learners to participate throughout the learning process. STEM teachers have a positive attitude toward research and see it as a means of professional development. They also recognized the positive benefits of research on their teaching abilities and the learning experiences of their students (Landicho, 2020). Conducting science investigative projects is one way to spark students' interest in STEM because it perpetuates creativity and other higher order thinking skills that allow them to innovate, improvise, and solve problems. Besides this, teacher preparation and teaching strategies that would suit their students' learning styles should be considered, as should the students explore an appropriate instructional style to maximize their development (Ramos, & Ramos, 2019). The various instructional strategies of the teacher therefore influence effective learning.

As supported by Nozaleda (2021), STEM teachers place a premium on research in the classroom. The development of creative and critical dispositions was cited as one of the most important goals of incorporating research into teaching. The teachers, on the other hand, reported low actual integration of research into their current teaching, revealing a significant gap between their beliefs and the perceived actual integration of research into their teaching practices.

At the present time, the pressing challenge of continuing education amid a pandemic has been exacerbated by a lack of preparation, facilities such as gadgets or computer sets, and connectivity (Tupas & Linas-Laguda, 2020). As an outcome, the blended learning (BL) modality is used to help students engage favorably in all activities and increase their behavior toward learning, as well as to enable them to become leaders, coaches, and mentors to their peers. The Department of Education (DepEd) proposed using online learning, a modular approach, radio-television methods, and any combination of these methods for a blended learning setup at the secondary level (Tupas et al., 2020).

To address the current challenge, a research-based teaching-learning approach is required. As teachers respond to this emergency remote teaching (Walsh et al., 2021), there is also a necessity of training faculty, including experienced instructors, to improve emergency preparedness in process of adapting to teaching in an online environment (Davis-Berg & Kocot, 2021) employing student-centered research and learning strategies. It is all about the students when it comes to teaching. To teach well is to facilitate student's learning so that he or she feels successful about it. *"Learning success is an emotional success, and an effective teacher recognizes this emotional foundation for learning"* (Zull, 2020). This refers to as the affective learning domain. Moreover, preparation and use of correct tools in teaching help make learning the information become effective, permanent, and impactful in creating an engaging and conducive classroom environment (Sayan & Mertolu, 2020). With the technological advancements of the twenty-first century (Karakoyun and Yapici, 2016), it is now critical to successfully integrate technological additions into teaching-learning environments.

Students who engage in socio-scientific issues can acquire some of the complex skills and competencies associated with scientific literacy, this is acknowledged by Tidemand and Nielsen (2017). However, there is a growing body of research on science teachers' understanding and application of socio-scientific issues as a vehicle for teaching factual content. Science education plays an important role in developing individuals with 21st-century skills who can adapt to a developing world. Biology is a branch of science education that covers information that people can use in their daily lives. This emphasizes the importance of biology education, and in the same way, teachers bear significant responsibilities in the implementation of effective biology instruction (Sayan and Mertolu, 2020).

Students' critical thinking skills can be improved with contextual learning (Hasruddin et al., 2015) by leveraging a variety of approaches that allow for the integration of technology into teaching-learning environments. Some of these approaches include computer-assisted instruction (Chaudhari, 2013); interesting activities involving digital storytelling (Karakoyun & Yapici, 2016); and the progression of creative thinking, information literacy and exchange, cooperation, research skills, technology, and media literacy skills via 'Slowmation' (Karakoyun & Yapici, 2018); cartoons as a teaching tool (Köse, 2013); informative booklet research-based teaching (Suniah et al., 2018); online cell biology lab alternatives (Delgado et al., 2020); instructional packages (GonzagaLeong-on, 2020); Strategic Intervention Material (SIM)-based Instruction (Gabucan, & Sanchez, 2021); having teaching assistants (Hughes & Ellefson, 2013); and especially flipped learning where autonomy is reinforced (Gariou-Papalexiou et al., 2017), classroom management can be improved (Gariou-Papalexiou et al., 2017); and active learning is demonstrated in the implementation of digital activities completed from a distance.

Overall, the concept of flipping gives a new perspective and potential to the limited options of conventional education.

STEM Education during the Pandemic

Because of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020, education systems were forced to quickly shift to online learning. Many educators were concerned that the impact of the crisis would aggravate social inequalities in learning outcomes and student learning opportunities, particularly for students from underrepresented groups (Zuckerman et al., 2021). Remote access to tools has increased the utility of virtual labs and has become a basic laboratory constituent. Science concepts can be enhanced in terms of student attention, and virtual laboratories could be an appropriate platform and effective teaching methods. The contribution of virtual laboratories in biological sciences education to improve quality education and collaborative learning through flexible pedagogies is examined to improve teaching in the field (Manchikanti et al., 2016).

There are digital practices that have been used in teaching at various levels. Conferring to Chiu and Piontkivska (2021), remote delivery presents numerous challenges, particularly for discussion-based classes. There are virtual laboratories that promote Internet-based learning using online protocols, simulation software, motion graphics, video tutorials, self-evaluation tailored to each objective, and experimentations in any field of science and technology (Manchikanti et al., 2016). Further to that, Gya and Bjune (2021) and Davis-Berg and Kocot (2021) underline how do-it-yourself (DIY) at home experiments can be a good way to include physical interaction with study species, system, or technique to give varied students more

adequately practical and authentic learning experience for how to best move conventionally hands-on laboratories into online formats; while Copley et al. (2021) suggest worksheets to guide students as they explored how students answer questions about the content in pairs and reflect on how the ideas in the documents related to current scientific understanding.

Active learning activities that let model exploration and simulation are another viable way to make these models more approachable, which rendered students got significant gains in their confidence and understanding of the concepts (McGuire et al., 2021). Copley et al. (2021) describe a library-based activity that allows students in an undergraduate microbiology class to investigate this relationship for centuries, with the library serving as a laboratory. This method can be applied to a variety of biology courses and educational levels.

Undergraduate students in STEM disciplines can benefit from authentic learning experiences and the acquisition of valuable skills through practical teaching. Citizen science projects, on the other hand, can be used in college laboratory settings to provide students with hands-on research experience during emergency remote learning (Lichti et al., 2021). Using citizen science during remote teaching allowed students to gain authentic research experiences and develop their skillset even when they were unable to be in the laboratory (Lichti et al., 2021). Similarly, the concept of the digital internship by Boury et al. (2021) can furnish students with a unique opportunity to develop critical, technical, and scientific thinking skills while also generating convenient open education resources in the form of annotated podcasts. And there is also a class management model that employs a conversational approach (Chiu and Piontkivska, 2021) simulating various aspects of the process of science, such as posing questions and creating hypotheses and is

directed at an emergent subject, such as COVID-19. This would have allowed students to connect their existing knowledge with new insights about SARS-CoV2, as shown by student feedback, and a way of connecting learning to real-world applications.

Human adaptability was at its peak during the COVID-19 period (Tehelka, 2020). The crisis has had a significant impact on countries all over the world. India was among the first countries to embrace various digital services for continuing education (Nair, 2020). Lessons are delivered via web conferencing and other online tools, and recorded learning modules and worksheets are shared via an LMS. India has no choice but to embrace technology (Tehelka, 2020). Students in India find online learning to be more enjoyable because it is more convenient and interactive than traditional classroom instruction (Sharma, 2020). Furthermore, they can use technology to do their task more effectively, learn at their own pace, and have immediate access to their teachers. The experience with online classes has been entirely positive. This new learning system has advantages such as more time to complete assignments at home and ensuring the safety of both teachers and students (Sharma, 2020).

Another positive view of online learning is mentioned in Columbia, where most students (56%) and parents (74%) concur that the future of high school will include a combination of online and in-person education. They have supported the online learning program (PR Newswire, 2020). However, as reported in Ghana News Agency (2020), inadequate infrastructure causes problems for parents, teachers, and school authorities in basic public schools as they attempt to adjust to the new normal in their country. Despite the efforts and advances made, it is possible to observe in Brazil a magnitude of struggles that required competencies from teachers that were not

anticipated in their academic training, such as consultations through the resources of Digital Information and Communication Technologies (DICTs), revealing a significant deficit in teacher training for the new normal (Cara et al., 2022).

Among ASEAN countries, such as Thailand, the digital divide caused by societal inequalities, demographic, and/or educational factors became more recognizable during the pandemic, which schools and universities were urged to shift from traditional face-to-face to synchronous teaching (Rofiah et al., 2022). In Malaysia, teachers at one public higher learning institution were eager to begin transformative emergency remote teaching but were unclear about the distinctions between emergency remote teaching and online teaching (Juhary, 2020). Even though they were able to effectively utilize platforms and applications during the pandemic, they did not have enough time to learn other platforms and applications.

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, as evidenced by Nguyen et al. (2021), has already had a significant impact also on teaching and learning in Vietnam's higher education institutions. Video conferencing tools (VCTs) were used across the country to ensure effective responses during this unexpected event. Indonesia also immediately adapted to conditions to contain the spread of this virus. Schools and universities agreed to shift learning activities to distance learning systems. However, poor implementation has exacerbated the situation, with students experiencing significant stress because of insufficient distance learning management (Churiyah et al., 2020).

Teaching Innovations: Pandemic and Post-Pandemic

The Philippines has always overcome numerous curriculum experiments in the past and will continue to do so in the coming years as the COVID-19 pandemic wreaks disruptions on the education sector (Toquero, 2020). The country must adopt distance learning, with the Department of Education (DepEd) making all necessary improvements and working on improving the processes for the various platforms (MENA Report, 2021). DepEd has already published guidelines under the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) that specify the various teaching modalities for offline and online interactions (MENA Report, 2020). Classes under the LCP will take the form of online learning, homeschooling, limited face-to-face interactions, virtual classes, the use of radio and television as platforms, or any of these combinations, for continuing education.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, various educational institutions transitioned their face-to-face teaching modality to a virtual modality or an online platform (Jiménez et al., 2021). Traditional teaching methods frequently result in lower learning gains, fear, and negative perceptions among students (Matawali et al., 2019). That is why many core concepts are being introduced outside of the classroom before scheduled class meeting times, and there are alternative instructional methodologies such as active learning and flipped classrooms, which invert traditional teaching methods (Silva & Galembeck, 2014; Goff et al., 2018). Also, there are stand-alone online learning modules used in many undergraduate biology courses (Goff et al., 2018) that significantly increased students' standardized gain scores on a cellular respiration assessment, and online lab opportunities carefully designed to engage students with inquiry-based activities to replace wet labs (Son, 2016).

Working from home digitally has been considered during the state of emergency (Carvalho et al., 2022); and the application of distance learning is essential to maintain the continuity of education after the physical shutdown of schools. Considering this situation, the learners are most likely to encounter a learning loss during the block. That is why remote emergency activities using Information and Communication Technologies were required in education to allow students to continue their studies (Cara et al., 2022; Martins et al., 2022). Besides this, the physical distance and the use of technologies enabled them to reduce separation distance and increase social interaction for an efficient teaching-learning process during times of crisis (Martins et al., 2022).

Because schools have adopted an online learning modality to keep the teaching-learning process going during the pandemic, technology integration into education has had an impact on how today's students learn (Tang et al., 2020). This has also become a challenge for teachers to deliver instruction outside of the norm, such as transitioning from the board and chalk model to tablet and virtual classrooms (Nair, 2020) at a rapid pace without compromising learning quality. Online classes are a better learning platform during these unprecedented times, and they have greatly aided students by allowing them to stay at home and study without fear of contracting the virus (Sharma, 2020).

Education in the new normal entails virtual learning and online classes (Fahim, 2021), with extensive teacher and student roles (Business World, 2020). Doing online lectures requires time, effort, and planning (Lal, 2020), unlike the traditional teaching comparably is much convenient for most teachers and students. According to a World Economic Forum report (Nair, 2020), the concept of teachers as experts who impart wisdom to their students is no longer appropriate for twenty-

first-century education. Everyone is on social media and attempting to share information on social media platforms because access to knowledge and technological skill is possible with a few clicks on their phones, tablets, and computers (Tehelka, 2020).

The inverted learning approach is regarded as a pedagogical innovation resulting from technological influence in learning environments (López Belmonte et al., 2019). In an expository online approach, students are taught in a lecture discussion format and all information is almost spoon fed to them. By contrast, inverted learning is an approach to teaching where students are actively involved in their own learning; thus, supporting to develop their self-efficacy as learners.

When given enough preparations for technology integration, inverted learning or flipping may be possible. Using an inverted classroom, students showed an increased awareness of the importance of self-learning and the advantage of taking responsibility for their learning (Mason et al., 2013). It had a positive effect on both the academic level of students, the work of class activities, the promotion of working in a team among students, and the changing roles of teachers and students. However, in the study of Tsai et al. (2017), the treatment of flipped learning did not always result in positive results because the approach did not result in better development of students' computing skills for using Microsoft Word and PowerPoint when students may lack confidence and are unwilling to ask questions or seek help. Students were generally dissatisfied with online learning, but incorporating the online model with inverted learning improved students' learning, focus, and course assessment (Tang et al., 2020). From the narrative systematic review of literature focused on the flipped learning approach in K-12 contexts of Bond (2020), it however

revealed that most of the research was heavily based on student perceptions of flipped and academic outcomes within STEM subjects, particularly Mathematics.

Inverted Learning Approach (ILA)

ILA: Description

Student-centered instruction, including active, participatory, and problem-based learning, is widely recognized for its educational benefits. Educators, in spite of this, are often hesitant to implement learner-centered activities because they believe it will take more time and that can reduce class content coverage (Mason et al., 2013). With the adoption of digital learning and the development of educational technologies (Tsai et al., 2017), this learner-centered instruction may be possible by developing a good learning environment and that is to make learning an active and reciprocal process (Jakobsen & Knetemann, 2017).

As per Bond (2020), the inverted or flipped learning approach is gaining popularity in both higher education and K-12, owing to its potential to increase active learning and student engagement. It has become a popular instructional method, but little is known about its connection with learners' emotions, which are known to play a significant role in science education (Jdaitawi, 2020). The approach promotes interaction between faculty and students, concentrates on problem-solving (Le et al., 2015), and frees up classroom time for learner-centered tasks (Mason et al., 2013), encourages students for becoming self-learners and prepares them for how they will need to learn (Mason et al., 2013), demonstrates improvement in self-directed learning and problem-solving skills without sacrificing knowledge of

fundamental concepts (Rutar et al., 2016), reflects a high improvement in academic performance (Meléndez & Iza, 2017) and has a positive impact in students' learning emotions (Jdaitawi, 2020; Jeong et al., 2021).

Inverted learning, also known as flipped learning, is a relatively new pedagogical method at the secondary level (Offerman-Celentano, 2017). It is gaining traction among researchers and educators (Evseeva & Solozhenko, 2015), especially in this new normal setup. Teachers will have more time to devote to student-centered, active learning strategies in which students can connect and demonstrate their understanding of the content delivery component of a class is removed from the traditional classroom setup (Jakobsen & Knetemann, 2017; Arfstrom & Network, 2013; Sletten, 2015).

Inverted instruction can be used as an alternative approach to providing a student-centered class (Jeong et al., 2021). It highlights a learner-centered and results-oriented approach (Ho, 2020). Students learn the primary course content outside of class in this inverted format (Jakobsen & Knetemann, 2017; Gross & Musselman, 2015; Mason et al., 2013). Moreover, it makes use of digital tools to deliver content outside of the classroom (Rutar et al., 2016), such as teacher-prepared recordings, presentations, or even content culled from a variety of sources (Romero-Garcia et al., 2018; Lee & Park, 2018; Ho, 2020).

Types and Applications of ILA

The flipped or inverted learning is regarded as a pedagogical innovation resulting from technological influence in learning environments (López- Belmonte et al., 2019). The popularity of learning approaches such as flipped learning is

increasing all over the world. It has been described as a useful tool in science education for improving students' learning, personal, social, and cognitive skills (Imam Abdulrahman Bin, 2021).

Inverted classes citing López-Belmonte et al. (2020) may be done using gamification, cooperative flipped (Lee et al., 2021), flipping thru Facebook (Jamridafrizal & Wibawa, 2021), inquiry-based for science teaching and learning (Tan et al., 2020), and remote sensing (Núñez et al., 2020) for contents related to environmental sciences. Rosa (2021) describes this instructional approach as an innovative methodology in the teaching and learning process, as opposed to the traditional arrangement where synchronous and asynchronous group work between student groups who are active participants in their learning. Talley & Scherer (2013) increased the academic achievement of learners by using flipped format, learning techniques, self-explanation, and practice testing. These techniques resulted in more time spent studying course material and higher exam grades. As a result, the incorporation of effective learning techniques into STEM courses may play a significant role in increasing retention in STEM disciplines.

Science teachers are encouraged to use teaching strategies developed from the use of modern technologies, particularly the inverted learning strategy, to teach their students (Elian & Hamaidi, 2018). It was also suggested that prospective teachers be trained on the use of teaching strategies as the inverted learning, which improves motivation and skills (López- Belmonte et al., 2019) and develops students' reflective thinking in science subjects (Ahmed, 2020). Inverted learning has grown in popularity over the last decade, and it has been used and studied in a variety of educational settings (Bergmann & Sams, 2012; van Alten et al., 2019). However, it is still a relatively new pedagogical strategy at the secondary or high

school level (Offerman-Celentano, 2017), with little research on how it is currently being implemented and what teachers think about it (Largo, 2017).

Because Generation Z students have short attention spans and multi-task on various digital screens (Alvarado et al., 2020), they must be engaged in a deeper level of understanding by relating the theory with practice (Konijn et al., 2018). This may be addressed using the inverted learning approach. Inverted or flipped learning revolutionizes traditional teaching methods and highlights students' active learning (Shao, & Liu, 2021).

The Virtual Flipped Classroom (VFC) is a combination of two concepts: Flipped Classroom and Virtual Classroom (Ahmed, & Abdulla, 2019), but Martinelli & Zaina (2021) still regard this VFC as a blended strategy that divides the learning process into two distinct moments called out of class and in-class, although they are conducted virtually. This learning approach allows teachers to teach and efficiently guide students in implementing the activities required to achieve the best learning levels during the distance learning period (Vavichkina, 2020). While according to Phillips and O'Flaherty (2019), this as a learning model allots more time for active instructional strategies when compared to more traditional pedagogies. It gives students more opportunities to develop higher-order thinking skills (HOTs) like laboratory courses (Ahmed & Asiksoy, 2021).

A virtual flipped classroom environment can help students improve their creative thinking and ICT literacy by using various types of scaffolding systems (Trairut & Jeerungsuwan, 2016). It has shown a statistically significant difference in learners' learning achievement and motivation (Ahmed & Abdulla, 2019). Thus, this digital learning and educational technology practice could be adopted or implemented at the primary and secondary levels of education (Fragkaki et al.,

2020). This, in turn, promotes students' autonomy and collaboration, despite the challenges they confronted during COVID-19 (Martinelli & Zaina, 2021).

The virtual format is efficient in delivering course content and has the potential to connect a broader audience by giving the students more time to develop HOTS and engage more deeply in the learning process (Phillips & O'Flaherty, 2019; Cook et al., 2021). For example, using gamified flipped learning in a virtual physics laboratory course resulted in a positive impact on students' innovation skills (Ahmed & Asiksoy, 2021); and using web-based virtual labs (VLs) to replace traditional physical labs (PLs) has a positive effect on learning and attitudes in a newly designed general education undergraduate biology course (Son et al., 2016).

Impacts on Students' Learning

Zoom, YouTube, Bandicam, Filmora, CapCut and Screencorder are some of the technology solutions used to record and generate video lessons and web tutorials for use in inverted learning, in addition to assigned reading materials, interactive activities, and presentation slides with voice-over (Mason et al., 2013). Students can use these to access learning materials ahead of time and at their own pace. They can also devote more time in synchronous classes to collaborative and higher-order learning activities like discussions and problem-solving, while also encouraging students to demonstrate their learning (Rutar et al., 2016; Romero-Garcia et al., 2018; Lin, 2019; Davies et al., 2013; Bergmann, & Sams, 2012).

The use of inverted instruction has some initial backlash from students to the new format (Mason et al., 2013) and it took them several weeks to adjust, so inverted learning should be put in place for an entire term to reap the full benefits of the

approach (Mason, et al., 2013). While in Le et al. (2015), students with higher grades in the traditional classroom approach liked the flipped classroom approach, and students with middling or lower grades in the traditional classroom approach disliked the flipped classroom approach. On the positive side, there are also students who have positive attitudes toward the use of inverted learning, and many of them would strongly suggest it for other courses. Biju et al. (2020) regarded flipped concepts as an effective approach to teaching students at varying levels in academia. This likewise improved students' learning outcomes (Zainuddin & Halili, 2016) such as learning achievement (Turan & Goktas, 2016), determination, experience (Konijn et al., 2018), connection and engagement (SteenUtheim, & Foldnes, 2018).

Investigating the traditions, transitions, and best practices in Technology Integration in STEAM (science, technology, engineering, agri-fisheries, and mathematics), teachers prefer traditional techniques and have a low level of engagement with web and learning applications in the perspective of pedagogy and content/discipline, and learners (Morales et al., 2021). However, when given enough preparations for technology integration, inverted learning or flipping may be possible. When doing flipped learning, the video-lectures do not need to be high-production-quality, but rather content-focused and concise (Mason et al., 2013).

Inverted Learning is a modern model in teaching-learning activities for students in grades K-12 (Zainuddin & Halili, 2016). It is a field of interest, which is rapidly growing, with a focus on STEM and higher education (Lundin et al., 2018). This approach provides learners with favorable, comfortable, enabling, and social learning experiences (SteenUtheim & Foldnes, 2018). It has also benefited shy and quiet students, and full-time students to allocate more time for learning (Zainuddin & Attaran, 2016).

Online ILA and Students' Learning

Students' Direct and Deferred Conceptual Understanding and Self-Efficacy

Inverted Learning is a pedagogical approach (Shahnama et al., 2021) that has received widespread attention in the last decade, particularly in higher education as an option to more conventional teaching methods (Lundin et al., 2018). It is based on the idea that students must complete pre-class learning assignments or lectures outside of class (Rawas et al., 2020; Shahnama et al., 2021), followed by high-quality, more class time dedicated to cooperative learning, individually tailored, and differentiated learning, and concept application activities during class time (Delozier, & Rhodes, 2017; Olalekan et al., 2020).

Active learning is the most intervening variable of success in classroom flipping (Jensen et al., 2015). The inverted classroom design with group-based face-to-face class activities produced higher test scores than the design with individual face-to-face class activities (Rawas et al., 2020). This is supported by Zhao and Wang (2018), who claimed that when students participated in flipped learning activities, they were more active in cooperating, interacting, and explaining with their peers than when they were in a traditional class. Flipped classroom interventions produced positive gains in all three learning domains (Bredow et al., 2021), namely academic, intra-/interpersonal, and satisfaction-related outcomes in higher education. But some difficulties affecting student learning encountered by Zainuddin and Halili (2016) in implementing flipped learning include poor video lecture quality and an untrained instructor.

Because learning gains may be forgotten, it is crucial to focus on efficient teaching strategies that encourage students to learn and form meaningful associations, resulting in learning that lasts longer (Al-Balushi & Al-Balushi, 2018). Tests not only measure stored information, but they can also improve learning and long-term retention (Karpicke & Roediger, 2007). However, as the test delay increases, so does the optimal gap (Cepeda et al., 2008). That is why, by providing alternative learning activities and environments, such as games, activities, and simulations, with meaningful repetition (Chow et al., 2011), repeated retrieval of information (Karpicke & Roediger, 2007), and studying information on multiple occasions (Cepeda et al., 2008), student understanding and long-term retention can be enhanced and improved; thus a lack of continued practice (Ritter et al., 2013) degrades the performance.

When students practice recovering previously studied information, they can achieve higher long-term retentive learning than simply reviewing or restudying (Nero & Zulkipli, 2021). This process is called as the testing effect (Carpenter et al., 2006; McDaniel et al., 2007; Nero & Zulkipli, 2021) or the retrieval practice effect (Carpenter et al., 2006; Karpicke & Roediger, 2007; Nero & Zulkipli, 2021). In most learning processes, retention of information is considered (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Nurisya et al., 2016; Talar & Gozaly, 2020). The ability to still remember concepts, and details in memory (Tapilow & Wawan, 2008) for a particular timeframe is referred to as retention, and this is crucial in the teaching and learning process (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). Retention is not only limited to recalling facts and information, but also a way in developing critical thinking, creativity, relationship between concepts, and transfer of understanding (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Haniah et al., 2020; Sholihah & Lastariwati, 2020).

Students' conceptual understanding was assessed using summative assessments administered in both synchronous and asynchronous sessions (L. Pinar, 2021) during the COVID-19 pandemic, which compels educational institutions to cancel face-to-face classes, resulting in a paradigm shift toward online learning and assessing. To continue providing education amid the crisis, innovative learning strategies were encouraged. This resulted in the transformation of classroom-oriented learning resources into distance learning-adapted learning resources, and innovations in teaching science. Secondary level biology academic performance has not been as good as expected (Bizimana et al., 2022). As a result, there has been a consistent emphasis on discovering emerging innovative student-centered pedagogy to improve understanding and retention in biology (Bizimana et al., 2022).

It would be interesting to see how inverted learning affects students' self-efficacy and conceptual understanding in terms of direct and deferred learning in the new normal. When faced with a problem, students with high self-efficacy are more likely to participate, put more effort, and spend more time than students with low self-efficacy (Riskiningtyas & Wangid, 2019). Grabau (2015) defined self-efficacy as a self-assessment of one's ability to master a task, which includes internal behavioral patterns such as judgments about one's ability to complete a task or goal (Harsch, 2008; Schunk & Miller, 2002; Riskiningtyas & Wangid, 2019; Wang & Tsai, 2016) and confidence in one's performance and abilities (Pintrich et al., 1991; Grabau, 2015). As Bandura (2006) articulated in Chacon Diaz, self-efficacy beliefs are self-proclaimed qualities (2017).

Online ILA and Students' Conceptual Understanding

In terms of context, design, and method, Bredow et al., (2021) highlighted the important benefits of flipped over lecture-based instruction. This is evident in how the learning approach can influence students' achievements in learning English as a second/foreign language; effectively improve nursing students' clinical competence, analytical abilities, self-direction, and learning motivation (Park & Suh, 2021); and vastly improve students' self-directed learning, learning satisfaction, efficacy, learning achievement (Kim & Lim, 2021), retention, and attitude as compared to a lecture-based instruction (Tutal & Yazar, 2021).

Since the beginning of the pandemic, teaching-learning processes have been remodeled to online solutions, and students' experiences with e-learning (online) courses have been positive (Zahriban Hesari et al., 2022). In fact, Wang et al. found that both high school and college students showed significant online academic achievement (2022). Technology integration revealed to improve students' academic performance in practical-related courses (Adeyeye et al., 2022), but not for Safitri et al. (2023) as their students struggled to learn online.

The students' performance and impression of flipped learning in Multivariable Calculus for Engineering that students repeating the course prefer not to choose flipped classes (Caerols-Palma and Vogt-Geisse, 2019) and the instructors' evaluation decreases in flipped classes; rather, they expressed a preference for mixed methodologies, which improved the learning experience of students, leading to an increase instructors' evaluation score and higher scholastic performance. While one of the modifications of the approach is the "productive failure" pedagogical design in the flipped classroom, still students explored, debated, and found solutions related to the new concepts first in class, even if they encountered failures, followed

by integrating the concepts and related processes using video clips at home (Song & Kapur, 2017). This resulted in significant improvements in conceptual knowledge among students, and the condition outperformed those in traditional flipped classrooms.

Online ILA and Students' Self-Efficacy

Inverted learning promotes deeper learning and perceived deeper learning competencies than traditional classroom counterparts (Çigdemoğlu et al., 2023), provides students with more time to learn, enables them to be more independent and responsible, and enhances their creativity (Algarni, 2023; Arante & Castro, 2022), and improves knowledge and skills for students of varying levels of achievement (Paul et al., 2023), but it is not seen as superior to traditional lecture-based instruction (Andujar & Çakmak, 2023).

When essential skills are lacking, high self-efficacy will not result in a competent performance (Ootim, 2000). Researchers working in educational settings are becoming more interested in the role that students' thoughts and beliefs play in the learning process, and their preparation and expectation. This may explain why students perform differently on exams (Hamann et al., 2020). Self-efficacy, as per Dintner et al., (2011), is a key component of the social cognitive theory that appears to be an important factor because it influences students' motivation, learning, and academic success (Mohamed et al., 2021; Zajacova et al., 2005).

Self-efficacy of students in inverted or flipped classrooms has also been studied by Namaziandost & Çakmak (2020), Li & Yang (2021), Latorre-Coscolluela et al. (2021), and Bouwmeester et al. (2019). Inverted learning increased individual

confidence and interest, which resulted in good learning performance (Namaziandost & Çakmak, 2020). It can help students build learning autonomy and self-efficacy, which is critical in terms of student stress and burnout (Bouwmeester et al., 2019).

When compared to learners in conventional instruction, flipping or inverting the class has a greater interactivity, which increases self-efficacy (Bouwmeester et al., 2019). Through social presence (Doo & Bonk, 2020) and collaborative learning assistance, it has improved learner engagement, particularly in the out-of-class learning phase (Zheng et al., 2020) or asynchronous class meetings. It has proven to be suitable for creating active learning atmosphere in which students could increase their sense of self-efficacy (Li & Yang, 2021; Latorre-Coscolluela et al., 2021) and improve knowledge retention (Bouwmeester et al., 2019). In the long run, students will be better problem solvers in their future careers as a result of this (Bouwmeester et al., 2019).

Self-efficacy beliefs (Gore et al., 2005) are the key to understanding why people initiate behavior, how much effort they put into it, and how they persevere in the face of adversity. Academic self-efficacy, which is a belief in one's ability to successfully engage at school, is a concept that may help us understand better persistence and performance. Online learning has recently been grown to support learners' learning processes (Yokoyama, 2019). A student's self-efficacy while learning online is influenced by their confidence in their ability to interact in an online environment (Code et al., 2021). This developing trend is a change in approach from the centralized brick-and-mortar locus of control to one of giving students choice and responsibility for how, when, and where they learn, with the spread of personalized learning and the expansion of Massive Open Online Courses. In educational

psychology, academic self-efficacy (ASE) is acknowledged as a powerful tool for improving academic achievement.

Interaction of Conceptual Understanding and Self-Efficacy

Conceptual understanding is described to as the ability to recognize a concept and apply its idea to a new setting (transfer) as well as the ability to answer questions (Holme et al., 2015). It is the thorough and functional understanding of the learning content. It is about more than just isolated facts and methods; it is about recognizing ideas, creating examples, representing concepts, and expressing critical thinking and reasoning. It is capacity to use knowledge in a variety of situations or instances (Darmofal et al., 2002). It is assessed using questions that imply the combination of distinct but related structures of stored knowledge that are not isolated or arbitrarily linked (Budé et al., 2011).

One of the primary goals of teaching and learning is to promote students' conceptual understanding (Edens & Shields, 2015). This goal, however, is sometimes hampered by the manner in which students' learning is assessed. Academic achievement is a critical component of the educational process. It is reflected in the concepts acquired by students as measured by grading or quarterly assessments. It is considered as a major criterion for determining a person's full potential and capabilities (Nuthana & Yenagi, 2009). This can be influenced by a variety of internal and external factors, one of which is self-efficacy. Self-efficacy assessments help to improve academic performance, which may be associated in scores, grades and/or concept understanding. Educators aim for meaningful conceptual understanding and retention of content (Witt et al., 2021) so that students

can build on it and apply it to practice. Albeit there has no definite way of measuring the knowledge, a wide spectrum of processes, research-based tools, and mechanisms are used to assess learners' conceptual understanding.

In educational contexts, self-efficacy beliefs along with self-regulation, self-concept, and self-control are views that students can improve their learning performance through their efforts, as well as the assistance of their families and teachers (Cheng, 2020). Ootim (2000) contrasted self-efficacy with related constructs (sense of control, result expectations, value perception of outcomes, attributions, and self-concept) and examined some efficacy studies pertinent to academic motivation after offering an outline of self-efficacy theory. Accordingly, failure reduces efficacy whereas success raises it, although if a strong sense of efficacy is established, a failure may have little impact (Bandura, 1986; Ootim, 2000).

Self-efficacy beliefs are sensitive to slight changes in students' performance contexts, to interact with self-regulated learning, and to intervene in students' academic achievement (Adesola & Li, 2018; Zimmerman, 2000). Academic motivation, as described by Ootim (2000) in terms of self-efficacy, is an individual's assessment of his or her own ability to perform specific tasks. High-achieving students were more likely to organize their environment, manage their time, deal with distractions, track motivation, and control negative emotions, and thus achieve better results (Cheng, 2020).

Grit and self-efficacy have been acknowledged as effective predictors of performance (Usher et al., 2019). Self-efficacy plays a critical role in determining student performance (Broadbent, 2016). In the new normal set-up, student performance and output may be determined by various online activity and

engagement. Improved online pedagogical practices to boost online student self-efficacy may develop techniques to assess online learning programs and raise retention rates, academic achievement, and mastery goals (Kesan & Kaya, 2018; Al-Harthy et al., 2010) in STEM courses according to Flowers (2011). Now, one challenge of online learning in both synchronous and asynchronous settings is the lack of group interactions during learning (Kusumawati et al., 2021), but when learning takes place by connecting material with real-life contexts, students will be able to analyze, evaluate, create, and solve problems in real life, which will improve their self-efficacy (Haryanto & Arty, 2019).

The Mixed Methods for Online ILA Studies on Students' Learning

Several studies have already compared flipped learning and traditional classroom lecture using a mixed-methods design (Anderson et al., 2017; Burak et al., 2017; Baharum et al., 2020; Li, & Li, 2022; Behmanesh et al., 2022; Purwanti & Suryawati, 2022; Atwa et al., 2022). This mixed-methods design is a research paradigm (Johnson et al., 2007) that allows for data collection and analysis at multiple points, allowing qualitative and quantitative findings to cohere and coexist. Using both quantitative and qualitative methods in the same study provides a lens from multiple perspectives, as well as richness and depth of information and experiences that make results generalizable and transferrable.

Inverted learning or flipping improved students' skill competence (Xu et al., 2019); increased student achievement (Boateng et al., 2022); and was significantly more effective than conventional teaching (Behmanesh et al., 2020) as students improved their scores, attitude, and interaction. Positive influencing factors included

the learning environment, instructor presence, and learning content (Li & Li, 2022); improved students' conceptual knowledge and practice, as well as a better attitude and more learning satisfaction (Behmanesh et al., 2022). Further, flipping is effective when students' learning outcomes improved, and when students perceived video lectures contributory on their participation and active learning (Purwanti, & Suryawati, 2022). However, these results contradicted the findings of Custer et al. (2022), who found that the flipped learning format resulted in the lowest mean examination scores and course satisfaction. It also did not improve the confidence and assessment scores from pre-test to post-test (McCabe et al., 2017). Burak et al. (2017) likewise revealed that students in the flipped classroom had significantly lower mean (SD) ratings of their learning experiences and less enjoyment of the learning experience.

Some challenges encountered according to Kenwright et al. (2017) when students did not engage with the new flipped learning activities, and their test resulted in a small but insignificant score improvement (McCue, 2016). Likewise, students were unmotivated when instructed through flipped learning, despite being satisfied with the course structure (Birgili, & Demir, 2022), as it caused excessive workload too on learners while lack of learning preparedness on the part of students (Li & Li, 2022) while teachers encountered technical challenges and found problems about the amount of time required for pre-class preparation, such as recording flipped videos because creating video lectures necessitates enough time, attention, skill and effort. This is supported by Kenwright et al. (2017) as flipping imposed a heavy cognitive load on students, impairing the knowledge construction process and by Cha & Kim (2020) that reported students' academic achievement and academic

self-efficacy did not change significantly, but their interviews with them reported mostly positive feelings toward it (McCue, 2016).

There are also numerous studies that show the link between conceptual understanding and self-efficacy (Marina & Ridlo, 2021; Mustofa, 2022; Kurniawan & Mashuri, 2021; Jose et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022). On the plus side, self-efficacy had a positive correlation with conceptual understanding when using inverted learning in algebra, calculus, and circulatory system materials, implying that students with high conceptual understanding and thinking ability have high self-efficacy (Marina & Ridlo, 2021; Mustofa, 2022; Kurniawan, & Mashuri, 2021). However, studies by Jose et al. (2021) and Wang et al. (2022) highlighted that self-efficacy scores did not predict engagement and that learning gains did not significantly vary between study groups with different levels of prior knowledge or self-efficacy.

For many years, learners have been taught through conventional instruction and home-based assignments. The key idea behind this modality is that the teacher first introduces the topic, then elaborates through examples, situations, and/or drills as extended practice. When learners have queries about the homework, they can raise it to the teacher in the next class meeting. Teachers address the queries, review the lesson, continue the discussion, assess learning, mark the evaluation, and give assignments. This is a classic method of efficiently communicating knowledge and skills to students (Namaziandost & Çakmak, 2020).

This time, the online-based model known as inverted learning, commonly known as "flipping" introduces new challenges that differ from those encountered in face-to-face instruction (Romero et al., 2019). Inverted instruction shifts basic content

learning to before class, while in-class time is used for concept application (Jensen et al., 2018; Ferreira, 2014). The existing evidence to support its effectiveness in K-12 science classrooms is insufficient to warrant such a fervent embrace (Zummo, 2020).

Inverted Learning spares more time for higher order thinking activities. While several researches have generally observed neutral to positive student feedback and effects on academic achievement, the quality of pre-class resources and the time needed for preclass work have been considered as potential issues with the approach (Kenwright et al., 2016). All the same, completing the out-of-class online learning activity was particularly critical (Zummo, 2020) of the process. Virtual Flipped has shown a statistically significant difference in learners' learning achievement and motivation (Ahmed & Abdulla, 2019). A virtual flipped classroom environment can help students improve their creative thinking and ICT literacy by using various types of scaffolding systems (Trairut & Jeerungsuwan, 2016). Thus, this digital learning and educational technology practice could be adopted or implemented at the primary and secondary levels of education (Fragkaki et al., 2020). This, in turn, promotes students' autonomy and collaboration, despite the challenges they confronted during COVID-19 (Martinelli & Zaina, 2021).

Viewing the conceptual understanding, the time needed for different students to learn the same material should be the focus of instruction, according to mastery learning theory. Due to their varying abilities, students can pace themselves or take their time reviewing or watching the videos. Semi-synchronous learning involves students being given online learning material and a time frame within which to study it. This enables students to use mastery-based development and just-in-time

learning strategies. Furthermore, this frees up lecture time, allowing them to focus on assisting students who are lagging (Alers et al., 2019). Inverted learning approach emphasizes autonomy, context, development, and experience (Yin, 2015). It also fosters students' confidence and competence and facilitates active learning (Bingen et al., 2020). This instructional intervention also flips Bloom's taxonomy by allowing students to focus at home on the lower functions (like knowing and understanding) while in virtual meetings, they will analyze, apply, and create.

On their academic achievement from the study of Ebrahim and Naji (2021), learners using flipped teaching methods outperformed learners using direct methods. It resulted in improved learning outcomes for students. Using short, prerecorded videos to introduce subject material was one of the most beneficial elements for student learning. It also creates inclusive online learning groups that enable students to gain conceptual knowledge as well as scientific inquiry and literacy skills (Garcia-Vedrenne et al., 2020). Furthermore, even when the course was moved entirely remote, most students perceived that the flipping would make the transition to emergency remote teaching easier, and they liked the learning environment (Fogg & Maki, 2020). While the face-to-face to face-to-screen transition was relevant, there were some difficulties encountered in the platform utilization for online lectures reflecting emotions in face-to-face interaction (Jeong & González-Gómez, 2021). As a corollary, communicating with students and assessing specific needs, such as access to technology, as well as being flexible with the course structure, would be essentially preferable (Garcia-Vedrenne et al., 2020).

Flipping encourages active learning and increasing student engagement (Gopalan, 2021). According to Gopalan (2021), this design effectively managed to learn in such a way that lower-order thinking, such as rote memory, is expected at

the individual student level in the form of homework and higher-order thinking, such as application and analysis, is expected to occur in the class. However, there is limited evidence on the effect of inverted learning in conceptual understanding among high school students and particularly in knowledge retention in learning Biology. In the study, this flipping approach was carried out mainly online and so it hoped to effect the same as how conventional flipped was done. It explored that flipping would be able to also promote active learning and student engagement in the online, flexible, or blended class set-up.

One of the primary goals of teaching and learning is to promote students' conceptual understanding (Edens & Shields, 2015). This goal, however, is sometimes hampered by the way students' learning is assessed. Academic achievement is a critical component of the educational process. It is reflected in the concepts acquired by students as measured by grading or quarterly assessments. It is considered as a major criterion for determining a person's full potential and capabilities (Nuthana & Yenagi, 2009). This can be influenced by a variety of internal and external factors, one of which is self-efficacy. Self-efficacy assessments help to improve academic performance. Educators aim for meaningful conceptual understanding and retention of content (Witt et al., 2021) so that students can build on it and apply it to practice. Albeit, there has no definite way of measuring the knowledge, a wide spectrum of processes, research-based tools, and mechanisms are used to assess learners' conceptual understanding.

Learners acquire facts (declarative knowledge) that may or may not be integrated; with learning and experience, they can utilize these facts to solve issues more systematically (procedural knowledge); and eventually, they become independent and create skill-based behavior (skill tuning of procedural knowledge).

Ritter et al., (2013) developed these three (3) stages of learning and retention. Learning improves performance (Ritter et al., 2013), and the rate at which it occurs, the phases of learning, and how it can be transmitted. However, the learning retention curve is identical to the learning plateau curve that takes over time.

Secondary level biology academic performance has not been as good as expected (Bizimana et al., 2022). That is why there has been a consistent emphasis on discovering emerging innovative student-centered pedagogy to improve understanding and retention in biology (Bizimana et al., 2022). Generally, tests for conceptual understanding of topics, like Bioenergetics, will not only provide solid support for a student's academic performance, but will also play a significant role in what happens to a student after school (Popham, 2003). Test proponents contend that more frequent classroom testing encourages practice and review, providing students with more opportunity for feedback on their work (Krenn et al., 2013).

Locally, Notre Dame Schools such as Notre Dame of Cotabato make use of the Notre Dame Educational Association Achievement Test, or NDEA Achievement Test, to assess students' academic achievement. The declining science performance of the school (NDC-AM Shift and NDC-PM Shift) with the mean scores of other schools in the NDEA- Cotabato Area from year 2015 to 2019. More specifically, a drop in performance was observed in the topic, Energy Transformation in Living Things as reflected in Figure 2.1. There also has an evidence of deteriorating performance among students in Figure 2.2 under the Grade 9 Science domain/strand–Ecosystem: *“Learners learn how plants capture energy from the sun and store energy in sugar molecules (Photosynthesis). This stored energy is used by cells during cellular respiration. These two processes are related to each other.”* (Source: K to 12 Science Curriculum Guide August 2016 Page 9 of 203 Learning

Materials and equipment technical specifications may be accessed at [http://lrmds.deped.gov.ph/.](http://lrmds.deped.gov.ph/))

Because the NDEA achievement test is no longer administered in Senior High School, a quick poll has been conducted in May 2022 among STEM graduates of NDC from S.Y. 2019-2020 to S.Y. 2021-2022 via Google Form. It gathered supporting data on their perception of the difficulty level of the content of General Biology as one specialized STEM course. As shown in Table 2.1, one hundred and twenty-two (122) students responded on a scale of 1 (most learned/easy) to 10 (least learned/difficult) to the topics that they believe require more focus and time in teaching.

Figure 2.1. Science Performance of NDC vs NDEA

Note: Obtained from the School Principal's Copy of NDEA Results in Science (2015-2019)

Figure 2.2 Performance of NDC vs NDEA in the Science 9 Ecosystem Strand

Note: Obtained from the School Principal's Copy of NDEA Results in Science (2015-2019)

Table 2.1

Level of difficulty of General Biology 1 Topics as Perceived by STEM Graduates

Content	Mean
Cell Organelles	5.69 ± 2.27
Cell Transport	5.89 ± 1.94
Cell Cycle	5.75 ± 2.35
Biological Molecules	6.10 ± 2.08
Photosynthesis	6.31 ± 2.09
Cellular Respiration	6.82 ± 1.79

Note: Scale: 1.00 (easy to learn) to 10.00 (difficult to learn), N= 122

Owing to the NDEA results and the quick poll among students, it can be deliberately shown that the topics in Bioenergetics, which includes Photosynthesis

and Cellular Respiration, are among the most difficult to learn content in General Biology. This levies a challenge to find innovative mechanism to improve Biology education. The thrust of biology education has changed from memorization to depth of understanding of core biological concepts such as matter and energy relationships (Uhl et al., 2021), particularly in learning the intricate nature of metabolic pathways that are difficult to understand (Jain et al., 2021), such as photosynthesis, respiration (Çıngıl Barış, 2022; Atilla, 2012), ATP as the energy currency of the cell (Fontecilla-Camps, 2022), and energy transfer in an ecosystem (Yoon & Karpudewan, 2022).

Even after teaching, Özay & Öztaş (2003) underlined that students have fundamentally contradictory, and frequently minor conceptual errors about photosynthesis, respiration, and energy flow in plant ecosystems. This strongly indicates that a different approach to teaching this subject area may contribute to reducing students' difficulties in understanding the concepts of photosynthesis when developing science resources and supporting teachers become more responsive to students' misconceptions.

Furthermore, cellular respiration is most often challenging for Biology students (Surendran et al., 2021) because the topic is both expansive and abstract because the students cannot just observe the process (Bentley & Connaughton, 2021). It is a topic in introductory and cellular biology curricula, and it is a detailed biological process that presents core biological concepts such as systems, ATP formation (Bentley & Connaughton, 2021), energy transformation in living things, structure and function relationships (Bergan-Roller et al., 2021), enzymes and co-enzymes, and redox reactions (Surendran et al., 2021).

Inverted learning is still a relatively new pedagogical method at the secondary level (Offerman-Celentano, 2017) and is relevant for application in this time of

changing educational set-up. Therefore, this research delved into how this inverted learning could affect learners' self-efficacy, which indicates how they feel about themselves, as well as their drive and level of confidence in learning quarter-long topics in Biology, particularly in the topics on energy transformation in living systems (bioenergetics). It further examined the differences in conceptual understanding in terms of direct and deferred conceptual understanding of students as exposed to the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA). Following the sequential mixed methods approach, direct experiences of the students were included in the analysis of the quantitative data, making sense and explanations of their experiences in learning Biology through ILA.

Theoretical Framework

Several existing theories, such as the Constructivist Learning Theory (CLT), which explain how learners take ownership of their learning from prior experiences, support the inverted learning approach. CLT inspired the teacher's role as a facilitator to guide students' self-directed learning and participation in engaging classes with a nonthreatening environment. Through the critical thinking process and immediate feedback, realistic challenging solutions enabled students to be more active and immersed in class (Piriyasurawong, 2018; Park & Park, 2020). The learning approach is a learner-centered educational approach (Xu & Shi, 2018) in which students contribute to outside-of-class exercises or self-learning rather than building knowledge or understanding contents before coming to class. It incorporates constructivist theory (Kanjug et al., 2018) as a foundation of the instructional design as an online self-study activity outside of class as well as

practical experience and higher-order thinking activities in class are done. In the context of information digitalization and the popularity of the Internet, flipping is a new teaching model (Xu & Shi, 2018) favorable to the constructivist learning approach, marked by active knowledge construction rather than passive intake of predetermined concepts (Hadiyahmetovi, 2021).

On the other side, the time needed for different students to learn the same material should be the focus of instruction, according to mastery learning theory. Due to their varying abilities, students can pace themselves or take their time reviewing or watching the videos. Semi-synchronous learning involves students being given online learning material and a time frame within which to study it. This enables students to use masterybased development and just-in-time learning strategies. Furthermore, this frees up lecture time, allowing them to focus on assisting students who are lagging (Alers et al., 2019). The approach, which is guided by mastery learning, emphasizes autonomy, context, development, and experience (Yin, 2015). It also fosters students' confidence and competence and facilitates active learning (Bingen et al., 2020). This instructional intervention also flips Bloom's taxonomy by allowing students to focus at home on the lower functions (like knowing and understanding) while in online meetings, they will analyze, apply, and create.

Piaget's theory of equilibration is especially applicable because learners constantly change their existing schema and incorporate new information with the old schema. Inverted learning depicts the interaction of newly received information with students' existing schema (Mubarik et al., 2018). This process includes assimilation, equilibration, accommodation, and rejection of new information. Students form schema as they watch the discussion videos; they ask questions,

discuss with classmates and teachers in the chat facility where they communicate with classmates, affecting their existing schema; and they assimilate new information so that they can use the existing scheme if appropriate and change the existing schema if it is not. Piaget's theory, which is at the heart of cognitive approaches to psychology and learning, placed a premium on the construct of equilibration (Bormanaki & Khoshhal, 2017). Equilibration is linked to practical contexts and explains how logic and reason, knowledge structures, integration, accommodation, and reading comprehension are all intersected.

Ultimately, inverted learning has an impact not only on students' cognitive learning outcomes, but also on their intrinsic dispositions (degree of motivation) and needs for mastery, autonomy, and belongingness, according to the concept of Self-Determination Theory (Sergis et al., 2018). Thus, self-determination theory applies to or is concerned with their autonomy or control over their learning experience. It is becoming more popular in secondary school settings and appears to address students' needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness, which are all components of self-determination theory (Muir, 2020). According to Liu (2017), motivation is strongly related to student achievement and perseverance; however, academic achievement can also influence persistence. Self-determination theory (SDT) is a framework for understanding how social context intertwines with people's motivation (Liu et al., 2018).

This paper most especially regards the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) model of Ryan and Deci (2000) as shown in Figure 3. Dr. Richard Ryan, a clinical psychologist, and Dr. Edward Deci, an experimental psychologist, are both professors at the University of Rochester's Department of Clinical and Social Sciences in Psychology. Their 30-year partnership has contributed to the

development and ongoing evolution of self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2002). SDT is an improvement of Skinner's theory of Operant Conditioning, where one's changed behavior is caused by an external factor like a positive or a negative reinforcement. SDT considers another factor, such as intrinsic motivation, that may influence how people respond and behave. Ryan and Deci's ideas in their 1985 book *Self-Determination and Intrinsic Motivation in Human Behavior* sparked the development of self-determination theory.

Figure 2.3. Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000)

Figure 2.3 shows that students who will be taught using inverted learning develop *independence* or autonomy as they self-pace their learning; *ability* as they feel able to be good at understanding the lesson on their own, as they will have actively experienced competence and control of the information they learn from viewing the videos; and *connection* or relatedness as they receive social support from teachers and classmates via the group chats where they may be able to share their thoughts about; thus one experiences a sense of belonging to a group. When students are satisfied or have experienced these three, it will be their source of *interest* to do more, their *sense of purpose* in doing things that make them feel more involved in the learning process, and their *self-efficacy* to do and finish task not because they are asked of it but because they are intrinsically motivated to learn. Given these, students

will be more *determined* to participate in the class, more *innovative* or creative, and will manifest *improved* academic performance.

Human beings, according to Ryan and Deci (2009), are inherently proactive and imbued with a predisposition to learn and develop as they engage not only with their outer environments, but also with their motives, desires, and perceptions. Self-determination theory (SDT) provides a consistent and comprehensive framework for understanding human motivation and personality development (Deci & Ryan, 2002). The theory is based on three basic and universal psychological needs: competence, autonomy, and relatedness (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

SDT, as a theoretical foundation of inverted learning approach, explains why students enjoy learning and perform better when they are intrinsically rather than extrinsically motivated to succeed. Students who participate in establishing educational goals are more likely to achieve them because they are intrinsically driven (Ryan & Deci, 2000), such as feeling more competent and autonomous. Students who are self – directed work on tasks that they enjoy. In other words, engagement is a reward in and of itself and is not dependent on external rewards such as praise, grades, or other extrinsic factors.

Though teachers usually resist to changes in the teaching approach (Van Twembeke & Goeman, 2018), which makes it difficult to introduce alternative strategies for teaching, using ILA is expected to improve students' motivation and confidence for self-directed learning. Through inverted learning, 21st century learners will improve their skill competence (Xu et al., 2019), critical thinking, and higher order thinking skills. In the end, because this learning model caters to the most convenient environment (virtual or cyberspace) that these generation Z

learners are already familiar with, this one aspect allows them to be more motivated and comfortable to learn.

Conceptual Framework

The Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has already had a significant disruptive impact on society, posing challenges to educational policies and systems worldwide (Anthony & Noel, 2021). As a result, physical classes were canceled abruptly, and students and teachers faced new challenges, such as the closure of all on-campus classes and extra-curricular and program-focused activities (Parker et al., 2021). Classes have further shifted to flexible, hybrid, blended, and online learning (Won et al., 2020; Mittal et al., 2021; Srivastava et al., 2021) where digital technologies (Anthony & Noel, 2021); and innovative emergency teaching (Parker et al., 2021) were adopted.

Potential consequences of the instructional pedagogy approach and effective integration of technological tools can be very helpful in ensuring continuous success in delivering learning content (Yuan, 2021) in this new normal, while also engaging students in online learning to improve their performance and outcomes (Khlaif et al., 2021) and experiences (Nguyen et al., 2021). This also includes the implementation of new technologies, pedagogies, and learning models (Chattaraj & Vijayaraghavan, 2021) that include synchronous and asynchronous instructions (Shamir-Inbal & Blau, 2021).

The study explored how the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) affected students' direct and deferred conceptual understanding and self-efficacy when compared to

those who were exposed to expository online teaching (EOT). It was interested to determine how ILA can improve the performance of students, by also looking at the retention of student learning as one research gap that needs to be addressed. It further looked into their lived experiences for a more in-depth understanding and processing of the results, from which the instructional improvement plan was derived. A week (or two) of pre-viewing of teacher-made discussion videos and topic presentation was followed by scheduled, synchronous online class sessions in the intervention group. This is the inverted learning approach (ILA). On the other hand, the conventional group received the expository online teaching (EOT). This is accomplished through a synchronous lecture-discussion format, followed by an assessment, an assignment and/or homework. The interplay of the variables used in the study as represented by the research paradigm is shown in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4. Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework

This proposed that one instructional approach could affect students' conceptual understanding and self-efficacy, as indicated by a one-headed arrow,

implying how the ILA improved conceptual understanding and self-efficacy when compared to EOT. The line connecting conceptual understanding (CU) and self-efficacy (SE) shows a relationship and/or association between the two variables. Two separate arrows from CU and SE suggest that these variables would serve as a framework for developing an instructional improvement plan. A unidirectional arrow is drawn to the instructional approach from this plan, confirming that the plan could recommend better ways to improve the implementation of ILA in the case of the paper, which could impact students' conceptual understanding and self-efficacy.

More specifically, the level of conceptual understanding of students has been drawn from the results of their posttest, which measures the direct understanding, and retention test, which represents the deferred understanding. From these information, an increment or decrement in performance was recorded. Their level of self-efficacy has been likewise assessed using adapted and validated tools reflective of the factors such as independence, competence, and interaction. It also looked into how these variables will be affected by the intervention, and at the same time how each variable affected/ related to each other to some extent. The focus group discussion was used to corroborate all these data (scores in the test and self-efficacy ratings), from which the framework of the instructional improvement plan of the study was designed. The improvement plan would be helpful in better implementing the Inverted Learning Approach as an innovative teaching-learning pedagogy in this new normal education.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were set at a 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant increase in the Posttest scores of students who received Expository Online Teaching.

H_{a1}: There is a significant increase in the Posttest scores of students who received Expository Online Teaching.

H₀₂: There is no significant increase in the Posttest scores of students who received the Inverted Learning Approach.

H_{a2}: There is a significant increase in the Posttest scores of students who received the Inverted Learning Approach.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference on the Posttest mean scores between students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach and Expository Online Teaching.

H_{a3}: Students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach have significantly higher mean scores in Posttest test than those taught using the Expository Online Teaching.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference on the Retention test mean scores between students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach and Expository Online Teaching.

H_{a4}: Students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach have significantly higher mean scores in Retention test than those taught using the Expository Online Teaching.

H₀₅: There are no significant differences between the pretest, posttest, and retention test scores of students who received Expository Online Teaching.

H_{a5}: There are significant differences between the pretest, posttest, and retention test scores of students who received Expository Online Teaching.

H₀₆: There are no significant differences between the pretest, posttest, and retention test scores of students who received the Inverted Learning Approach.

- H_{a6}: There are significant differences between the pretest, posttest, and retention test scores of students who received the Inverted Learning Approach.
- H_{o7}: There is a significant difference in the self-efficacy level of students who received the expository online approach before and after the quarter.
- H_{a7}: There is a no significant difference in the self-efficacy level of students who received the expository online approach before and after the quarter.
- H_{o8}: There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy level of students who received the inverted learning approach before and after the quarter.
- H_{a8}: There is a significant difference in the self-efficacy level of students who received the inverted learning approach before and after the quarter.
- H_{o9}: There is no significant difference on the Self-Efficacy Level between students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach and Expository Online Teaching.
- H_{a9}: Students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach have significantly higher Self-Efficacy Level than those taught using the Expository Online Teaching.
- H_{o10}: There is no relationship between the conceptual understanding and self-efficacy of students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach.
- H_{a10}: There is a positive relationship between the conceptual understanding and self-efficacy of students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined as to how they are used in the study:

Conceptual Understanding – the thorough and functional understanding of the learning content. It is about more than just isolated facts and methods; it is about recognizing ideas, creating examples, representing concepts, and expressing critical thinking and reasoning. It is the capacity to use knowledge in a variety of situations or instances (Darmofal et al., 2002). In the study, it is indicated by the scores obtained by the students from the pre-test, post-test (direct conceptual understanding), and retention test (deferred conceptual understanding). It may be used interchangeably with content understanding and learning retention, concept understanding, learning performance, and academic performance, or achievement.

Correlation coefficient - a statistical measure that quantifies the magnitude and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. In the study, the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used to measure the association between the direct and deferred conceptual understanding and self-efficacy among STEM students. It ranges from -1 to +1, where -1 indicates a perfect negative correlation, +1 indicates a perfect positive correlation, and 0 shows no correlation.

Deferred Conceptual Understanding – the ability to restore, recover, or remember previously learned information and use it when prompted. It is a more thorough understanding of knowledge and skills acquisition. It is assessed using questions that imply the combination of distinct but related structures of stored knowledge that are not isolated or arbitrarily linked (Budé et al., 2011). In the study, it may be interchangeably used with postponed, delayed, or retentive conceptual understanding or learning retention. Al-Balushi and Al-Balushi (2018) recommended assessing long-term retention of the subject matter 6 weeks after the end of the

study; however, Maymoona & Sulaiman (2015) and Eguchi et al., (2021) used a two-week delayed post-test, thus in the paper, the deferred conceptual understanding was determined thru the retention test conducted four (4) weeks or one (1) month after the posttest administration.

Direct Conceptual Understanding - the ability to transfer new information into long-term memory, demonstrating how information is effectively absorbed and can be used readily when prompted. It is being able to recognize a concept and apply its idea to a new setting (transfer) as well as the ability to answer questions (Holme et al., 2015). It also describes the ability to quickly retrieve content from direct knowledge and skills acquisition. In the study, this is the academic or learning performance of students measured by the Posttest RBAT scores. This can be determined after interventions or treatments.

Effect size - a measure that indicates the strength of the effect or difference between groups or variables in a standardized and comparable manner. The standardized effect size formula depends on the statistical test used such as t-test and ANOVA. In the study, Cohen's d levels (1988) was used to measure the effect size, which may be nonsignificant (below 0.20); small (0.20-0.49); medium (0.50-0.79); or large (0.80 and higher).

Expository Online Teaching (EOT) - the direct online teaching method in which the lecture or discussion method is done synchronously or during the online sessions. In general, EOT students receive information, and the method is dominated by the teacher. Online learning is being implemented in emergency situations such as the COVID-19 to allow the education process to continue where learning is through information technology (Qazia et al., 2020). In the study, this is

designed as the expository or typical online teaching given to the conventional (comparison) group.

Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) – a pedagogical approach in which students receive course content outside of class by viewing digital presentations and/or watching assigned short discussion videos prior to the online class meeting, which can be effective and efficient in facilitating learning activities. This is also known as flipped learning. It is based on the concept that ILA students must complete pre-class learning assignments or lectures outside of class (Rawas et al., 2020; Shahnama et al., 2021), followed by highquality, more class time dedicated to cooperative learning, individually tailored, and differentiated learning, and concept application activities during class time (Delozier & Rhodes, 2017; Olalekan et al., 2020). In the study, it was mainly done virtually or online, or in a synchronous (online) meeting component. This is given as a teaching approach/ method to the intervention group. Its effectiveness is compared with the expository online teaching (EOT) given to the conventional group.

RBAT - stands for Researcher-validated Biology Achievement Test. This is a multiplechoice test instrument used to assess concept understanding in Bioenergetics. In the study, it has been subjected and trialed for its validity and reliability. The results of this test will indicate how much of an effect the intervention will have on the learners' direct and deferred conceptual understanding.

Self-Efficacy - a self-assessment of one's ability to master a task, which includes internal behavioral patterns such as judgments about one's ability to complete a task or goal (Harsch, 2008; Schunk & Miller, 2002; Riskiningtyas & Wangid, 2019; Wang & Tsai, 2016; Grabau, 2015) and confidence in one's performance and abilities (Pintrich et al., 1991).

In the study, it is one which is measured by the self-efficacy instrument as to the learners' self-rating of their capabilities and confidence before and after the exposure to inverted learning approach. Specifically, the study determines the self-efficacy to attend synchronous online classes complete an online course, interact socially with classmates, handle tools in a Learning Management System (LMS), and interact with teachers and classmates in an online course and for academic purposes.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, locale, subjects of the study, research instrumentation, results of the pilot run and validity and reliability tests of the instruments, and the details of the intervention, ethical considerations, data collection procedure, statistical treatment, and processes of analyzing the data.

Research Design

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. It primarily conducted a two-group quasi-experimental, controlled group design, followed by a thematic qualitative analysis. The study used a quantitative approach in obtaining the levels of direct and deferred conceptual understanding through the RBAT and the level of self-efficacy through a validated questionnaire and qualitative survey. The Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) served as the treatment given to the experimental or intervention group, also known as ILA group. On the other hand, the Expository Online Teaching was given to the conventional group, or the EOT group, which did not receive treatment. The design also aimed to verify, evaluate, and analyze non-numerical information and feedback from the respondents. The qualitative analysis was also performed to further elucidate the experiences of students who received the ILA. The qualitative data gathered has the potential to support quantitative information, supplement and enrich the findings, as well as to generate new knowledge (Bowen et al., 2017). Figure 3.1 illustrates the flow of the study.

Figure 3.1. Diagrammatic Flow of the Study

Study Site

The locale of the study is a private Catholic high school in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). It is the country's first Marist school and the only Marist school in Cotabato City. Notre Dame of Cotabato (NDC) is an educational institution owned and run by the Marist Brothers and has been in operation since 1948. It is one of the Notre Dame Educational Association (NDEA)-member schools and an affiliate of the Catholic Educational Association of the Philippines (CEAP). The study site is a Level III accredited secondary school by the Philippine Accrediting

Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU). Level III status is the highest level of accreditation for basic education programs given by the PAASCU, which means the school upholds a certain level of academic quality. It is also certified by the Private Education Assistance Committee (PEAC), a DepEd-contracted body that monitors schools' adherence to DepEd standards, policies, and regulations. It has a student population of approximately 2,000 and offers day and afternoon shift classes in Junior and Senior High School. It is a new normal-ready school and is K-12 compliant. For the first semester of the S.Y. 2022-2023, NDC has adopted a blended learning modality with the following schemes for the SHS program: 2 online classes; 1 modular/offline period; and 1 limited (by set) face-to-face session per week.

The Sample

Six (6) Grade 12 STEM classes during the school year 2022-2023 were the respondents. Each class comprises 45-48 students who are all taught by the same science teacher to maintain parity of conditions except for the treatment. All in all, the study initially involved 287 STEM students; however only 232 submitted the informed and consent forms required by the ethics board to be able to participate in the study.

The random assignment of the classes into intervention and conventional groups was determined by their Pre-test scores. After the pre-testing, only 225 out of 232 were able to complete the data, that is, 116 students to represent the intervention group and 109 students to represent the conventional group, with an approximately equal ratio of male and female students. After post-testing, there were

only 218 respondents remaining, with 112 for the intervention group and 106 from the conventional group.

Since there are six (6) STEM classes, it was made sure that randomization via random assignment was observed in such a way that each group would have the same number of classes, and almost the same number of students. Three (3) intact classes served as the intervention group (exposed to the inverted learning approach), while the remaining three (3) classes were the conventional group that received the expository online teaching. Finally, they were chosen as respondents because they most fit the following criteria: a) officially enrolled during the S.Y. 2022-2023; b) Qualified for STEM strand; c) Grade 12 level (equal preparation and all qualified in terms of their academic background); and d) taking up Biology course in the First Semester of the school year as stipulated in the K-to-12 Curriculum Guide in General Biology for the Senior High School. Students who did lack any of the information (pretest, posttest, and survey responses) were automatically removed and whose data were discarded in the analysis.

Data Gathering Instruments

Curriculum Maps and Learning Plans

The curriculum maps containing the learning goals, namely 1) Acquisition, 2) Meaning Making, and 3) Transfer and learning plans having these stages, a) Explore, b) Firm-up, c) Deepen, and d) Transfer) were designed by the researcher. This instructional design/ format was recommended by the Private Educational

Assistance Committee (PEAC). This ensures that students receive the same standards, learning competencies, and learning targets.

To establish the clear flow of instruction between the intervention and conventional groups, Gagne’s nine (9) events of Instruction were paralleled or incorporated into the three main parts of the learning plan template. General Biology is a STEM course taught in two (2) semesters. Each semester has two quarters in a span of 80 hours. The study covered only the second quarter topics of the course during the first semester, that means 40 hours or 4 meetings in a week for ten (10) weeks of exposure. Appendix E further details the topics covered during the second quarter, alongside the time frame and learning competencies from the curriculum guide. The Comparative Flowchart of the Events for the Conventional and Intervention Groups is reflected in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2. Comparative Flowchart of the Events for the EOT and ILA Groups

Gagne's nine (9) events of instruction were paralleled or incorporated into the three main parts of the teaching guide [See Appendix G]. Between the EOT and ILA groups, as presented in Figure 3.2, the main difference could be the intentional off-class or asynchronous event in the ILA, which is the advance deployment of the teacher-made discussion videos. EOT group does not receive the content materials ahead.

Another notable difference is the use of entry tickets in ILA that guides in determining which concepts should be deepened or emphasized for the period. On the other hand, no entry tickets before the class starts for EOT group. The scores in the entry ticket are not recorded, however, students are strongly encouraged to take it, and the results (or insights from the Google form) are presented in aggregate before the class; this is also not seen in EOT, simply because objectives are given directly before moving on to the discussion in lecture format, which takes more time. Under ILA, scaffolding and deepening through breakout rooms and Q&A reinforces information processing.

The application and feedback processes are nearly the same for both groups, with the EOT group receiving a short quiz, while the ILA group will be given random Q&A or oral questioning. EOT is assigned reading tasks or homework, whereas ILA is assigned the task of making learning logs and/ or watching the next topic's discussion videos.

Microsoft Teams (MS Teams)

This is the official Learning Management System (LMS) for distributing all learning/instructional materials to the respondents of the study. Each class had its

own team comprised of channels for instruction and communication. Each student, on the other hand, had an individual account too. MS Teams was used to host synchronous online classes as well as focus group discussions. This platform has been already in use since 2020 by the school where the study was conducted; thus, students already have the knowledge in navigating and/ or using the LMS. The google form links containing the online self-efficacy questionnaire and qualitative survey on inverted learning approach were forwarded to the students via the team's channels.

Researcher-validated Biology Achievement Test (RBAT)

This is also known as the RBAT. This was used as a Pretest, Posttest, and Retention test to assess students' conceptual understanding. The test was revisited, and items were shuffled twice, so students would not think the same test was given. The RBAT consists of 50 multiple-choice questions, 60% of which are knowledge-based, and 40% are process-based. Each objective question has four options, with only one correct answer. The test has been already reviewed and checked by the school's Science Department Coordinator before its face and content validity had been checked by eight (8) science teachers of the school and its reliability had been tested in a one-intact Grade 12 STEM class in the afternoon shift program during the 2nd Semester of the S.Y. 20212022, following the approval from the school principal.

The researcher initially constructed an 80-item test based on the listed competencies in the General Biology 1 Curriculum Guide. The students' total scores

were entered into an MS Excel spreadsheet and arranged in descending order. Twenty-four (24) students, or 27 percent of the high and low achievers, were chosen for item analysis. The middle 46% were excluded from the analysis on the assumption that they behaved in a similar pattern. Table 3.1 shows the difficulty or ease indices.

Table 3.1

Difficulty and Discrimination Indices of RBAT

p-value	Interpretation	Mean p-value	No. of items (n=80)
> 0.70	Too easy	0.773± 0.060	4 (5%)
0.30-0.70	Average	0.444± 0.116	49 (61%)
< 0.30	Too difficult	0.234± 0.039	27 (34%)
DI	Interpretation	Mean DI	No. of items (n=80)
≥ 0.35	Excellent	0.609± 0.136	29 (36%)
0.25- 0.34	Good	0.289± 0.043	19 (24%)
0.15- 0.24	Marginal	0.167± 0.000	10 (13%)
< 0.15	Poor	0.027± 0.107	22 (27%)

Item difficulty is the percentage of students who correctly answered each item, which is also referred to as the p-value, and it ranges from 0.00 to 1.00, with the higher the value indicating that the item is easier. Table 3.2 also shows that only forty-nine (49) items have an acceptable and recommended level of difficulty, while twenty-seven (27) items are very difficult and must be reviewed or rejected, and four (4) items are very easy and may be rejected. On the other hand, the discrimination indices (DI), also known as Point-Biserial Correlation (PBC) are also presented in Table 3.1. It describes the degree to which success or failure on an item

distinguishes between high and low scorers. This number ranges from -1.00 to +1.00. It shows that fifty-eight (58) items or 60% are good to excellent, with nineteen (19) items or 24% being good and twenty-nine (29) or 36% being excellent. The higher the DI, the more frequently high-performing students chose the correct answer for a specific item than students with low overall scores.

Moreover, Figures 3.3 and 3.4 reveal the test items chosen based on item difficulty and power of discrimination, respectively. Thirty (30) items were rejected due to difficulty or discrimination index.

Figure 3.3. Bar diagram showing the selected items based on Ease Indices/ p-values

Figure 3.4. Bar diagram showing the selected items based on Point-Biserial Coefficients

Moreover, Figure 3.5 displays a line diagram of the rejected items. Series 1 represents the difficulty index, whereas Series 2 represents the items' discrimination power. Item numbers 8 and 72 were carefully revised and selected from the rejected items with less than $p = 0.30$ to have a fair amount of item distribution in the Table of Specification (T.O.S.). This ensures that all competencies are well-represented in the 50-item researcher-validated Biology Achievement Test (RBAT); thus, the inclusion of difficult items is intentionally aimed at assessing top scorers and testing students' conceptual understanding.

Figure 3.5. Line diagram showing DI and p-values of the rejected test items

The ease index and the Point-Biserial Correlation are most often reciprocally related (Hingorjo & Jaleel, 2012), but this is not always the case. High p-value questions (easier items) discriminate poorly. In contrast, questions with a low p-value (harder items) are thought to be good discriminators. Based on the information obtained from the discussions, a 50-item RBAT was developed after reviewing all the psychometrics of the test items. Items that are acceptable/appropriate, as well as those that may be good or excellent, are all retained, while two items, numbered 8 (acceptable but discriminating item) and 72 (difficult but discriminating item), are

included to ensure fair item distribution across competencies stipulated in the curriculum guide.

After being evaluated for validity, reliability, consistency, and quality, the now 50-item RBAT was tested for internal consistency using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20). The internal consistency method revisited each student's success and failure in assessing the test item. It employed dichotomous scores of 0 and 1. Based on the computation, it came up with a KR-20 value of 0.844, which Taber (2018) describes as adequate, highly reliable, and acceptable. The RBAT (pretest, posttest, and retention test) was given to students through google forms. To ensure the validity of the data gathered, the tests were given to students during the on-campus administration of examinations or quarterly assessments. Items of the test, however, are conceptual, process-based questions answerable within a time limit of 60 minutes.

Self-Efficacy Questionnaire

A self-efficacy questionnaire was adopted and modified. It has three (3) related parts, which can be accomplished in approximately twenty (20) minutes. Part 1 of the questionnaire is the 25-item Self-Efficacy Questionnaire for Online Learning (SeQoL) from Tsai et al. (2020) & Shen et al. (2013) that was re-validated resulting in the following five (5) domains with the re-computed Cronbach alpha values, *Domain 1*: self-efficacy to complete an online course ($\alpha = 0.914$); *Domain 2*: self-efficacy to interact socially with classmates ($\alpha = 0.921$); *Domain 3*: self-efficacy to handle tools in an LMS ($\alpha = 0.819$); *Domain 4*: self-efficacy to interact with teachers

in an online course ($\alpha = 0.925$); and *Domain 5*: self-efficacy to interact with classmates for academic purposes ($\alpha = 0.911$). Part 2 is a researcher-made feedbacking tool on their self-efficacy when exposed to a remote inverted learning approach and their recommendations for its application and/or adoption in the teaching-learning process. Data were used to guide the researcher in conducting the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and Interviews to students. The results of the tool's re-validation, along with their corresponding scale statistics, are also shown in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2

Scale Statistics of the Self-Efficacy Instruments

Domains	Items	M	SD	A	ω
<i>1: Self-efficacy to complete an online course/subject</i>	1-7	8.11	1.59	0.91	0.92
<i>2: Self-efficacy to interact socially with classmates</i>	8-11	7.46	2.28	0.92	0.93
<i>3: Self-efficacy to handle tools in the LMS</i>	12-14	7.05	2.27	0.82	0.85
<i>4: Self-efficacy to interact with instructors in an online course/subject</i>	15-19	7.65	2.15	0.93	0.93
<i>5: Self-efficacy to interact with classmates for academic purposes</i>	20-25	8.13	1.90	0.91	0.92

Note: M- Mean; SD- Standard Deviation; α - Cronbach's α ; ω - McDonald's ω . Participants responded to the items using 11 response options (0= cannot do at all, 5= moderately confident can do, 10= highly confident can do)

Even though online learning is becoming more popular, not every student is successful in this setting (Tsai et al., 2020). Self-efficacy is an important factor that can predict a successful online learning experience. Tsai et al. (2020) examined the Selfefficacy Questionnaire for Online Learning (SeQoL) developed by Shen et al.

(2013), which was originally used among college students aged 18 and up, mostly Americans pursuing undergraduate degrees (90 %) and master's degrees (10%). That is why revalidation was performed to localize and contextualize the instrument and make it and its terms more appropriate for high school students.

Teacher-made pre-recorded discussion videos

The researcher created discussion videos of the biology topics fully covered for the Second Quarter of the First Semester. Eight (8) tenured science teachers of the school were invited to content validate the teacher-made discussion videos for STEM students in May to July 2022, as shown in Table 3.3. They are tenured science teachers who have permanent rank status and have served at the school for more than 30 years and not less than 5 years as science teachers, subject area experts and coordinators, laboratory incharge, and administrators,

Table 3.3

Profile of Tenured Expert Science Teachers

Years in Teaching	<i>F</i>	%
5-10	2	25
11-15	0	0
16-20	2	25
21-25	1	13
26-30	2	25
> 30	1	13
Field of Specialization	<i>F</i>	%
Biology	4	50

	Chemistry	2	25
	General Science	2	25
Highest Educational Attainment		<i>F</i>	%
	BS/ BSEd	2	25
	MA/ MS units	4	50
	MA/ MS	1	13
	EdD/ PhD units	1	13
	EdD/ PhD	0	0
Position Held		<i>F</i>	%
	JHS Teacher	2	25
	SHS Teacher	2	25
	Science Chairperson	1	13
	Lab-in-charge	1	13
	Administrator	2	25

Each discussion video was 6-10 minutes following Namaziandost & Çakmak (2020) and Brame (2016) for an appropriate and manageable screen viewing time in creating effective educational tools. This amount of time is needed to integrate the competencies and objectives of the discussion, prompt pauses for interactions, and to further elucidate deeper concepts for presentation. This guarantees that the cognitive load of the video would be regulated while also increasing students' motivation and engagement.

Figure 3.6 presents the flow and procedure of the process of the development and validation of teacher-made discussion videos. The topics are based on the curriculum guide, where the competencies for the second quarter of the course General Biology 1 were derived to conceptualize and tailor the videos.

Figure 3.6. Phases of the Development and Validation of Discussion Videos

Further, Table 3.4 shows the result of the validation of the developed videos of the topics related to Bioenergetics. A rate of 3.00 is indicated by Robles & Acedo (2019) to make the videos valid. It revealed that the teacher-made discussion videos were acceptable (4.42 ± 0.51), relevant (4.45 ± 0.40), usable (4.63 ± 0.38), and appropriate (4.70 ± 0.36).

Table 3.4*Validation Results of Teacher-made Discussion Videos*

A. Acceptability ($\alpha = .870$)	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. Suitable content; systematic explanations; aligned in the curriculum guide	4.88 \pm 0.35	Very High
2. Acceptable and appropriate explanations to students' level of understanding	4.50 \pm 0.53	Very High
3. Appropriate and accurate concepts; free from grammatical errors	4.50 \pm 0.76	Very High
4. Acceptable content to students with different learning styles	3.88 \pm 0.84	High
5. Creative approach allowing viewers to understand vital concepts worth remembering	4.38 \pm 0.52	High
Overall Mean	4.42 \pm 0.51	High
B. Relevance ($\alpha = .716$)	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. Relevant discussions on the subject matter	4.88 \pm 0.35	Very High
2. Essential tool to achieve better retention of learning	4.25 \pm 0.46	High
3. Reinforcing/supplementing concepts necessary for mastery	4.25 \pm 0.46	High
4. Substantial explanation and explicit discussion	4.38 \pm 0.74	High
5. Relevant and aligned with the skills and competencies	4.50 \pm 0.76	Very High
Overall Mean	4.45 \pm 0.40	High
C. Usability ($\alpha = .791$)	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. Innovative content; reinforces students' learning	4.63 \pm 0.52	Very High
2. Beneficial in enhancing their 21st-century skills; maximizes students' learning	4.63 \pm 0.52	Very High
3. Helpful to the viewers for understanding a series of concepts	4.63 \pm 0.52	Very High
4. Comprehensive content; enhances students' learning	4.50 \pm 0.54	Very High
5. Suitable for students' learning styles and preferences; helpful to both students and teachers	4.75 \pm 0.46	Very High
Overall Mean	4.63 \pm 0.38	Very High

D. Appropriateness ($\alpha = .838$)	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. Appropriate to helps students understand their current lesson better	4.75 \pm 0.46	Very High
2. Appropriate to develop students' critical thinking skills	4.50 \pm 0.53	Very High
3. Useful supplementary material for reinforcement and application of new learning	4.88 \pm 0.35	Very High
4. Effective video quality; free from grammatical errors	4.50 \pm 0.53	Very High
5. Effective, relevant, and useful to both students and teachers	4.88 \pm 0.35	Very High
Overall Mean	4.70 \pm 0.36	Very High

As per Cook (2013), the video-lectures do not need to be high-production-quality, but rather content-focused and concise in an inverted learning set-up. The validation has been made on the basis of the following criteria or indicators adopted from the tool of Acedo & Robles (2019), which they have used in the development and validation of educational video tutorials for 21st Century Secondary Learners. These include Acceptability ($\alpha = .870$); Relevance ($\alpha = .716$); Usability ($\alpha = .791$); and Appropriateness ($\alpha = .838$). Based on the information, the discussions videos are acceptable (Mean=4.42; SD=0.506); relevant (Mean=4.45; SD=0.396); usable (Mean=4.63; SD= 0.377); and appropriate (Mean=4.70; SD=0.355). Thus, all the video discussions are considered valid because the average rating per domain has reached High and Very High extent. The description is based on the Likert scale as follows: 1.00-1.49 for least extent; 1.50-2.49 for less extent; 2.50-3.49 for moderate extent; 3.50-4.49 for high extent; and 4.50-5.00 for very high extent. Table 3.5 further gives the video titles, thumbnails, and runtime details of teacher-made discussion videos.

Table 3.5*Video Title, Thumbnail, Runtime details of teacher-made discussion videos*

Video Title	Thumbnail	Runtime	Upload Week/ Dates
1- Introduction to Bioenergetics; Subtopics: Energy; Metabolism, and ATP		07:05	03-07 October 2022
2- ATP-ADP Cycle		05:17	03-07 October 2022
3- Redox Concept; Electron carriers		07:55	10-14 October 2022
4- Anatomy of a Leaf; Overview of Photosynthesis Part 1		07:36	10-14 October 2022
5- Overview of Photosynthesis Part 2 (Chloroplast, Light, other requirements)		05:51	17-21 October 2022
6- The Light-dependent and light-independent reactions		11:50	24-28 October 2022
7- Overview of Respiration; Glycolysis explained.		12:33	03-11 November 2022
8- Pyruvate Oxidation and Krebs Cycle		08:52	14-18 November 2022
9- Electron Transport Chain/ System; ATP counting (sugars only)		06:04	21-25 November 2022
10- Fermentation		03:27	21-25 November 2022

Inverted Learning Approach

Education in the new normal would be delivered mainly online, limited face-to-face with courses moving to digital platforms (Ahmed & Asiksoy, 2021) at primary and secondary levels of education (Fragkaki et al., 2020). In this modality, inverted learning could help students improve their creative thinking and ICT literacy by using various types of scaffolding systems (Trairut & Jeerungsuwan, 2016). This digital learning and educational technology practice promotes students' autonomy and collaboration, despite the challenges they confronted during COVID-19 (Martinelli & Zaina, 2021).

The Virtual Flipped (inverted online) is a combination of two concepts: Flipped Classroom and Virtual Classroom (Ahmed & Abdulla, 2019), but Martinelli & Zaina (2021) still regard this one as a blended strategy that divides the learning process into two distinct phases called out of class and in-class, although they may be both conducted virtually. Inverted Learning on the other hand is a response especially this time of pandemic; thus, the approach allows teachers to teach and efficiently guide students in implementing online or blended activities required to achieve better learning experience during the distance learning period (Vavichkina, 2020). However, it should be considered that by Phillips and O'Flaherty (2019), this learning model allots more time for active instructional strategies when compared to more traditional pedagogies.

Inverted learning revolutionizes traditional teaching methods and highlights students' active learning (Shao, & Liu, 2021). In terms of context, design, and method, Bredow et al. (2021) highlighted the important benefits of inverted over lecture-based instruction. When inverting the class, following Konijn et al. (2018),

there is a strong link between theory and practice, which is combined with active learning to engage students and spur them to reach a deeper level of understanding.

The Inverted Learning Approach (X1) is a digital revolution in science education for 21st-century learners. This utilizes easily available technology to replace passive learning and in-class lecturing to maximize instructional time in an online platform allocated for interactive discussions, games, laboratory activities, and other available learning resources and materials. The Expository Online Teaching (X2), on the other hand, is the conventional method of instruction that is perceived to be less or as effective as the method used in the treatment group. These approaches are observed in Table 3.6.

Table 3.6

Model of a Pretest-Posttest-Retention Control Group Design

Group						
Intervention (innovation tested)	01-----	X1	-----	02	-----	03
Conventional (existing condition)	01-----	X2	-----	02	-----	03

Note: 01- pretest; X1- use of ILA; X2- use of EOT; 02- posttest; 03- retention test

The Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) and Expository Online Teaching (EOT) both had asynchronous-synchronous combination since class schedule is composed of both online and offline/ modular periods; however, the ILA has a more controlled asynchronous component since discussion videos are being presented to them ahead of time. The two groups were grouped on the basis of their pretest (01) and were compared on their performance in the posttest (02) and in the retention test (03), which was administered one month after the posttest. ILA and EOT

likewise shared the same learning stages/ phases as templated in Table 3.7, which details the comparison of the activities between the two types of instructional approach. Both teaching and learning approaches follow Gagne’s nine events of instruction which were paralleled to the learning phase template of the school, namely Motivation and Introduction (Hooking, Activating Prior Knowledge, Informing the Learning Targets), Learning Delivery or Instruction (Presenting, Scaffolding, Applying), and Lesson Closure/ Evaluation (Feedbacking, Assessing, Generalizing).

Table 3.7

Learning Phases using Gagne’s 9 Events of Instruction

MOTIVATION/ INTRODUCTION		
	EOT	ILA
Gagne’s 9 Events of Instruction	<i>Offline period</i>	<i>*Discussion videos are given ahead</i>
1. Hooking	The teacher employs an activity to create a psychological state in each student that hopes to learn what the teacher intends to teach. This creates a connection/ rapport with the students and a sense of direction that is established throughout the session.	
2. Activating Prior Knowledge	The teacher connects the past and present topics. This clearly expresses the students' level of preparedness by enabling them to make conceptual connections and establish prerequisite knowledge (and skills) for learning the next competency/content.	The teacher establishes a link between previous and ongoing activities. This overviews the summary of the insights from the entry ticket conducted as selfassessment. This shows the students' level of preparedness and establishes the initial information needed to accomplish the task/activity for the meeting.

3. Informing the Learning Targets	The teacher communicates the learning competency and learning objectives for the live meeting. This is intended to help students in setting their own goals and managing their focus on what information and skills they are expected to learn and perform.	The teacher communicates the learning competency and learning objectives for the meeting through an entry ticket. This is to assess what students already know after viewing the pre-deployed discussion videos.
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INSTRUCTION/ LESSON DEVELOPMENT

4. Presenting	The teacher implements appropriate instructional methods in discussing the learning materials/resources	. The teacher implements appropriate instructional methods to process the results of the selfassessment and to deepen the discussion of the concepts.
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5. Scaffolding	The teacher provides specific support to students, such as unlocking the difficulties, modeling, chunking the topics, slowing down the process. This entails management of online class environment and time for students.	The teacher provides specific support to students, such as unlocking the difficulties, modeling, chunking the topics, slowing down the process, describing through logic and mind-mapping as they develop understanding of the new concept or skill. This may be done in breakout or bigger group discussions with process-based questions.
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6. Applying	The teacher conducts drills and practices. This provokes critical thinking and questioning of students and improves their understanding and skills in sharing their ideas, clarifying some concepts, and proposing solutions to real-life problems.	
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LESSON CLOSURE/ EVALUATION

7. Feedbacking	The teacher provides students with genuine feedback or a concept and practical check considering their performance in relation to the learning targets. This is intended to point out areas where students can improve or become better at completing the tasks/activities assigned to them.	
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8. Assessing	The teacher monitors and measures students' learning and success by carrying out various forms of assessments.	
9. Generalizing	The teacher wraps up the topic for the meeting and assigns relevant homework.	The teacher wraps up the topic for the meeting and directs students to accomplish their learning logs.

Ethical Considerations

Before participating in the research, the respondents, and their parents and/or guardians were asked to read and understand the assent form [see Appendix D] signed by the students and the informed consent form [see Appendix C] signed by their parents/guardian. The purpose of the study, the type of research intervention, and the criteria of selection were elucidated in the forms. In view of their being part of the study, their participation was entirely voluntary. They could withdraw at any time by not responding to the survey tools or participating in the focus group discussions and/or interviews. There would be no grade implications or consequences if they choose not to participate in or withdraw from the study at any time. If they choose to participate, they would be asked to fill out survey forms and some may take part in focus group discussions (FGD) about their online class experiences. They would also be asked to provide feedback on how the instructional approach has worked and how to improve the learning experience when the intervention is used in class. Answering the forms will take about 15 minutes. At any point, they can choose to skip any questions they do not want to answer. However, they might opt to accomplish the instrument at home when they are most comfortable or during one of their offline or asynchronous classes.

In conducting Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), participants were chosen based on the results of the test and self-efficacy survey. The selection had been based on their observable increase or decrease in scores; that means if they are higher, lower, or average scorers. However, for ethical reasons, only students who were available and willing to participate were included in the activity, though some were invited as they potentially could share more experiences and information helpful for the study. This, too, has no grade implications. There were 10-12 students scheduled for their FGD, led by the teacher-researcher himself. In this way, they could not feel awkward or threatened sharing their experiences and open-ended responses with anyone they do not know. This was also audio-recorded upon their permission, and only the teacher-researcher had the copy of the file for the sole purpose of research. The records would be temporarily stored for the duration of the study, and for analysis purposes only. There had been no questions, issues, or discussions which might be sensitive for them or potentially cause them embarrassment.

The Focus Group Discussion (FGD) focused on their first-hand experience, objective thoughts, honest opinions, ideas, and recommendations to improve the instructional approach. It further explored their perspectives in terms of how they learn, how their teacher teaches, and how they relate with their classmates during the biology course. There were three (3) FGDs conducted held online, and conversational partners had the option to open their cameras when sharing, they even could only respond either orally or in writing. Each FGD was held for sixty (60) minutes only.

For interviews, the selection was based on their peculiar and unprobed responses to the qualitative survey and FGDs; shown performance; and willingness

to take part. However, for ethical reasons, those requested were given the option to accept or refuse such an invitation. To ensure confidentiality and safety on their part, students might decide if they want to be accompanied by their parents/guardians during the online interview at their most convenient schedule. They likewise had the option of responding orally, in writing, or not at all. They might also not need to open their cameras when sharing their answers. An online interview was deliberately held for a maximum of 30 minutes to obtain more in-depth information from the participants. This activity was likewise recorded when permission was granted.

For self-efficacy survey, it was administered online, through the MS Teams. Students could skip to the next question if they do not feel comfortable answering any of the questions. They had the option to not participate if they were unable to access the materials due to an internet connection problem, emergency activities, and/or sickness. All information was kept confidential, including their name and any of their identification, which were not required at all. They might be given access to a copy of their own responses as well as the aggregate results if they so wish. Accomplishing the forms might take them 15 minutes maximum.

There was no associated risk in participating in the study. This means that students faced no specific physical, physiological, or reducing vulnerability. There were no discussions of sensitive or personal issues that made them feel uneasy. Albeit the intervention might seem apparently novel to students, selected topics in the first quarter were flipped for them to adjust to the full exposure of the approach in the second quarter. Formative assessments were typically recorded but non-graded; this was part of the orientation during the first week of classes. The grading basis or components remain consistent with the school grading policy reflected in the DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015

[Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 basic Education Program]. Therefore, there have been no changes and no source of bias in grading. On the other hand, students might also benefit either indirectly or directly from this activity.

As an instructional intervention, the Inverted Learning Approach might benefit them by advancing their study time and making them more productive and engaged in the class. Because course materials/lessons were delivered outside of class time and ahead of the week, they were more prepared and informed for scheduled synchronous meetings. Thus, their academic performance might improve. In addition, the approach was used for the students under the control group after the study. This was to address the issue of fairness when they did not receive such intervention during the study.

On confidentiality, the findings of the study might be published, but all their responses were strictly confidential, and their identity would not be associated with any of the results or used in any way. They might be aware of the consequences of disclosing their own experience or understanding, or lack thereof, when using the inverted learning approach, as an explanation for their level of academic performance. As conversational partners or participants in the FGD, they were reminded to also respect one another's ideas, experiences, and thoughts.

Data were temporarily stored in the researcher's UP email's Google Drive. Should the teacher-researcher's device be unable to respond to the account, the UP email is synced across two devices, protected by passcodes that only the teacher-researcher has access to. The files were kept only for the duration of the study and would be destroyed for three (3) years right after the analysis was completed. Moreover, the results of the study would be shared or disclosed in aggregate

following the final defense of the paper. The findings would be disseminated widely, through a school-level research colloquium, publications, and paper conferences.

Finally, since their participation was entirely voluntary, they were not compensated for taking part in the study. Likewise, they did not pay or reimburse any costs associated with their participation in the study. They have the right to access their own responses and decide whether they should be included in the data, withdraw at any time, refuse to partake in the research, be informed about how my feedback and relevant data are being processed, and lobby a complaint with the National Privacy Commission.

Data Collection Procedure

Prior to fielding the research, the paper had been subjected to a full board research ethics review last June 2022 and a certification clearance [See Appendix A] had been secured last July 2022 from the Cotabato Regional and Medical Center (CRMC) Review Ethics Committee, which is a Level 2 accredited ethics board awarded by the Philippine National Health Research System and Philippine Health Research Ethics Board (PHREB). This is to safeguard potential research participants, monitor likely risks and benefits, and establish high ethical standards where the research was conducted. For approval to conduct the pilot and actual run of the study, communication letters of permission [See Appendix B] were given to the school principal. The importance of data privacy and child protection policies was highlighted. Curriculum materials such as curriculum maps and learning plans were submitted to the chairperson of the science department for use in an online

(virtual) class observation. This has ensured uniformity and parity in teacher behavior except for the application of treatment.

In the second quarter of the school year 2022-2023 that fell from October to December 2022, the online inverted learning, and the conventional/ expository online teaching modalities were fully implemented, covering 40 class meetings/ sessions after the orientation week. To lessen the novelty effect of the method, some selected topics in the first quarter (August to October) were occasionally flipped to practice and gradually introduced the intervention to the experimental groups only. Prior to the formal classes, the RBAT (pretest) was given, where results were based to determine the homogeneity of the groups involved. Six (6) STEM classes were involved; three of which were part of the intervention group while the other three (3) classes were the conventional group. The teacher-researcher was assigned to teach the subject so that students would not be sensitized that they are used for an experiment. This kept them from acting differently or faking their responses.

Before the scheduled examination week in December 2022, the RBAT (posttest) was administered as a summative test. Its results served as the students' direct conceptual understanding of students. The self-efficacy surveys were administered before and after the intervention. This was to monitor the students' self-management, motivation, and selfbelief in the learning process at a certain interval. After a month, in January 2023, the RBAT (retention test) was administered to gauge the deferred conceptual understanding of students in the course. In December 2022, the FGDs were held to confirm the information supplied by the students in their self-efficacy surveys and responses to qualitative survey on the use of inverted learning approach. It was also an avenue to process the students' experiences as they were exposed to instructional intervention. This information

provided recommendations to further improve the adoption of an inverted learning approach. There had also been a meeting with the science department coordinator for feedback and assessment of the teacher's performance.

Data Analysis Procedure

The assignment of the classes into intervention and conventional groups was determined by their pre-test scores, which were tested for equal variances, normality, and homogeneity of groups, which means if the two groups are comparable in the study. However only the scores of students who have submitted the consent and assent forms were included for analysis. A total of two hundred and twenty-five (225) STEM students from six (6) classes were able to participate in the pretest administration. Figure 3.7 shows the pretest performance of students in RBAT. Forty (40) or 18% of them had a very low scores, none had above average to excellent scores, and the majority, 174 (77%) had low scores.

Figure 3.7. Distribution of Students by Instructional Approach thru Pretest Scores

Note: N= 225

With this information, 109 students were assigned to the conventional group (EOT), while 116 were under the intervention group (ILA) as shown in Figure 3.8. Six

(6) STEM classes were randomly distributed into each study group (EOT and ILA), each having three (3) STEM regular classes with almost identical or similar characteristics (number per class, sex, academic achievement based on Pretest scores, and subject teacher).

Figure 3.8. Randomization via random assignment of students into groups (EOT vs ILA)

Based on Levene's test of equal variances, the difference between the sample variances of all the groups is not big enough to be statistically significant. In other words, the averages of all groups assumed to be equal since $p=0.6343 > \alpha$, therefore the two groups have almost equal variances. In addition, the observed effect size is nonsignificant (0.032), which indicates that the magnitude of the difference between the averages is small. Table 9 shows the Levene's test, using F distribution (right tailed).

Table 3.8

Levene's test of equal variances of pretest scores of STEM students

Source	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F Statistic	P-value
Groups (between groups)	1	1.3284	1.3284	0.2269	0.6343
Error (within groups)	223	1305.3115	5.8534		
Total	224	1306.6399	5.8332		

Note: $P > 0.05$ is not significant

Even though the results from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test of normality revealed that the Pretest results of the conventional and intervention groups showed a difference from the normal distribution, ($D(225) = .099$, $p = .0237$). The effects level is very small which means the difference between the sample distribution and the normal distribution is very small, therefore it can be practically assume that the distribution is normal as depicted by the Q-Q plot and histogram of the data in Figure 3.9. In other words, the difference between the data sample and the normal distribution is not big enough to be statistically significant.

Figure 3.9 Q-Q Plot and Histogram of Pretest data

Given that the criteria of equal variances, assumed normal data distribution, and randomization via random assignment have been met, the data should be analyzed using parametric statistics. However, its nonparametric counterparts were also presented for comparison and consistency of statistical interpretation and results. To establish if the two groups under study are comparable, the homogeneity of data was determined by the twosample t-test (pooled variance), using T distribution ($df=223$) (two-tailed) and the two sample Mann-Whitney U, using Normal distribution (two-tailed) as both are presented in Table 3.9.

Table 3.9*Test results for the homogeneity of data between EOT and ILA*

Groups	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE	P-value (a)	P-value (b)
EOT	109	13.7	13.0	3.93	0.376	0.1858	0.1895
ILA	116	14.4	14.0	3.79	0.352		

Note: $P > 0.05$ is not significant; a- 2-sample t-test; b- 2-sample Mann-Whitney U

Two sample t-test (pooled variance), using T distribution ($df=223$) (two-tailed) indicated that the average of the conventional group is assumed to be equal to the average of intervention group since $p\text{-value} > \alpha$, therefore the two groups are homogenous. In other words, the difference between the sample average of two groups is not big enough to be statistically significant. The p-value equals 0.1858, ($p(x \leq T) = 0.9071$) and the effect size d is 0.18, which means that the magnitude of the difference between the two groups' averages is nonsignificant.

This held the same results from the two sample Mann-Whitney U Test, using Normal distribution (two-tailed) which explains that the randomly selected value of conventional group (EOT) is assumed to be equal to the randomly selected value of intervention group (ILA). In other words, the difference between the randomly selected value of EOT and ILA populations is not big enough to be statistically significant. The p value equals 0.1895, ($p(x \leq Z) = 0.9053$) while the observed standardized effect size, $Z/\sqrt{(n_1+n_2)}$, is nonsignificant (0.087). These values ($p=0.1858$; $p=0.1895$) conclude that the two groups are *comparable* and do not significantly vary in terms of their pretest results; thus, the requirement for homogeneity was met, which indicates that both groups were balanced in terms of

their academic standing, even with the age, grade, and sex distribution was similar.

Figure 3.10 shows the jittered box plot and the graph of homogeneity of measures.

Figure 3.10. Jittered box plot and graph of homogeneity measures

The data from the pretest, posttest, and retention tests were processed descriptively and inferentially. The normalized gain, also known as the g-factor, was used to represent the conceptual understanding of students in Biology from their pretest, posttest, and retention test scores. The g-factor has been widely used to evaluate students' performance in pre- and post-tests (Bao, 2006). It is defined as $g = \frac{\text{post-test} - \text{pre-test}}{\text{total score} - \text{pre-test}}$ and is calculated from the scores on a pre-test administered before the intervention and a post-test administered after the intervention (Francisco & Prudente, 2022; Stewart & Stewart, 2010). The same formula was used for posttest and retention test scores. Table 3.10 shows how to interpret the RBAT scores.

Table 3.10*Interpretation of RBAT Scores and Mean gains by Hake's Defined Range (1998)*

Raw Score	Percent	Interpretation	Mean Gain (<i>g-factor</i>)	Interpretation
41-50	91-100%	Excellent	0.70-1.00	High gain
31-40	81-90%	Above Average	0.30-0.69	Medium gain
21-30	71-80%	Average	0.00-0.29	Low gain
11-20	61-70%	Low		
00-10	50-60%	Very Low		

The data were presented using means, percentages, and qualitative descriptions. The scale of descriptive equivalents of points was designed to properly label and interpret the scores obtained. Graphs or charts were also used to supplement the data analysis to improve the interpretation of the results. Thus, making the discussion and analysis of the data gathered much elucidated. Standardized effect sizes were also included to determine the magnitude or strength of a relationship between the groups in the study; thus, describing the extent or practical significance of the using the Inverted Learning Approach. Cohen's *d* levels (1988) was likewise used to measure the effect size of the significant relationship/difference between the groups. Table 3.11 shows the effect size interpretation.

Table 3.11*Effect size interpretation*

Effect size value, <i>d</i>	Interpretation
Below 0.20	Nonsignificant
0.20- 0.49	Small effect size
0.50- 0.79	Medium effect size
0.80 and higher	Large effect size

In addition, a t-test for dependent samples (before and after) was carried out to compare and analyze their test scores, and self-efficacy levels between groups. The level of significance for evaluating the hypotheses was set at 0.05. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was run to compare the means of the students' performance between the ILA and EOT groups, and post hoc tests were also done to determine the differences between the pretest and posttest means; pretest and retention test means, and posttest and retention test means. The results of the self-efficacy survey as well as the focus group discussions and interviews were analyzed through Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA), from where information can be derived in designing the instructional improvement plan. Table 3.12 further shows how to interpret the survey instrument scales.

Table 3.12

Interpretation of the Self-Efficacy for Learning and Performance

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
8.51-10.00	Highly Confident can do	Very High Efficacy
7.01-8.50	Fairly Confident can do	High Efficacy
5.51-7.00	Moderately Confident can do	Above Moderate Efficacy
4.01-5.50	Somewhat Confident can do	Moderate Efficacy
2.51-4.00	Slightly Confident can do	Below Moderate Efficacy
1.01-2.50	Not Confident can do	Low Efficacy
0.00-1.00	Cannot do at all	Very Low Efficacy

Further, the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was also used to measure the association between the direct and deferred conceptual understanding and self-efficacy among STEM students when exposed to ILA in learning Biology. The strength

of coefficient values is based on the guidelines provided by Cohen (1988) and other researchers in the field of statistics shown in Table 3.13.

Table 3.13

Spearman's rank coefficient values interpretation

r	Interpretation
$r < 0.1$	negligible correlation
$0.1 \leq r < 0.3$	weak correlation
$0.3 \leq r < 0.5$	moderate correlation
$r \geq 0.5$	strong correlation

Participants for the focused group discussions and interviews were chosen based on the results of the test and self-efficacy survey. The selection had been based on their observable increase or decrease in scores; that means if they are higher, lower, or average scorers. To provide context for the analytic report, data extracts were also included to enrich in the discussion. The inductive bottom-up approach was used to analyze the themes.

Thematic Analysis is an experiential analysis that is inductively oriented and is based primarily on data rather than existing theories and concepts (Clarke et al., 2015). It stays as close to the meaning of the data as possible. To critically obtain the codes from the etic transcript, which is the scholarly version of the emic transcript taken from the participants' original and raw responses, hand or manual coding was used, which applied both semantic and latent (inferential) analysis.

To validate the coded and labeled transcripts, the categories formed, and the themes identified, the researcher tapped the service of three (3) English and qualitative research teachers in the SHS program of the school. This kind of audit trail

was intended to ensure that themes are derived from the categories or patterns aligned from the codes clustered. This likewise established the trustworthiness and rigor of the qualitative part of the study. Additionally, a simulacrum was created to display the visual framework and interrelationship of themes and categories critically identified.

When information power was attained, the researcher intentionally rested the data collection because responses were recurring, thus avoiding data saturation. Nonetheless, the responses are sufficient to support or address the qualitative part of the study. Figure 3.11 shows the study visual diagram.

Figure 3.11. The visual diagram of the study’s methodology

As shown in Figure 3.11, the quantitative data, which included RBAT scores in the pretest, posttest, and retention test, and the responses to the self-efficacy survey, were primarily used for data collection and analysis. Test results showed direct conceptual understanding (from posttest) and deferred conceptual understanding (from retention test), while the survey outcomes revealed their level of self-efficacy.

The participants were systematically determined for the focus group discussions and interviews, and from which qualitative data or non-numeric information were processed and analyzed. The researcher was able to identify the themes or patterns displayed in a simulacrum and develop an instructional improvement plan based on the transcripts, qualitative survey, and feedback from respondents on their experience when exposed to ILA and how the intervention affected their conceptual understanding and self-efficacy.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the analysis, and discussion of data. It specifically includes the assumption tests of data, descriptive interpretation of both quantitative and qualitative information, and presentation of statistical results, thematic analytic report, and the instructional improvement plan derived from the results.

Levels of Conceptual Understanding

EOT Pre-Post Tests Analysis

For the conventional group, one hundred six (106) students were able to take the posttest. Figure 4.1 reveals that eighty-two (82) or 77% of students were able to get average to excellent scores in the posttest, with no students getting very low scores.

Figure 4.1 Comparison of the Pretest and Posttest of the Conventional Group (EOT)

Compared to their performance in the pretest where majority, 102 or 96% got low to very low scores, students had observably improved their performance in view of the

increasing scores. The result could add to the existing evidence on the effectiveness of online learning to enhance students' conceptual understanding despite the presence of some challenges, such as internet connection, gadget usage, and new learning delivery modality. Since the beginning of the pandemic, teaching-learning processes have been remodeled to online solutions, and students' experiences with e-learning (online) courses have been positive (Zahriban Hesari et al., 2022). In fact, Wang et al. (2022) found that both secondary and tertiary students demonstrated significant online academic performance.

However, to make online instruction effective, Sun and Chen (2016) suggested to carefully plan the course content, integrate technology, have a supportive online learning community and allow interactions between the teachers and learners. Online learning could be a great way for students to improve their skills and knowledge, especially during a pandemic (Thomas et al., 2020). Even though there are drawbacks to administering online classes, such as issues with internet connection, gadgets, technical and technological know-how, and personal preparations, Lohi et al. (2020) believe that online teaching is the future of education.

The result also highlights the importance of integrating technology into the teaching-learning process. The improvement of students' conceptual understanding indicates that the integration of the technology into the process allows them to effectively understand the concepts discussed in the class. Adeyeye et al. (2022) reported similar cases where they observed that technology use has shown to improve students' academic performance although Safitri et al. (2023) reported otherwise. According to them, students had struggled to learn cell biology online. They suggested motivating students even more and making creative use of and

maximizing the online platform by incorporating investigative activities and in-depth discussions, to help them grasp the concepts.

As indicated by the result of the study, online instruction can be pursued to improve the conceptual understanding of students in biology. This can be critical because education is expected to move towards the digital environment with courses being delivered via digital platforms (Ahmed & Asiksoy, 2021). As experienced by various education institutions in the country and abroad during the pandemic and post-pandemic, teachers change the design of their work and select good practices that help them do online teaching (Vilchez-Sandoval et al., 2021; Martinelli & Zaina, 2021). Table 4.1 shows the results of the comparative analysis in students' level of direct concept understanding in Bioenergetics between pre-test and post-test in the conventional group using paired t-test.

Table 4.1

t-test Results of the Pre- and Posttest Direct Conceptual Understanding of the EOT Students

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	13.6	3.96	-18.6	p<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Posttest	25.8	6.91				

Note: p < 0.05 is significant

Data revealed that there still was a significant difference between pretest and posttest among EOT students ($t=-18.649$, $p<0.01$), as Thomas et al. (2020) highlighted that there is no significant pedagogical change or difficulty in delivery via online teaching. Teaching, whether online or in person, always needs some level of preparation. As supported by Swan (2003), there are no significant differences in

learning outcomes between online and traditional courses in terms of interactivity. It means that when teachers are intentionally and truly involved in the learning process, online teaching would be effective.

Further, the p-value generated was less than the significance level of 0.05, which means that there was statistical evidence to support that the mean difference between pretest and posttest is significant. The observed effect size d is 1.81, which indicates that the magnitude of the difference between the average of the differences and the expected average of the differences is large.

ILA Pre-Post Tests Analysis

One hundred five (105) or 94% of the students fared low to very low scores during the pretest; with only 7 or 6% average scorers, and no above average to excellent scores. Comparing the result with that of their posttest, an increment of scores was also observed. One hundred and twelve (112) or 83% of them got average to excellent scores, with only 1 or 1% very low score as presented in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2. Comparison of the Pretest and Posttest of the Intervention Group (ILA)

This is in concurrence with the findings of Çigdemoğlu et al. (2023), Shen & Chang (2023), and Paul et al. (2023), where Inverted learning promotes deeper learning and perceived deeper learning competencies than traditional classroom counterparts and improves knowledge and skills for students of varying levels of achievement. In contrast, there was feedback that the model/approach was not seen as superior to traditional lecture-based instruction (Andujar & Çakmak, 2023). Nonetheless, inverted learning provides students with more time to learn, enables them to be more independent and responsible, and enhances their creativity (Algarni, 2023; Arante & Castro, 2022).

In inverted learning, resources were employed to deliver content outside of the classroom (Rutar et al., 2016; Jakobsen & Knetemann, 2017; Gross & Musselman, 2015; Mason et al., 2013), such as video recorded discussion of the teacher or even content culled from a variety of sources (Romero-Garcia et al., 2018; Lee & Park, 2018; Ho, 2020). Table 4.2 presents the results of the comparative analysis in students' level of direct conceptual understanding in Bioenergetics between pre-test and post-test in the intervention group using paired t-test.

Table 4.2

t-test Results of the Pre- and Posttest Direct Conceptual Understanding of the ILA Students

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	14.4	3.83	-19.3	p<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Posttest	28.5	8.28				

Note: p < 0.05 is significant

Based on test results, there has been a significant difference between pretest and posttest when these students were exposed to Inverted Learning Approach ($t = -19.289$, $p < 0.01$). The p-value generated was less than the significance level of 0.05, which tells that there was statistical evidence to support that the mean difference between pretest and posttest is significant. In addition, the observed effect size d is 1.82, which indicates that the magnitude of the difference between the average of the differences and the expected average of the differences is large. It can be said that even when classes are inverted, students are able to demonstrate their learning as they devote more time in synchronous classes to collaborative and higher-order learning activities like discussions and problem-solving, while also learning content outside the classroom (Rutar et al., 2016; Romero-Garcia et al., 2018; Lin, 2019; Davies et al., 2013; Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

EOT vs ILA Post-test Analysis

Posttest scores reflect the direct conceptual understanding of STEM students. For the conventional group, 20 or 19% had above average to excellent scores; while there had been 40% from the intervention who got the same range. The intervention group comparably has higher mean score of 28.54, but with more dispersed scores represented by the standard deviation of 8.28. After the second quarter about 58% from the conventional and 43% from the intervention group got average scores in the posttest, as reflected in Table 4.3.

The normalized gain, also known as the g-factor, has been widely used to evaluate students' performance in pre- and post-tests (Bao, 2006). It is defined as $g = \frac{\text{post-test} - \text{pre-test}}{\text{total score} - \text{pre-test}}$ and is calculated from the scores on a pre-test

administered before the intervention and a post-test administered after the intervention (Francisco & Prudente, 2022; Stewart & Stewart, 2010).

Table 4.3

Interpretation of Posttest Scores by Hake's Defined Range (1998)

Range of Score	Conventional group		Intervention Group		Interpretation
	<i>f</i>	Percentage	<i>f</i>	Percentage	
41-50	3	3%	9	8%	Excellent
31-40	17	16%	36	32%	Above Average
21-30	62	58%	48	43%	Average
11-20	24	23%	18	16%	Low
00-10	0	0%	1	1%	Very Low
MEAN	25.82				28.54
SD	6.91				8.28
N	106				112

The normalized gains, g , represent the conceptual understanding of students, which is described to as their capacity to answer questions (Holme et al., 2015) and use knowledge in a variety of situations or instances (Darmofal et al., 2002). Based on the results, the average normalized gain is 0.33 (N=106) for the conventional approach and 0.41 for the inverted learning approach (N=112). Though the ILA students had received a higher computed g value than the students in EOT, the approach however was unable to help more students to reach the high gain level. Of the 116 ILA students who took the posttest, only 10% ($n = 11$) who were able to have high gain in the exam. On the other hand, only 3% ($n = 3$) of the EOT students who reached the high gain level. Table 4.4 and Figure 4.3 present the normalized gains

of the two different teaching-learning approaches, expository online teaching and inverted learning approaches.

Table 4.4

Interpretation of Mean gains (Posttest) by Hake's Defined Range (1998)

Mean Gain	Conventional group, N= 106		Intervention Group, N= 112		Interpretation
	<i>F</i>	Percentage	<i>f</i>	Percentage	
0.70-1.00	3	3%	11	10%	High gain
0.30-0.69	53	50%	65	58%	Medium gain
0.00-0.29	50	47%	36	32%	Low gain

Students who were taught using the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) have higher normalized gains than those taught using the expository online teaching (EOT). These results confirm the study of Purwanti & Suryawati (2022) that applying inverted learning approach resulted in a significant difference in the performance of students who received it compared to those exposed to online non-flipped method who got comparably lower scores. This could be also supported by Piaget's theory of equilibration as students formed already the schema prior to joining the online class. Students could have already communicated their learning with classmates and assimilated the new information with their existing schema (Mubarik et al., 2018).

Figure 4.3. Normalized Gain Comparison between the EOT and ILA Groups

The result of the study could be attributed to the ability of the ILA to introduce many core concepts outside of the classroom; hence, it can be adopted to address the challenge on improving the academic performance of learners (Silva & Galembeck, 2014; Goff et al., 2018). Even though Hew et al. (2020) discovered that participants in fully online flipped classes performed as effectively as participants in traditional set-up, and Shim & Inti (2022) stated that flipping is not effective for online courses, several studies support that ILA is better than EOT.

Jia et al. (2021) found that online flipped course participants outperformed their counterparts that used the conventional learning format, and that students' interest levels retained consistently high throughout the online inverted classes. This is supported by the study of Fadol et al. (2018), in which both the online and flipped sections outperformed the students exposed to traditional set-up; and the online flipped set-up performed better than the online non-flipped set-up.

Table 4.5 shows the t-test results of the direct conceptual understanding of the EOT and ILA students. As indicated by the result, the post-test scores of the ILA students are significantly higher ($t = -2.8539$; $p < 0.01$) than the scores of their EOT counterparts.

Table 4.5

t-test Results of Direct Conceptual Understanding between EOT and ILA Students

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
EOT	25.8	6.91	-2.8538	0.00237	Reject Ho	Significant
ILA	28.5	8.28				

Note: $p < 0.05$ is significant

The difference between the scores of the two groups can imply that the ILA has successfully make the in-class discussions more inclusive, interactive (Ahmad & Arifin, 2021) and focused (Morris & McDermott, 2022), hence, students were able to grasp easily the concepts discussed in the class. As such, the ILA can possibly help in the transitioning of the traditional in-person instruction to a fully online learning. In addition, students had mixed feelings about the effectiveness of the ILA model. Thus, Azmin et al. (2021) warned that ILA can result in ineffective online learning if it is not carefully designed. Morris and McDermott (2022) also suggested that teachers as curriculum designers must be more innovative and responsive in order to dispel the stigma that online learning is a weaker option for in-person learning.

EOT vs ILA Retention Test Analysis

The retention test scores reflect the deferred conceptual understanding of STEM students. After a month taking the posttest, it was observed that the intervention (ILA) group has 91 students or 81% average to excellent scorers; while the conventional (EOT) group only had 26 or 25% who placed under the same range. Retention is not only limited to recalling facts and information, but also a way in developing critical thinking, creativity, relationship between concepts, and transfer of understanding (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Haniah et al., 2020; Sholihah & Lastariwati, 2020). The intervention group comparably has higher mean score of 28.18 ± 7.52 ; while the conventional group had 17.49 ± 6.60 . Table 4.6 show the comparative difference of the retention test results between the conventional and intervention groups.

Table 4.6

Interpretation of Retention Test Scores by Hake's Defined Range (1998)

Range of Score	Conventional group		Intervention Group		Interpretation
	<i>F</i>	Percentage	<i>F</i>	Percentage	
41-50	2	2%	8	7%	Excellent
31-40	3	3%	38	34%	Above Average
21-30	21	20%	45	40%	Average
11-20	69	65%	20	18%	Low
00-10	11	10%	1	1%	Very Low
MEAN	17.49		28.18		
SD	6.60		7.52		
N	106		112		

The results in Table 4.6 prove the findings of Chettaoui et al. (2022) on their multimodal embodied interaction modalities that the use of ILA has improved the retention of students. When students practice recovering previously studied information, they can achieve higher long-term retentive learning than simply reviewing or restudying (Nero & Zulkipli, 2021). This process is called as the testing effect (Carpenter et al., 2006; McDaniel et al., 2007; Nero & Zulkipli, 2021) or the retrieval practice effect (Carpenter et al., 2006; Karpicke & Roediger, 2007; Nero & Zulkipli, 2021). In most learning processes, retention of information is highly regarded as important (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Nurisya et al., 2016; Talar & Gozaly, 2020). Because learning gains may be forgotten, it is crucial to focus on efficient teaching strategies that encourage students to learn and form meaningful associations, resulting in learning that lasts longer (Al-Balushi & Al-Balushi, 2018). Therefore, the results show that ILA rather than EOT can reinforce deferred understanding of students. Table 4.7 presents the comparative mean gains between the EOT and ILA groups.

Table 4.7

Interpretation of Mean gains (Retention test) by Hake's Defined Range (1998)

Mean Gain	Conventional group, N=106		Intervention Group, N= 112		Interpretation
	<i>f</i>	Percentage	<i>f</i>	Percentage	
0.70-1.00	2	2%	8	7%	High gain
0.30-0.69	10	9%	67	60%	Medium gain
0.00-0.29	94	89%	37	33%	Low gain

Students who were taught using the Inverted Learning Approach (Intervention) have higher normalized gains than those taught using the conventional online lecture discussion (conventional). Data revealed that the average normalized gain is 0.10 (N=106) for the conventional approach, which indicates a lower mean gain while 0.39 for the inverted learning approach (N=112), which indicates a medium gain for the deferred conceptual understanding. The higher mean gain of the ILA group for the deferred conceptual understanding can indicate that ILA is able to develop students' ability to retain concepts and details in memory (Tapilow & Wawan, 2008) for a particular timeframe compared to EOT.

This is crucial in teaching and learning process (Adiansyah et al., 2021; Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001) because education is supposedly aimed to retain content and develop meaningful conceptual understanding (Witt et al., 2021) so that students can build on it and apply it to practice. In addition, as Adiansyah et al. (2021), Haniah et al. (2020) and Sholihah & Lastariwati (2020) had indicated, retention is not only limited to recalling facts and information but also a way to develop critical thinking, creativity, and skill to see the relationship between concepts, and transfer of understanding. This is the reason why educators should be aware of the significant amount of learning plateau that occurs during instruction and use of instructional strategies so that they would be able to provide longterm learning to their students (Schneid et al., 2019).

Further, shown in Table 4.8 is the comparative analysis of the retention test results between the students who were taught using the expository online approach (conventional) and those students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach (intervention). Through a two-sample t-test (pooled variance), using T distribution (df=216), it shows that there was a significant difference between the retention test

scores between the two groups; specifically, that the mean of the conventional group is significantly lower than the intervention group ($t = -11.10$, $p < 0.01$). The p-value generated was less than the significance level of 0.05, which suggests that there was statistical evidence to support that the mean difference between their deferred conceptual understanding is significant. In addition, the observed effect size d is 1.50, which implies that the magnitude of the difference between the two means is large.

Table 4.8

t-test Results of Deferred Conceptual Understanding between EOT and ILA Students

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
EOT	17.53	6.62	-11.10	P < 0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
ILA	28.41	7.77				

Note: $p < 0.05$ is significant

The result implies that inverted learning can influence deferred learning since the retention test results of students were observably and significantly better than those taught using the expository online teaching. As far as discovering emerging innovative student-centered pedagogy to improve understanding and retention in biology (Bizimana et al., 2022) is concerned, inverted learning approach improves students' self-directed learning, learning satisfaction, efficacy, learning achievement (Kim & Lim, 2021), retention, and attitude (Tutal & Yazar, 2021). In real life application, this deferred understanding would address the gap between what the students learned and the skillsets they acquired at school and what the workplace need or require among the graduates (MurilloZamorano et al., 2019). Thus, exploring

on this variable is still recommendable to further explain how instructional interventions such as ILA can affect the students' retentive learning or deferred conceptual understanding and its application.

Test Improvement (Pre-Post-Retention Tests)

Results from the Analysis of Variance, using F distribution $df(2,315)$ comparing the means from pretest (Mean= 13.63 ± 3.96), posttest (Mean= 25.82 ± 6.91), and retention (Mean= 17.53 ± 6.62) test of students who were taught using the expository online teaching (EOT) revealed that the groups' means were not equal as shown in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9

ANOVA Results – EOT Test Improvement

Source	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F Statistic	P-value
Groups (between groups)	2	8215.328	4107.664	114.8445	<0.001
Error (within groups)	315	11266.6609	35.7672		
Total	317	19481.9888	61.4574		

Note: P < 0.05 is significant

The same results were observed in Table 4.10 showing the Analysis of Variance, using F distribution $df(2,333)$ comparing the means from pretest (Mean= 14.37 ± 3.83), posttest (Mean= 28.78 ± 8.28), and retention (Mean= 28.41 ± 7.77) test of students who were exposed to Inverted Learning Approach (ILA). The difference between the averages of some groups under EOT and ILA was sufficient to be statistically significant to describe $F= 114.84$, $p= <.001$ and $F= 158.01$, $p= <.001$,

respectively. Both groups generated a p-value, which is lesser than the significance level of 0.05 with large effect sizes of 0.85 for EOT and 0.97 for ILA. These figures therefore can mean that both instructional interventions are equally effective for students as per Hew et al. (2020). Thus, post-hoc analyses were conducted to further understand the differences between the tests per group.

Table 4.10

ANOVA Results – ILA Test Improvement

Source	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F Statistic	P-value
Groups (between groups)	2	15122.0426	7561.0213	158.0104	< 0.001
Error (within groups)	333	15934.5175	47.8514		
Total	335	31056.5601	92.7061		

Note: P < 0.05 is significant

Post Hoc Analysis – EOT vs ILA

After running a post hoc analysis using Tukey HSD / Tukey Kramer in Table 4.11 for students exposed to EOT and Table 26 for students taught using ILA, there were significant differences between the pretest and posttest means; pretest and retention test means, and posttest and retention test means. The only difference in the result was observed in the ILA group where posttest and retention test results did not significantly vary, which implies that ILA can sustain conceptual understanding over time since retention test was administered after 4 weeks. This supports the idea that ILA can improve the deferred conceptual understanding of students in learning Biology.

Table 4.11*Post hoc Analysis Results – EOT*

Pair	Difference	SE	Q	Lower CI	Upper CI	Critical Mean	p-value
x1-x2	12.1887	0.5809	20.983	10.2542	14.1232	1.9345*	1.306e-10
x1-x3	3.8962	0.5809	6.7074	1.9617	5.8307	1.9345*	0.000009535
x2-x3	8.2925	0.5809	14.2756	6.358	10.2269	1.9345*	1.307e-10

Note: x1- Pretest; x2- Posttest; x3- Retention test

Table 4.12*Post hoc Analysis Results – ILA*

Pair	Difference	SE	Q	Lower CI	Upper CI	Critical Mean	p-value
x1-x2	14.4107	0.6536	22.0469	12.2345	16.5869	2.1762*	1.325e-10
x1-x3	14.0446	0.6536	21.4868	11.8684	16.2209	2.1762*	1.325e-10
x2-x3	0.3661	0.6536	0.5601	-1.8102	2.5423	2.1762	0.9172

Note: x1- Pretest; x2- Posttest; x3- Retention test

Students were asked how ILA has helped them improve their academic performance. Because the results showed that the approach had an effect on information retention, the majority of their responses revolved around the discussion videos that were provided prior to instruction. A male student from the Focus group mentioned that discussion videos help them rewatch or relearn concepts (*"helpful po yung discussion video para mabalikan ung topic..."*). This was supported by one of the

narrations, "pwede kong ipause para may matakde down notes" [*"I can pause the videos when I want to take down important notes, and then play it to resume"*]. Even though they shared some struggles to the learning environment, they also expressed desire and excitement when they understood the topic (*"When I do get or understand the lesson, it's kinda enjoyable"*, A. Dipantar, Interview, December 13, 2022). Several participants agreed that using videos in the ILA is especially helpful. These could be plausible explanations for the observed learning retention.

Level of Self-Efficacy

Self-Efficacy among students – EOT vs ILA

Grabau (2015) defined self-efficacy as a self-assessment of one's ability to master a task, which includes internal behavioral patterns such as judgments about one's ability to complete a task or goal (Harsch, 2008; Schunk & Miller, 2002; Riskiningtyas & Wangid, 2019; Wang & Tsai, 2016) and confidence in one's performance and abilities (Pintrich et al., 1991; Grabau, 2015). Self-efficacy plays a critical role in determining student performance (Broadbent, 2016). In the new normal set-up, student performance and output may be determined by various online activity and engagement.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used to identify and ensure the suitability of a domain for a specific construct (Mustafa et al., 2020; Alavi et al., 2020). The compatibility of the domains was tested to make sure that the obtained factors match the constructs. The domains of self-efficacy in this study were grouped into Independence, Competence, and Interaction. CFA is predicated on the researcher

having a strong theory about the structure of the concept under investigation (Hox, 2021). The data-model fit was evaluated using several indices, including the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), and the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). A CFI close to 0.95, an SRMR less than 0.08, and a TFI greater than 0.90 indicate an acceptable model-data fit (Tsai et al., 2020). The study's model is a good fit. In other words, the data from the study are highly representative of the data expected in the actual population. The path diagram displaying the fit measures of the Self-Efficacy domains under study is shown in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4. A path diagram showing the Fit Measures of the Self-Efficacy Domains

To elaborate the results on these domains (*Dm*) in the context of the study, self-efficacy of students while learning online is affected by their ability to successfully engage at school, which is a concept that may help them become more autonomous or in-control of their performance by studying independently the learning materials, which is referring to *Independence, Ind*. It is a core component of social cognition that

influences their motivation, learning, and academic success (Dinther et al., 2011; Mohamed et al., 2021; Zajacova et al., 2005), which is *Competence, Cmp*. Lastly, it is also influenced by the confidence in their ability to interact in an online environment (Code et al., 2021), which is referring to *Interaction, Int*.

Independence

Independence is reflected in Domain 1 of the self-efficacy tool. It describes how STEM students, on their own, can study and complete a task or class. Self-efficacy also leads to feelings of greater confidence in acting on one's goals and intentions, making it easier to make positive changes toward those goals. Both students from EOT and ILA group have moved from Above Moderate to High level of Self-Efficacy as they have been always willing to face challenges in the new normal, as evidenced by the means 7.37 ± 1.66 and 7.88 ± 1.86 respectively. Alongside this is their capacity to understand complex concepts using the online learning modalities (EOT= 7.10 ± 1.58 ; ILA= 7.32 ± 1.86). Table 4.13 shows level of self-efficacy among students in terms of being independent learners.

Table 4.13

Domain 1- Self-efficacy to complete an online subject ($\alpha = 0.914$)

Items	CONVENTIONAL				INTERVENTION			
	BEFORE		AFTER		BEFORE		AFTER	
	Mean \pm SD	Description						
Willing to face challenges	6.90 \pm 1.72	Above Mod	7.37 \pm 1.66	High	6.84 \pm 1.85	Above Mod	7.88 \pm 1.86	High

Create a plan to complete the given assignments	6.95 ± 1.93	Above Mod	7.33 ± 1.68	High	7.11 ± 1.94	High	7.96 ± 1.59	High
Adjusting the learning styles	7.29 ± 1.52	High	8.03 ± 1.59	High	7.32 ± 1.88	High	8.21 ± 1.77	High
Understand complex concepts	6.39 ± 1.64	Above Mod	7.10 ± 1.58	High	6.51 ± 1.97	Above Mod	7.32 ± 1.86	High
Keep up with course schedule	6.64 ± 1.64	Above Mod	7.43 ± 1.54	High	7.04 ± 2.01	High	7.80 ± 1.90	High
Evaluate own assignments	7.21 ± 1.49	High	7.74 ± 1.42	High	7.45 ± 1.79	High	7.98 ± 1.74	High
Complete an online course	7.44 ± 1.84	High	7.31 ± 1.67	High	7.21 ± 1.90	High	8.07 ± 1.74	High
Overall Mean ± SD	6.97 ± 1.68	Above Mod	7.47 ± 1.59	High	7.07 ± 1.91	High	7.89 ± 1.78	High

Note: **8.51-10.00** (*Very High*); **7.01-8.50** (*High*); **5.51-7.00** (*Above Moderate*); **4.01-5.50** (*Moderate*); **2.51-4.00** (*Below Moderate*); **1.01-2.50** (*Low*); **0.00-1.00** (*Very Low*)

It is also quite revealing how EOT students improved their self-efficacy in creating plans to complete their assignments (Mean= 7.33 ± 1.68) and in keeping up with the course (Mean= 7.43 ± 1.54) which improved in the quarter. The ILA group has maintained with High level of efficacy in both items, which may be attributed to the little by little introduction of the approach from the start of classes to avoid the novelty effect of the approach if it was used directly during the intended quarter of the study. Students taught using ILA improved their independence, learned strategies which helped them to achieve at higher level of this domain (Mean= 7.89 ± 1.78),

compared to those under expository approach (Mean= 7.74 ± 1.42). ILA was able to promote these students were able to adjust their own learning style (Mean= 8.21 ± 1.77) given the shift of learning modalities. They become more independent and responsible learners (Willey & Gardner, 2014). The new normal set-up offers innovative opportunities to learn as well, not only improving their academic achievement but their capacity for autonomous learning (Angelina, 2019).

Compared to students exposed to EOT, ILA students have become so selfdetermined (Khayat et al., 2021) that they can create a plan to complete (Mean= 7.96 ± 1.59) and evaluate their assignments (Mean= 7.98 ± 1.74). An account from a female participant in the focus group conveyed, *“mas madali sa akin yung discussion vid kasi kadalasan po mahiya po ako mag tanong, at pwede ko maulit ulitin ung video, if meron akong ndi maintinidhan, pwede ako mag research. If wala na talaga sa internet, mas confident po akong magtanong po thru PM. Tapos mas madali saakin, kasi nagsusulat ako ng reviewer.”* [Easier for me to have discussion videos. As a shy type of a person, most often I research over the internet the questions I have in mind about the concepts in the discussion videos presented. If I am not satisfied with what I researched, I directly message the teacher. Also, this allows me to put down my thoughts and make reviewers], which represents independent learning.

Since ILA provides support for students especially with the time (Rosen et al., 2017) they really need to accomplish things, the approach emphasizes autonomy, context, development, and experience (Yin, 2015). It also fosters students' confidence and competence and facilitates active learning (Bingen et al., 2020). When the content is brought home or accessible at home, it is also a need to consider how parental involvement can be crucial (Muhajir & Syahrul, 2022). As ILA develops independent learning, a good environment at home must be also regarded. Thus, it

can be suggested for a collaborative effort between the teachers and parents, especially with regard high school learning context.

Overall, both the conventional and intervention groups achieved a High level of learning independence. Students are prepared to face academic challenges, develop a plan to complete assigned tasks, adjust their learning style, understand difficult concepts, stick to the course schedule, and review their own work to complete the online course. This characteristic of students who are taking responsibility for their learning (Mason et al., 2013) could make them more likely to be intrinsically driven (Ryan & Deci, 2000), such as feeling more competent and autonomous, especially speaking to ILA students.

Competence

One of the universal psychological needs is competence (Ryan & Deci, 2000), which is one of the components of the self-determination theory (Muir, 2020). Domain 3 of the self-efficacy tool refers to the capacity of students to accomplish tasks through their own efforts, rather than relying on others. This is competence. Self-efficacy beliefs (Gore et al., 2005) are the key to understanding why people initiate behavior, how much effort they put into it, and how they persevere in the face of adversity. Students with low self-efficacy rarely complete tasks and assignments, struggle to make decisions and tend to be frustrated when things go wrong. Table 4.14 shows level of self-efficacy among students in terms of their competence. Competence refers to doing what you are best at, even if that means performing some tasks poorly at first. An integral part of learning is the process that improves a person's belief in their competence to succeed.

Table 4.14*Domain 3- Self-efficacy to handle tools in an LMS ($\alpha = 0.819$)*

Items	CONVENTIONAL				INTERVENTION			
	BEFORE		AFTER		BEFORE		AFTER	
	Mean \pm SD	Description						
Send email to others with/without attached files	6.33 \pm 2.33	Above Mod	7.17 \pm 2.21	High	6.61 \pm 2.58	Above Mod	7.48 \pm 2.40	High
Reply to others' messages in a discussion	6.73 \pm 1.55	Above Mod	7.32 \pm 1.69	High	6.26 \pm 2.35	Above Mod	7.46 \pm 2.23	High
Post a new message in a discussion/thread	6.02 \pm 1.90	Above Mod	6.63 \pm 2.13	Above Mod	5.80 \pm 2.43	Above Mod	7.20 \pm 2.43	High
Overall Mean	6.36 \pm 1.93	Above Mod	7.04 \pm 2.01	High	6.22 \pm 2.45	Above Mod	7.38 \pm 2.35	High

Note: **8.51-10.00** (Very High); **7:01-8.50** (High); **5.51-7.00** (Above Moderate); **4.01-5.50** (Moderate); **2.51-4.00** (Below Moderate); **1.01-2.50** (Low); **0.00-1.00** (Very Low)

As shown in Table 4.14, students who received the Inverted Learning Approach were able to better submit their outputs whether with files such as links or digital outputs or without attachments (Mean= 7.48 \pm 2.40) when they require to submit textual responses only; reply in the chat box or meeting chats (Mean= 7.46 \pm 2.23); and respond when asked about their ideas on issues or particular discussions (Mean= 7.20 \pm 2.43).

This Above Moderate increased to High level of Self-Efficacy of students under EOT and ILA in handling tools and features of the Learning Management System (LMS) such as sending files through emails and replying to messages of class mates can be explained by the introduction of online learning modalities and intensified use of the MS Teams for the official use of the school in all teaching-learning activities and interactions. Based on data, both groups got high level of self-efficacy in handling

the different tools in the learning management system, that they independently operate and learn to use technology for learning. While according to Phillips and O'Flaherty (2019), this as a learning model allots more time for active instructional strategies when compared to more traditional pedagogies. It gives students more opportunities to develop higher-order thinking skills (HOTs) like laboratory courses (Ahmed & Asiksoy, 2021).

However, ILA students (Mean=7.20 ± 2.43) were able to let students feel more competent as they post or respond to messages and questions during the synchronous online sessions. Students felt that they interacted more with their instructors and peers (Murray et al., 2015). This difference highlighted how ILA can be seamless by allowing students to access the instructional materials without being limited by time and space (Hwang et al., 2019), and thus they come to class even more prepared and with more questions for the synchronous online class period. As one male participant from the focus group honestly stated, “...*nag improve po ako sir...nung prepandemic (pandemic years) ginagawa ko lang nagakopya, pahayahay lang...*” [My academic performance improved this year; unlike before that I sometimes cheat and just careless]. This experience is a form of competence after ILA was used in class.

Sufficient time, however, is needed for students to understand the content from the lectures given in the form of a video (Ibrahim, Khairudin, & Salleh, 2018). This is something that ILA gives to student as to explain the vertical movement of their level of efficacy from Above Moderate to High (7.20 ± 2.43). This result implies the need to have extra support during the initial stages of inverted classes (Fisher et al., 2015); thus classes to receive the ILA were transitioned to this kind of approach to address adjusting to the new approach of teaching-learning experience.

Interaction

Online classes are a better learning platform during these unprecedented times, and they have greatly aided students by allowing them to stay at home and study without fear of contracting the virus (Sharma, 2020). While the face-to-face to face-to-screen transition was relevant, there were some difficulties encountered in the platform utilization for online sessions reflecting emotions in face-to-face interaction (Jeong & GonzálezGómez, 2021).

Students who received the intervention were noticeably develop friendships with classmates (Mean= 8.63 ± 1.67). Such kind of interaction often drives self-efficacy. Inverted learning approach promotes interaction between teachers and students (Le et al., 2015), and encourages students for becoming self-learners (Mason et al., 2013), which affects their engagement or interaction (Gopalan et al., 2021). ILA Students have vertically increased their level of efficacy on paying attention to other students' social actions from Above Moderate to High after the quarter because the approach drives them to be more responsive (Doman & Webb, 2017), reflective (Steen-Utheim & Foldnes, 2018), and interactive (Lee et al., 2014) with their peers. These discussions are reflected in Table 4.15 showing the social Interaction of students with their classmates.

Table 4.15

Domain 2- Self-efficacy to interact socially with classmates ($\alpha = 0.921$)

	CONVENTIONAL				INTERVENTION			
	BEFORE		AFTER		BEFORE		AFTER	
Items	Mean \pm SD	Descrption						

Pay attention to other students' social actions	7.17 ± 1.91	High	7.36 ± 1.61	High	7.00 ± 1.91	Above Mod	7.72 ± 1.86	High
Initiate social interaction with classmates	7.23 ± 1.97	High	7.75 ± 1.81	High	7.49 ± 1.98	High	8.00 ± 1.70	High
Apply different social interaction skills	7.30 ± 1.82	High	7.84 ± 1.88	High	7.47 ± 1.67	High	8.20 ± 1.50	High
Develop friendship with classmates	8.19 ± 2.13	High	8.39 ± 1.71	High	8.30 ± 1.77	High	8.63 ± 1.67	Very High
Overall Mean	7.47 ± 1.96	High	7.84 ± 1.75	High	7.57 ± 1.83	High	8.01 ± 1.68	High

Note: 8.51-10.00 (Very High); 7.01-8.50 (High); 5.51-7.00 (Above Moderate); 4.01-5.50 (Moderate); 2.51-4.00 (Below Moderate); 1.01-2.50 (Low); 0.00-1.00 (Very Low)

Education in the new normal entails virtual learning and online classes (Fahim, 2021), with extensive teacher and student roles (Business World, 2020). Doing online lectures requires time, effort, and planning (Lal, 2020), unlike the traditional teaching comparably is much convenient for most teachers and students. Inverting the class has a greater interactivity, which increases self-efficacy (Bouwmeester et al., 2019). It also revealed that students exposed to ILA tend to develop friendship among classmates (Mean= 8.63 ± 1.67; Very High) compared with EOT students.

In addition, Domain 4 in Table 4.16 supports also the Interaction phase as both EOT students, described by the means (7.71 ± 2.07; 7.32 ± 2.17) and ILA students, with Means= 7.78 ± 2.01; 7.60 ± 2.00, interact by clearly asking questions to their teacher and initiate discussions with the teacher This could be explained by the fact that they all have experienced online learning modality and such movement is an improvement after the quarter since MS Teams are used officially as the school's learning management system.

Interaction with students is the action of providing feedback on student work, encouraging students to be active participants, and improving classroom interactions between teacher and students. Notably in Table 4.16, students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach can ask questions and seek help from the teacher (Mean= 8.35 ± 1.86). Because of this, students feel good about their capabilities, and express respectfully their opinions (Mean= 8.39 ± 1.62), which can help build confidence and increase performance.

Table 4.16

Domain 4- Self-efficacy to interact with instructors in an online course ($\alpha = 0.925$)

Items	CONVENTIONAL				INTERVENTION			
	BEFORE		AFTER		BEFORE		AFTER	
	Mean ± SD	Description	Mean ± SD	Description	Mean ± SD	Description	Mean ± SD	Description
Clearly ask my questions to instructor	6.74 ± 2.12	Above Mod	7.71 ± 2.07	High	6.71 ± 2.22	Above Mod	7.78 ± 2.01	High
Seek help from instructor when needed	7.52 ± 2.13	High	7.98 ± 2.17	High	7.40 ± 2.00	High	8.35 ± 1.86	High
Timely inform the instructor when unexpected situations arise	7.23 ± 1.77	High	7.66 ± 2.02	High	7.29 ± 1.96	High	8.20 ± 1.70	High
Initiate discussions with the instructor	6.71 ± 2.04	Above Mod	7.32 ± 2.17	High	6.37 ± 2.10	Above Mod	7.60 ± 2.00	High
Express my opinions to instructor respectfully	7.10 ± 2.19	High	8.15 ± 2.19	High	7.17 ± 2.23	High	7.97 ± 1.98	High
Overall Mean	7.06 ± 2.05	High	7.76 ± 2.12	High	6.99 ± 2.10	Above Mod	7.98 ± 1.91	High

Note: **8.51-10.00** (Very High); **7:01-8.50** (High); **5.51-7.00** (Above Moderate); **4.01-5.50**

(Moderate); **2.51-4.00** (Below Moderate); **1.01-2.50** (Low); **0.00-1.00** (Very Low)

A student's self-efficacy while learning online is therefore influenced by their confidence in their ability to interact in an online environment (Code et al., 2021). Interaction can also take place with the learning materials, particularly as one male participant from the focus group shared, “*anytime pwede ireview ung videos sa mga students na ndi nakapasok sa klase nila*” [Students can review or rewatch the videos; especially those who could not attend the online meetings or absent]. In case students cannot make it present during the online classes, they can access the learning materials and receive the content through the discussion videos made by the teacher. In this way, the student can still cope with the missed topics in class.

Domain 5 specifically describes that both groups have high levels of interaction since classes have already been conducted virtually, they may have been accustomed to interact with classmates in an online learning environment. Data revealed that students who were exposed to Inverted learning approach were more active in cooperating, interacting, and explaining with their peers than when they were in a traditional class, same goes with the results of Zhao and Wang (2018). However, one highlight was that the ILA students have very high level of self-efficacy (Mean= 8.60 ± 1.43) in providing help to their classmates when their assistance is needed.

A student may have low self-efficacy because they are not confident in their abilities to follow directions or use technology. In this case, students who feel their interactions with teachers are positive and supportive will likely be more motivated to learn. Table 4.17 reveals that students under the intervention group were able to interact with classmates for academic purposes, such as they were active during the

class and responding to others for discussion (Mean= 8.13 ± 1.89). Their desire to reach out others and give their help was evident to be very high (8.60 ± 1.43).

Table 4.17

Domain 5- Self-efficacy to interact with classmates for academic purposes ($\alpha = 0.911$)

Items	CONVENTIONAL				INTERVENTION			
	BEFORE		AFTER		BEFORE		AFTER	
	Mean ± SD	Descr ption						
Actively participate in online discussions	6.75 ± 1.77	Above Mod	7.56 ± 1.98	High	6.84 ± 1.85	Above Mod	7.61 ± 1.89	High
Effectively communicate with my classmates	7.71 ± 1.84	High	8.09 ± 1.89	High	7.50 ± 1.83	High	8.13 ± 1.89	High
Respond to other students in a timely manner	7.41 ± 1.89	High	8.04 ± 1.99	High	7.49 ± 1.73	High	7.99 ± 1.84	High
Request help from others when needed	7.86 ± 1.81	High	8.06 ± 2.06	High	7.81 ± 1.84	High	8.31 ± 1.77	High
Express my opinions to ± other students respectfully	7.57 ± 1.82	High	7.83 ± 2.24	High	7.55 ± 2.03	High	8.39 ± 1.62	High
Provide help to other students when assistance is needed	7.65 ± 2.01	High	8.41 ± 2.15	High	7.92 ± 1.79	High	8.60 ± 1.43	Very High
Overall Mean	7.49 ± 1.86	High	8.00 ± 2.05	High	7.52 ± 1.85	High	8.17 ± 1.74	High

Note: 8.51-10.00 (Very High); 7:01-8.50 (High); 5.51-7.00 (Above Moderate); 4.01-5.50 (Moderate); 2.51-4.00 (Below Moderate); 1.01-2.50 (Low); 0.00-1.00 (Very Low)

This may be explained that pre-recorded discussion videos allow them to increase collaborative dialogue among their peers (Zarrinabadi & Ebrahimi, 2019). Since Inverted Learning Approach promote focus on knowledge and comprehension level at home (Bramley, 2018), students can do peer-to-peer interaction (Lee et al., 2014) and become more responsive for other students (Doman & Webb, 2017). The results imply academic support from parents and school administrators to upskill or retool teachers in understanding more and applying inverted learning approach (ILA) in practice.

As evidenced, students learn self-efficacy during the period when they are fully engaged with other students in an inverted learning approach where they can have a greater role in teaching by answering questions and discussing ideas with their peers or classmates (Mean= 8.17 ± 1.74). As supported by Steen-Utheim and Foldnes (2018), this approach provides learners with favorable, comfortable, enabling, and social learning experiences (Zainuddin & Attaran, 2016).

Students are less likely to pursue the learning resources they are being taught if they feel they are not prepared to do so. Inverted learning allows students to connect and demonstrate their understanding of the content delivery component of a class is removed from the traditional classroom setup (Jakobsen & Knetemann, 2017; Arfstrom & Network, 2013; Sletten, 2015). Encouraging them to work independently and developing their belief to complete an online course or activity is one observable results among students especially those who received the inverted learning (Mean= 7.89 ± 1.78). Finally, they feel much more comfortable if they do not feel pressured to perform better than the other students in class, thus a need to interact socially and form social interactions with classmates (Mean= 8.01 ± 1.68). Data revealed in Table

4.18 the different self-efficacy means between the conventional and intervention groups.

Table 4.18

Comparison of Self-Efficacy Means Between EOT and ILA Groups

GROUP	CONVENTIONAL				INTERVENTION			
	BEFOR		AFTEI		BEFORE		AFTER	
Domains	Mean ± SD	Descr iption	Mean ± SD	Descr iption	Mean ± SD	Descr iption	Mean ± SD	Descr iption
1: Self-efficacy to complete an online course/ subject (α = 0.914)	6.97 ± 1.68	Above Mod	7.47 ± 1.59	High	7.07 ± 1.91	High	7.89 ± 1.78	High
2: Self-efficacy to interact socially with classmates (α = 0.921)	7.47 ± 1.96	High	7.84 ± 1.75	High	7.57 ± 1.83	High	8.01 ± 1.68	High
3: Self-efficacy to handle tools in a CMS (α = 0.819)	6.36± 1.93 (α	Above Mod	7.04 ± 2.01	High	6.22 ± 2.45	Above Mod	7.38 ± 2.35	High
4: Self-efficacy to interact with instructors in an online course (α = 0.925)	7.06 ± 2.05	High	7.76 ± 2.12	High	6.99 ± 2.10	Above Mod	7.98 ± 1.91	High
5: Self-efficacy to interact with classmates for academic purposes (α = 0.911)	7.49 ± 1.86	High	8.00 ± 2.05	High	7.52± 1.85	High	8.17 ± 1.74	High
OVERALL MEAN	7.07 ± 1.90	High	7.62 ± 1.90	High	7.07 ± 2.03	High	7.89 ± 1.89	High

Note: 8.51-10.00 (Very High); 7.01-8.50 (High); 5.51-7.00 (Above Moderate); 4.01-5.50 (Moderate); 2.51-4.00 (Below Moderate); 1.01-2.50 (Low); 0.00-1.00 (Very Low)

Comparing EOT and ILA students on the five domains of self-efficacy, it is highlighted that EOT students have moved from Above Moderate to High Level of SelfEfficacy on Domain 1- Self-efficacy to complete an online course/ subject (α =

0.914); while ILA students have the same improvement of self-efficacy level on Domain 4- Selfefficacy to interact with instructors in an online course ($\alpha = 0.925$). Students exposed to EOT have been used to online teaching and that initially they feel less committed to online set-up since they look forward to re-opening or returning of face-to-face classes at that time. As self-efficacy plays a pivotal role in the processes and outcomes of the present online learning modality (Tsai et al., 2011), they eventually develop this component as to successfully take the quarter (Shen et al., 2013).

However, students taught using ILA have maintained their High Level of SelfEfficacy as they were gradually introduced or exposed to the approach prior to the formal conduct of the study during the second quarter. Thus, they observably have higher learning goals (Levterova-Gadjalova & Tsokov, 2021) and are more dedicated to participate in the online learning modality. Moreover, it was found out that ILA students have improved their self-efficacy in interacting with their teacher in the online class since they have become immersed with the content thru the discussion videos they watched at home and have already been prepared for the synchronous online class discussion. This explains the movement from being Above Moderate (6.99 ± 2.10) to High Level (7.98 ± 1.91) of Self-Efficacy.

Self-Efficacy Analysis - EOT vs ILA

Through the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank, using Normal distribution and paired t-test, it was revealed that there was a *significant difference* in the level of self-efficacy before and after the implementation of the expository online teaching ($W= 2122.50$, $t= -2.59$, $p=0.03$) and the inverted learning approach ($W= 1608$, $t= -4.25$, $p= < .001$) among STEM students in a General Biology course. The p-values generated were lesser than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates that there was still statistical evidence to support that the mean difference in the self-efficacy level of students who received either the expository online approach or the inverted learning approach is significant. Likewise, the observed standardized effect size, Z/\sqrt{n} , is 0.21 for EOT and for ILA is $Z/\sqrt{n}= 0.42$, which both mean to have a magnitude of the difference between the self-efficacy levels before and the value from after that is just small or minimal. Tables 4.19 and Table 4.20 display the results of the comparative analysis in students' level of self-efficacy before and after the implementation of the teaching-learning approach in Bioenergetics in the conventional and intervention groups, respectively.

Table 4.19

EOT Students' Level of Self-Efficacy (Conventional)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Wilcoxon	P- value	Decision	Interpretation
Before	7.12	1.35					
			-2.59	2122.5	0.0349	Reject Ho	Significant
After	7.61	1.26					

Note: p < 0.05 is significant

Table 4.20*ILA Students' Level of Self-Efficacy (Intervention)*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Wilcoxon	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Before	7.14	1.32		1608	< .001		
After	7.95	1.44	-4.25			Reject Ho	Significant

Note: $p < 0.05$ is significant

The results revealed that both ILA and EOT as teaching-learning approaches were effective in increasing students' self-efficacy levels. This means that there could be a variety of interventions available to improve student online learning. Apart from the conventional teaching models, significant changes in performance such as using gamified flipped learning in a virtual physics laboratory course resulted in a positive impact on students' innovation skills (Ahmed & Asiksoy, 2021); and using web-based virtual labs (VLs) to replace traditional physical labs (Son et al., 2016) were some that found effective among students. Further this implies no definite strategy, but teachers and school administrators can select the most appropriate intervention type for their students. This will assist in ensuring that all students can learn and develop a stronger sense of self-efficacy.

With the adoption of digital learning and the development of educational technologies (Tsai et al., 2017) especially in this new normal, inverted learning approach would be highly recommendable in improving students' self-efficacy. This is supported in Table 4.21, which details the results of the comparative analysis in students' level of self-efficacy in Bioenergetics of students between the two groups

under study through the two-sample t-test (pooled variance), using T distribution (df=216) and two sample MannWhitney U.

Table 4.21

Comparison of Students' Level of Self-Efficacy- EOT vs ILA

	Mean	SD	t	pvalue	U	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
EOT	7.61	1.26	-1.84	0.033	4870.5	0.0110	Reject Ho	Significant
ILA	7.95	1.44						

Note: p < 0.05 is significant

Students who have high self-efficacy and are affectively and cognitively engaged perform better in science classes (Uçar and Sungur, 2017). The results showed that the EOT students' self-efficacy level was lower than the ILA students' and such difference is big enough to be statistically significant (t= -1.8468; p=0.03307). The p-value generated was lesser than the significance level of 0.05, which means that there was enough statistical evidence to support that the mean difference in the self-efficacy level of students between groups is significant. In addition, the observed effect size d is small, 0.25. Apart from the t-test that compares the means, the Mann-Whitney U test was also run to compare randomly selected value from the EOT group to a randomly selected value from the ILA group. It also revealed that the EOT students' self-efficacy level is likewise lesser than the ILA students' (U=4870.5; Z= -2.2888; p= 0.01105). The reported standardized effect size, $Z/\sqrt{(n_1+n_2)}$, is 0.16, which is nonsignificant.

Therefore, students are enabled by ILA to attain self-efficacy in virtual learning environments as supported by Heaperman & Sudweeks (2001). Inverted learning approach encourages deeper learning than expository online teaching (Algarni, 2023; Arante & Castro, 2022). It gives students more time to learn, empowers them to be more independent and responsible, and fosters their creativity, as well as improving knowledge and skills for students of varying levels of achievement (Paul et al., 2023). This further implies providing students with flexibility for “anytime and anywhere” learning (Martin et al., 2010) by revolutionizing the learning platform such as development of learning management system (LMS) or adopting multiple learning modalities in the new normal set-up. ILA is reasonably considered purposeful maximization of technology or digital resources in education (Drozdikova-Zaripova, & Sabirova, 2020).

Relationship of Concept Understanding and Self-Efficacy of ILA Students

Since the data are not continuous, and may contain outliers, Spearman's rho correlation was used to determine the level of relationship between the conceptual understanding and self-efficacy levels in Bioenergetics. Tables 36 and 37 display the correlation among the self-efficacy domains to direct and deferred conceptual understanding of students exposed to Inverted Learning Approach.

Results of the spearman correlation indicated that there was a nonsignificant, weak positive relationship between their direct and deferred conceptual understanding and self-efficacy especially on handling tools in the LMS indicated by $r(110) = .262, p = .005$ and $r(110) = .221, p = .019$ respectively and interacting with instructors in an online class, as meant by the values $r(110) = .283, p = .002$ and

$r(110) = .287, p = .002$. In addition, their direct conceptual understanding and their self-efficacy to interact with classmates for academic purposes also are marked as positively weak but significantly correlated as indicated by $r(110) = .289, p = .002$.

Table 4.22

Correlation Between the Direct Concept Understanding (Posttest) and Self-Efficacy-ILA

Self-Efficacy Domains	Direct Concept Understanding		
	r	P	Relationship
Self-efficacy to complete an online subject	.159	.094	Weak positive
Self-efficacy to interact socially with classmates	.133	.161	Weak positive
Self-efficacy to handle tools in the LMS	.262	.005*	Weak positive
Self-efficacy to interact with instructors in an online class	.283	.002*	Weak positive
Self-efficacy to interact with classmates for academic purposes	.289	.002*	Weak positive

Note: $r < 0.1$: negligible correlation; $0.3 \leq r < 0.5$: moderate correlation;

$0.1 \leq r < 0.3$: weak correlation; $r \geq 0.5$: strong correlation

$P < 0.05$ is significant

Though it revealed in the study that the conceptual understanding is not highly related or associated with self-efficacy among students (Puzziferro, 2008), this finding is supported by the studies of Jose et al. (2021) and Wang et al. (2022), which found that self-efficacy scores did not predict engagement (Jose et al., 2021) and that learning gains did not differ significantly between study groups with different levels of prior knowledge and self-efficacy (Wang et al., 2022), while Honicke and Broadbent

(2016) resulted having moderately correlation between self-efficacy and academic performance.

Table 4.23

Correlation Between the Deferred Concept Understanding (Retention Test) and Self Efficacy – ILA

Self-Efficacy Domains	Deferred Concept Understanding		
	R	P	Relationship
Self-efficacy to complete an online subject	.127	.181	Weak positive
Self-efficacy to interact socially with classmates	.176	.063	Weak positive
Self-efficacy to handle tools in the LMS	.221	.019*	Weak positive
Self-efficacy to interact with instructors in an online class	.287	.002*	Weak positive
Self-efficacy to interact with classmates for academic purposes	.134	.159	Weak positive

Note: $r < 0.1$: negligible correlation; $0.3 \leq r < 0.5$: moderate correlation;

$0.1 \leq r < 0.3$: weak correlation; $r \geq 0.5$: strong correlation

$P < 0.05$ is significant

Despite these, Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) may still be able to be adopted or implemented at the primary and secondary levels of education (Fragkaki et al., 2020). Regardless of the challenges they faced during COVID-19, this learning approach promotes students' autonomy and collaboration (Martinelli & Zaina, 2021). This can also implicate that, aside from self-efficacy, academic performance may be influenced by a variety of internal and external factors.

Given the scarcity of research in this area, more investigation into how these variables interact over time is required to establish relationship and identify the complex interaction between self-efficacy, and direct and deferred conceptual understanding. Thus, to investigate further this phenomenon and explain additional information from the participants, this study further carried out a thorough qualitative exploration of the respondents' experiences with ILA and how it affected their learning experiences.

These findings might also suggest that learning is predicted by other factors, which may be affected by how the learning environment is designed, as teachers strive for meaningful conceptual understanding and retention of content (Witt et al., 2021), especially in the new normal set-up. It must be flexible, nonthreatening, and technology oriented. Even though students were initially challenged by the new learning environment, but they quickly adapted and found ILA to be satisfactory and effective.

As per observations, ILA has also been responsive to the new normal set-up to address learning gaps when teachers are still able to cover more topics or competencies and improve confidence during online classes (*"may mas confidence ako this time"* [I become more confident now], - Interviewee, Female, ILA group). With this in mind, educational institutions are deemed challenged to provide better learning opportunities, such as upskilling or retooling for teachers' technological pedagogy, and giving appropriate platforms that truly support student learning and engagement and develop their self-efficacy.

Feedback on the use of Inverted Learning Approach

Table 4.24 illustrates the respondents' evaluation on the use of the inverted learning approach in Bioenergetics. Items number 1-5 refer to their extent of concurrence on the pre-class phase of the intervention. Items number 6-15 are during the actual virtual classes while items number 16-20 detail the post-class phase.

Pre-class (before class) is a time allocated before class session. The students are not present in class and can achieve the educational objectives at their own pace. This phase provides students with opportunities to process and make sure they do not feel intimidated or overwhelmed as they learn new things. In the study, it is asynchronous, independent learning phase that helps students connect with the material ahead of time and prepare themselves for class so that when they will be more prepared and ready during the actual class sessions. For academically challenged students, this ensures that they are not falling behind other classmates, and an extra time for those who have difficulty focusing.

Table 4.24

Evaluation Tool on the use of Inverted Learning Approach in Bioenergetics

BEFORE CLASS Description	Mean \pm SD	
1. Watch deliberately the discussion videos	3.82 \pm 0.88	High Extent
2. Connect with the teachers and classmates	3.80 \pm 0.88	High Extent
3. Improve the relationship with teachers and classmates	3.92 \pm 0.80	High Extent
4. Handle well my time and self-pace one's learning	3.57 \pm 0.98	High Extent
5. Receive the expected course competencies ahead of schedule	3.84 \pm 0.80	High Extent
Overall Mean \pm SD	3.79 \pm 0.87	High Extent

DURING CLASS

6. Maximize in-class time for learning	3.80 ± 0.84	High Extent
7. Become more involved than in a traditional classroom approach	3.70 ± 0.94	High Extent
8. Participate in more collaborative activities	3.78 ± 0.86	High Extent
9. Take more learning opportunities	3.89 ± 0.87	High Extent
10. Receive assessment/ monitoring of performance	3.85± 0.85	High Extent
11. Supply with differentiated instruction and activities	3.95 ± 0.89	High Extent
12. Learn the concepts and skills expected	3.80 ± 0.83	High Extent
13. Express and respond freely to the activities	3.99± 0.83	High Extent
14. Ask for clarifications	4.22± 0.84	High Extent
15. Get honest feedback on work/progress	4.13 ± 0.87	High Extent
Overall Mean ± SD	3.91 ± 0.86	High Extent

AFTER CLASS

16. Rewatch the videos for remediation/ review	3.97 ± 0.95	High Extent
17. Participate in self-evaluation exercises	3.91± 0.91	High Extent
18. Consider the approach to be an effective approach in teaching Biology	3.94± 0.87	High Extent
19. Look forward to studying next/ more topics	3.94 ± 0.91	High Extent
20. Become more confident doing the post-class activities/ tasks.	3.77 ± 0.88	High Extent
Overall Mean ± SD	3.91 ± 0.90	High Extent

Note: **4.50-5.00** (*Very High Extent*); **3.50-4.49** (*High Extent*); **2.50-3.49** (*Moderate Extent*); **1.50-2.49** (*Less Extent*); **1.00-1.49** (*Least Extent*)

All items have been assessed “High Extent” and that means the entire phase of the intervention has been smoothly implemented. To highlight, students were able to receive the expected course competencies ahead of schedule (Mean= 3.84 ± 0.80) and improve their relationship with teachers and classmates (Mean= 3.92 ± 0.80), as Female, #3, Interviewee described, “*may mas confidence ako this time; not consistent*

ako mag study; usually nag cra-cramming” [I become more confident; usually I cram]; and thus students tend to engage and ask other class mates, “...*nagatanong lang po ako sa class mates kung ndi ko magets*” [I ask my class mates when I have questions], according to Female, #4, Interviewee.

Meanwhile the students are aware that time management and self-paced learning have been both challenging as this pre-class item obtained their lowest assessment level with a mean of 3.57 ± 0.98 . Inverted learning means that events that used to happen inside the classroom now happen outside of it, and vice versa (Lape et al., 2014). As a result, students have enough time to prepare for the class by watching the discussion videos ahead (Ahmed et al., 2022). This is clearly articulated by a female interviewee, “...*sa room, medyo distracted. Sa bahay, may time talaga ako na manuod sa discussion videos, mag take down notes, word by word...*” [In the classroom, bit distracted. At home, we have more time to watch and really take down notes].

In this manner, they will become more interactive, involved, or engaged in the actual class sessions. Inverted learning allows students to learn new material and apply it immediately during class time (Ishak et al., 2020), whereas expository teaching introduces concepts during class, and processing of information may occur after or at home as they complete their assignments or tasks. The opportunity to test oneself without any restrictions helps develop critical thinking skills. Students can learn more and ask for more during the class. Class meetings can then focus on the important and harder work of developing higher level thinking skills. In the study, this is the synchronous class online session that deepens students’ understanding of what they have learned at home through the discussion videos.

This also provides them the platform to tackle content from very different perspectives, as well as giving teachers the opportunity to prepare for in-class activities while they can work with other students and engaged in their own learning experiences. The fact that they had the taste or experience of both online and physical classes (before pandemic), their involvement may not be as better as in a traditional approach (Mean= 3.70 ± 0.94), since online classes limit some laboratory and hands-on experiences or activities. One participant from the FGD however expressed her optimism about the use of ILA, "*mahirap sya... baka masanay din ako na ganito sa Bio sa mga gagawin*" [It is challenging, but I believe I will be used to this approach in learning Biology]- *Female, #1, Focus Group*. Nevertheless, students freely expressed and responded to activities (Mean= 3.99± 0.83); can ask their teacher for clarifications (Mean= 4.22± 0.84); and were able to receive genuine feedback on their work/ progress (Mean= 4.13 ± 0.87).

After class learnings are not the same as before class. Inverted Learning Approach benefits students before class, during class, and even after class. Students can rewatch the videos for remediation/ review (Mean= 3.97 ± 0.95). These video-lectures do not need to be high-production-quality, but rather content-focused and concise (Mason et al., 2013). By asking students to independently learn first the concepts, they will be able to grasp firsthand the information and improve retention. Learning this way, students will always look forward to studying next/ more topics (Mean= 3.94 ± 0.91), as evidenced by this narration, "*nung OL class, naging mas productive po ako,, kung may assignments ginagawa ko po agad.*" [During the online meeting, I feel very productive; I do the assignments right away to avoid piling up]. – *Female, #3, Focus group*. Finally, they considered Inverted Learning Approach to be an effective approach in teaching Biology (Mean= 3.94± 0.87).

The Self-Determination Theory (SDT) of Ryan and Deci (2000) supports the findings of the study where students who were taught using ILA developed independence as they were able to feel good at understanding the lesson on their own. They had actively experienced competence and control of the information when viewing the videos; and connection, which created social support from teachers and classmates and sense of belongingness. The Self-Determination Theory explains why students who experienced ILA have the drive or source of interest to do more and attend classes, the sense of purpose in participating in the learning process, and the self-efficacy to do the tasks or activities because they are intrinsically motivated to learn. As a result, ILA students have become more innovative or creative, and performed better in the tests compared to EOT students.

Reflexive Qualitative Analysis of STEM Students' Experiences

Inductive thematic analysis was used in the qualitative phase of the study. Generated themes are grounded from the collected data (Clarke et al., 2015). By exploring the essence of experiences of using the Inverted Learning Approach articulated by the STEM students through a semi-structured online focus group discussion, qualitative survey, and live informal interviews, the phenomenological design unravels four (4) emerging themes that addressed the research question, "*Why would the inverted learning approach be adopted in teaching Biology based on the experiences of STEM Students?*"

Thematic analysis was used to code, interpret, and make sense of the qualitative data (Atwa et al., 2022). To generate themes from textual and audio-to-text data obtained through focus group discussions, interviews, and a qualitative survey,

manual/hand coding was used. In accordance with the analytic process of the reflexive thematic analysis, the researcher used the lens of instructional experience and pedagogical practice to temper subjectivity issues.

The following themes have emerged from the researcher’s engagement with the participants, and these are presented in a simulacrum in Figure 4.5. This figure presents the framework and interrelationship of themes and categories that emerged during the researcher’s qualitative data gathering processes.

Figure 4.5. Simulacrum of themes and categories on the use of ILA

The themes include a) *Developing into active and reflective learners*, which supports inquiry, reflection, and sharing of information; b) *Enabling students to engage and collaborate more freely*, which involves learning teams or groups and that encompasses innovation in terms of content and style; c) *Establishing a flexible, seamless, and nonpressuring space for learning*, which is flexible and technology-based that renders seamless information; and d) *Becoming disciplined and*

responsible for one's learning, which can be the result of students' self-direction and self-accountability of their own learning.

Developing into active and reflective learners

Through the inverted learning approach, students are involved in both the active and passive parts of the learning process. Students are pulled into more active inquirybased learning rather than being pushed through traditional textbooks, lecture notes and teacher-provided assignments in a one-sided format. This allowed them to come to class prepared as mentioned by one of the responses:

"The inverted learning approached helped me to prepare for the incoming written works. My classmates' reactions and participation also got better, and we were able to ask each other about the topic which helps a lot, Task are also easier to understand." [The inverted learning approach has made me more prepared in class. My classmates and I got better understanding of the topic and become more participative.] - *Female, #1, Survey Group*

Inverted Learning Approach helped students become more comfortable with the material being taught by allowing them to spend time on tasks related to the main concept before going through practice exercises at a slower pace. They too have time to discuss and share knowledge with their classmates as form of interaction. The experience of one of the participants in the focus group was able to narrate, "*...easier to learn by listening... I tend to learn when discuss with classmates.*" [I tend to learn by listening and when discussing with classmates.]- *Male, A1, Focus Group*; "*nagatanong lang po ako sa class mates kung ndi ko magets.*" [I ask my class mates when I have questions.] - *Male, #2, Interview*

Inverted learning increased individual confidence and interest, which resulted in good learning performance (Namaziandost & Çakmak, 2020). This approach gave

them an opportunity to discover and understand more important ideas, from a variety of perspectives. It helped them become reflective on learning the materials and develop into active learners (*“When I do get or understand the lesson, it’s kinda enjoyable.”* [When I got the concept, I enjoy it.] - *Male, #1, Interview*). This approach further involves students focusing early on areas in which they know less or think they do (*“It helps me to focus and improve my learning skills especially the ability to understand things more thoroughly and concentrate more on the topics.”* [My focus/ concentration and ability to learn and understand things are improved.]- *Female, #2, Survey Group*).

Enabling students to engage and collaborate more freely

Through social presence (Doo, & Bonk, 2020) and collaborative learning assistance, Inverted Learning approach has improved learner engagement, particularly in the out-of-class learning phase (Zheng et al., 2020) or asynchronous class meetings. There are opportunities for students to engage in meaningful and deep learning activities which lie at the heart of an inverted learning approach. It encompasses both time for one to learn self-pace in watching the discussion videos and to interact with others during activities. This new style of learning is not spoon feeding the students, instead the teacher works with students in small groups for activities that are more authentic and engaging than traditional lecture-based instruction. Evident from their narratives:

“...blended kasi may time na makausap mo personal yung iba; and online para may time ka po sa sarili mo, balance lang po.” [I want blended to have time to be with other students; and to have time for oneself as well (online).]
- *Female, #3, Interview*

“Parang mas magustuhan ko yung teacher to make discussion videos; nag e-effort yung teacher para matulungan yung students na ma-learn yung subject.” [I enjoy the discussion videos and see the effort of teachers making them for students to learn from their subject.] - Male, #4, Survey Group

Thus, students have more freedom in their ability to explore concepts, become more ready (*“...kapag online recitation, nag reready ako ng script.”* [Online recitation allows me to make script before answering.]- *Female, #3, Interview*), make connections between different disciplines, and work better in groups (*“My classmates are together helping each other so that the learning experience is good at us.”* [Learning experience is good because my classmates and I are helping one another.]- *Male, #3, Survey Group*). ILA provides students with opportunities where they can work together to solve problems and gain understanding. It creates active learning atmosphere in which students could increase their sense of self-efficacy (Li & Yang, 2021; Latorre-Coscolluela et al., 2021) and improve knowledge retention (Bouwmeester et al., 2019). Teamwork creates opportunities for learning and mastery that would not otherwise be possible. In working collaboratively, students become critical thinkers during and after viewing the learning resources.

Establishing a flexible, seamless, and nonpressuring space for learning

To ensure a continuous success in delivering learning content (Yuan, 2021) in this new normal, while engaging students in online learning to improve their performance and outcomes (Khlaif et al., 2021) and experiences (Nguyen et al., 2021), Inverted Learning Approach uses technology as a learning environment. The learning environment is flexible and seamless that provides students with high quality, interactive materials and adaptive support in the classroom and beyond. It further

allows students to customize their learning experience, which makes it adaptive and flexible (*"It is more free for students to study/ watch it anytime they want to. It is more accessible and more convenient way for students to have an active learning in their own space."* [It gives more freedom to students to study any time; access and convenience to learn in their own space.] - *Female, #10, Survey Group*). They access content from anywhere and at any point in time as well as engage in 'flipped' classes where teachers prepare learning activities and then the whole class collaborates on them.

On the positive side, learning materials are available and accessible on their mobile, tablet devices, and/or computer. The ease and flexibility of asynchronous learning allows students to learn at their own pace and when they are ready (*"Information is easily accessible; Encourages us to develop an adaptive learning style; Gives us a bit of breathing space unlike before."* [Information is easily accessible; the learning approach encourages adaptive learning style and gives breathing space unlike the learning modality before (pandemic S.Y.)] - *Male, #5, Survey Group*). Through automated technology, such as mobile apps or online quizzes and assessments, students can demonstrate mastery of skills before moving on to new topics.

This approach includes the implementation of new technologies, pedagogies, and learning models (Chattaraj & Vijayaraghavan, 2021) that include synchronous and asynchronous instructions (Shamir-Inbal & Blau, 2021), which means that learning happens both online and offline. This caters different learning style of students. Because learners aren't confined to a single venue for instruction, opportunities for synchronous interaction are increased. This approach allows

students to work at their own pace with clear guidance from instructors or peers who can quickly respond when needed. As recounted:

"It made me more alert than usual. My learning style had been changed drastically. It was a familiar experience..."

[This familiar experience made me become more alert as my learning style changed.] - Female, #4, Survey Group

Becoming disciplined and responsible for one's learning

The approach relies on the learner's ability to learn at their own pace within a self-paced learning environment. It encourages self-paced, self-study, and now even accountability. It separates independent work from assessments, making it easier than ever for them to learn how to learn (*"I think it's much better na may discussion videos para ma-ready na kami for upcoming lessons."* [The discussion videos make us more ready for the upcoming lessons.]- Male, #6, Survey Group). Students work asynchronously with instructors via email, text messages or video conferencing.

Students are in control and responsible of their own learning. They can decide what to do for the day, when and how often, based on their schedule and preferences. The inverted learning approach makes it easy for students to keep up with the class by ensuring they self-paced, self-study and take ownership of their education. They can try, cope with missed class sessions, make mistakes and try again.

"You can rewatch the video anytime, you have time to take notes, and you have the freedom." [It allows access to the video anytime; one has freedom and can take down notes.]- Female, #13, Survey Group

"I can pause it to give myself more time to understand." [You can self-pace watching the video.]- Male, #7, Survey Group

“I develop independent learning skills, whenever I’m absent during online classes I am not behind and I can catch up easily since I can rewind it when I don’t understand. But if you have poor internet connection it can be very frustrating 😞.” [I develop independent learning skills; I can cope with the missed topics whenever I am absent. I can catch up easily through the discussion videos which I can rewatch; however, it is challenging with no internet.]- *Female, #17, Survey Group.*

Instructional Improvement Plan

The data obtained from the results of the pretest, posttest, and retention test and self-efficacy tools, the evaluation of ILA, and the qualitative information and relevant slices of experiences from FGDs and interviews were deliberately considered for the researcher to come up with an instructional improvement plan. The goal of this plan is to make a guide to better implement or conduct the intervention in the long run. It presents a few challenges or issues that emerged from data transcripts derived directly from the responses and experiences of the respondents and from the observations and reflection of the researcher.

Specifically, it includes the challenges or issues identified from the evidence or data transcripts, the activities or proposed activities or programs to address them, the targets and indicators of success, and the linkages or focal persons/ group of individuals who may be connected. The areas for improvement are shown in the instructional improvement plan in Table 4.25.

Table 4.25

Instructional Improvement Plan

A- TEACHER'S PREPARATION/ PERFORMANCE					
Challenges/ Issues	Evidence from Data Transcripts	How to address	Objective/s	Indicator/s of Success	Linkage/s
Codeswitching may be considered in explaining the concepts in the discussion video. Subtitles may be added and better audio effect may be considered.	<p><i>"I hope the teacher would use Tagalog language even for just phrases that are easier to understand when said in Tagalog."</i></p> <p><i>"I suggest is that maybe add subtitles because sometimes the microphone is bad."</i></p>	<p>The use of standard Filipino subtitles or closed captions may be explored as new versions of video will be developed.</p> <p>A better quality of recording platform may be considered in the next versions of videos.</p>	<p>To make a script that uses Filipino phrases to emphasize concepts.</p> <p>To acquire a quality audio device to resolve microphone issues and enable or use of accurate captions</p>	A discussion video using standard English as medium of instruction, with Filipino closed captions or subtitles.	<p>Instructional Media Center</p> <p>ICT Office</p>
The use of discussion videos in the inverted learning is recommended for use in other learning areas.	<p><i>Sana po lahat ng subject sa G12 ganyan yung approach, kase po hindi lahat fast learning isang turo ng teacher gets na agad....."</i></p> <p><i>"...in Physics and Research..."</i></p>	Share the results of this paper to other departments thru a local or school-based presentations with thrust on the use of ILA as a good deal of new normal teachinglearning approach.	To present the results of the study that makes use of technology into teaching and learning experience	The development and use of video recorded discussion or lecture by teachers in other learning areas.	<p>Principal</p> <p>Subject Area Coordinators</p>

Challenges/ Issues	Evidence from Data Transcripts	How to address	Objective/s	Indicator/s of Success	Linkage/s
To include a good background music/ better sound quality in the discussion videos	<i>"it is good to use music for us to enjoy the topic especially when the teacher uses popular songs.."</i>	Integrate background music whenever necessary to make the videos more appealing.	To identify appropriate sound/ music background and video editing application	A discussion video with much better music background	Instructional Media Center ICT Office
B- TEACHER'S EXPERIENCE/ REFLECTIONS					
Congested learning competencies	<i>Teacher's observation</i>	Select only the topics that need to use inverted learning approach	To identify complex concepts or processes that require time for students to understand for inverted learning approach	Selected difficult topics with discussion videos	Subject Area Coordinator Teacher-incharge
Teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge	Teacher's reflection	Learn and relearn to use technology in teaching, such as online applications Part of discussion in Professional Learning Communities (PLCs)	To become skilled or literate at media information and production To conduct a webinar on the use of inverted learning approach	Continuously using online applications even in the implementation of full face-toface classes	ICT Office TLE Teachers Subject Teachers

Challenges/ Issues	Evidence from Data Transcripts	How to address	Objective/s	Indicator/s of Success	Linkage/s
C- STUDENT'S FEEDBACK/ PERFORMANCE/BEHAVIOR					
Conduct of individual consultations among students	<i>"Individual Consultation to the students"</i>	Conduct remediation / consultation program for students after classes	To implement a remediation / consultation program for students as recovery period (post-class)	Remediation/ Consultation/ Kamustahan period at 3:305:00 PM (be it online or face-to-face)	Homeroom Advisers Guidance Staff Subject Teacher
It requires the use of and dependence to gadgets and internet.	<i>"More use of gadgets." "it is device dependent, and lost of creation."</i>	Give more offline activities instead of internet-based activities	To employ diverse ways of introducing the topic/ content	Use of diverse ways of introducing the topics/content to align it with the objective	Subject Area Coordinator Teacher-incharge
Discussion Videos cannot be downloaded/ watched/ accessed without internet connection	<i>"ndi sya mdownload kung wala ka internet." "when you have no proper connection, you cannot watch it."</i>	Make the discussion videos available for download and offline viewing	To enable download option and saving of discussion videos in the library access.	Downloadable and more accessible discussion video materials	Instructional Media Center ICT Office
Learning may be tiring.	<i>"medyo tiring po ang learning"</i>	Conduct reading breaks	To observe mental health breaks even classes are held face-toface already	Psychological first aid for both teachers and students	Principal Guidance Staff Homeroom Adviser
Students' varying learning preferences/ styles/ habits	Teachers' observation	Develop flexible class schedule or program in preparation for higher education	To adopt blended learning modality / offer hybrid class sessions	Multimodal learning options	Director Principal Academic Council

Challenges/ Issues	Evidence from Data Transcripts	How to address	Objective/s	Indicator/s of Success	Linkage/s
D- LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN BOTH SYNCHRONOUS AND ASYNCHRONOUS PHASES					
It is more challenging when tasks from all learning areas will be deployed and given to students; some cannot cope with.	<i>“sabay sabay ang task; usap usap muna kada week ito muna ibigay na specific task; mahirap mag sabay sabay lahat magbibigay.”</i>	Pursue/ explore an interdisciplinary approach in making tasks so that students will just perform one to three tasks for all learning areas.	To intensify the PLCs on matters regarding giving of tasks to ease students' load	Collaborated tasks between and among learning areas per grade level	Principal Subject Area Coordinators Teachers-incharge
Use of MS Teams as Learning Management System	Teacher's reflections	Continued subscription to MS Teams even classes are back faceto-face	To subscribe MS Teams as the school's official platform and communication tool	Continued use of MS Teams	Director ICT Office Academic Council
E- ASSESSMENT OF LEARNING					
More authentic assessment (like open-ended questions) right after watching	Teacher's observation	Implement alternative authentic assessment of student's learning in the new normal set-up apart from the traditional ones.	To administer new normal assessment of learning	The use of diverse assessment tools such as wise-mapping; menti-meter; padlet, kahoot, etc.	Principal Subject Area Coordinators Subject Teachers
Reward system for well-performing department based achievement tests.	Researcher's reflection	Incentivize wellperforming learning areas annually.	To improve the academic performance of students per learning area	Increased academic performance	Principal Subject Area Coordinators

Table 39 covers five areas, which include **A-** Teacher's Preparation/Performance; **B-** Teacher's Experience/Reflections; **C-** Student's Feedback/Performance/Behavior; **D-** Learning Activities in both Synchronous and Asynchronous phases; and **E-** Assessment of learning.

Students appreciate the teacher-made discussion videos, however, it is crucial for instructors to consider the diversity of their learners' needs and adapt accordingly by providing a number of options for accessing the types content materials, such as offering both captioned and non-captioned videos (*"I suggest is that maybe add subtitles because sometimes the microphone is bad."*), or allowing students to choose whether or not they prefer background music (*"it is good to use music for us to enjoy the topic especially when the teacher uses popular songs.."*). Besides that, teachers should also ensure that the use of background music does not hamper students' concentration or detract them from the lesson content.

Teachers can use pre-recorded discussion videos to engage with their students in a controlled environment. This enables them to cut, merge, remove, or splice video segments that they do not want their students to see, resulting in a more effective presentation. Also, pre-recording discussions can save both the teacher and the students time and resources. The teacher can record the video whenever it is convenient for them and make it available to their students at any time, allowing students to watch the video on their own time, especially those who have other more activities or are unable to attend a live discussion. Plus, these videos can be a valuable resource for students to use when studying for exams or working on assignments. Students can review, pause, fast forward or replay them to better understand and retain the material (*"Sana po lahat ng subject sa G12 ganyan yung approach, kase po hindi lahat fast learning isang turo ng teacher gets na agad."*).

These are ways in doing flexible and inclusive approach to cater for the diverse learning styles of students in view of teacher's preparation.

In addressing congested or overcrowded competencies, teachers provide the learning resources that cover the key concepts and topics that are covered in class. Students are then expected to go through these materials through ILA at any time and from any location, so that they can come to class prepared to take part in deeper discussions and activities related to the content. The ILA can be especially effective and useful when classes are cancelled due to bad weather or other incidents. It assists students to continue learning even when there are unexpected disruptions, such as weather-related cancellations of classes. Students who have access to materials online may keep up with the content. By giving students the opportunity to engage with content before class, they can come to class with a basic understanding of the material, which can help them retain and apply the information better. Thus, ILA has the potential to improve student retention and conceptual understanding. Similarly, when students are engaged in the learning process, they are more likely to retain the information from the material.

Regarding student performance, intentional remediation programs or periods can be an effective way to support students who are having difficulty adjusting to the online learning environment ("*...individual consultation to the students...*"). These programs can be part of an extensive recovery strategy that should put in place after the full implementation of online learning. Remediation programs can help to address gaps in knowledge and understanding that may have occurred because of the transition to online learning by providing students with specific help and focus. This can be particularly important for students who have struggled with the design of the online setup or who have encountered other issues or academic challenges ("*medyo*").

tiring po ang learning"). These programs can aid in addressing the learning gap for struggling students and ensuring that everyone has an equal chance to succeed.

Moving toward more authentic assessment is one of the most important changes we need to make in the way we assess learning. It should assess not only what students know, but also how they apply that knowledge in real-world situations. Students are frequently given multiple-choice tests or short answer questions that require them to recall information in the conventional testing. While this method is essential for assessing basic knowledge, it does not always reflect the skills that students require to be successful in the transfer of understanding. Another suggestion is the reward system. This reward system does not always have to be cash-based; it can also be moral. Students and teachers can be driven to engage in more positive and relevant pedagogy by using a reward system. Students specifically can be more self-directed and proactive in their learning. The use of a reward system can also provide for the empowerment of teachers. Teachers are more likely to feel engaged and motivated when their efforts are recognized. This, in turn, can lead to a more favorable atmosphere for learning and improved educational results.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary, conclusions and the recommendations based on the results sought throughout the study. It specifically highlights the results, shows the decisions over hypotheses set, and recommendations to make better the study, and suggestions for future related or similar studies.

Summary of the Findings

An explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was employed in this study. A quasi-experimental, controlled group design was primarily conducted, followed by a reflexive thematic qualitative analysis. It sought to ascertain whether an inverted learning approach (ILA) influences direct and deferred conceptual understanding, as well as self-efficacy, among STEM students enrolled in a biology course in Senior High School. A pilot/ trial study was carried out during the second semester of the School Year (S.Y.) 2021-2022, where the instructional materials for the approach were validated by local school experts and the tools used were tested and revalidated. These were observed prior to the study being formally conducted at Notre Dame of Cotabato, the First Marist School in the Philippines.

Aside from descriptive and inferential statistical information, it also analyzed nonnumerical data and feedback from respondents to further explain their experiences with the Inverted Learning Approach. The study covered the second quarter topics of the First Semester for the S.Y. 2022-2023 as prescribed by the

Department of Education's K to 12 curriculum guides, which were revised in August 2016. The ATP-ADP Cycle, Photosynthesis, and Cellular Respiration are among the topics covered. The school implemented a hybrid learning model, with two (2) online periods, one (1) limited face-toface session, and one (1) modular session per subject per week. The Microsoft Teams (MS Teams) was used as the official Learning Management System (LMS) for distributing all learning/instructional materials to the respondents of the study, especially the teacher made pre-recorded discussion videos (only for the intervention group).

For ethical considerations, the students and their parents/guardians were asked to read and understand the assent form and consent forms before signing them prior to participating in the research. The respondents were from the six (6) Grade 12 STEM classes for the School Year 2022-2023. To maintain parity of conditions, each class consists of 45-51 students were taught by the same science teacher. The study initially included 287 STEM students, but only 232 completed the informed and consent forms required by the ethics board to participate in the study. The classes were randomly assigned to intervention or control groups based on their Pre-test scores. Only 225 out of 232 were able to take the Pretest, with an approximately equal ratio of male and female students.

The following are the summary of the key findings of the study:

1. Assumption tests for equal variances using the Levene's test, normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, and homogeneity using both two sample t-test (pooled variance) and two sample Mann-Whitney U Test were performed prior to analyzing the results. It was determined that the conventional and intervention groups are significantly comparable and do

not significantly vary in terms of their pretest results as basis for random assignment of groups.

2. Comparing the pretest and posttest results of the EOT group, one hundred six (106) students were able to take the posttest, with eighty-two (82) or 77% of students were able to get average to excellent scores in the posttest, thus an observed increment of scores. For the ILA group, one hundred twelve (112) students were able to take the posttest, with ninety-three (93) or 83% of the students got average to excellent scores in the posttest.
3. In comparing the posttest results of the EOT and ILA groups, the normalized gain, also known as the g-factor, has been determined. Data revealed that students who were taught using the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) have higher normalized gains than those taught using the Expository Online Teaching (EOT). The average normalized gain is 0.33 (N=106) for the conventional approach and 0.41 for the inverted learning approach (N=112). Both figures fall under 0.30-0.69 medium gain range (Hake, 1998). Thus, the intervention group has higher direct conceptual understanding level compared to the conventional group.
4. In view of their retention test results, students who were taught using the ILA have higher normalized gains than those taught using the EOT. It is evidenced by the average normalized gain of 0.10 (N=106) for the conventional approach, which indicates a lower mean gain while 0.39 for the inverted learning approach (N=112), which indicates a medium gain. This indicated that the intervention group has higher deferred conceptual understanding level compared to the conventional group.

5. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used to assign the domains into three constructs, *Competence, Interaction, and Independence*. To elaborate the results on these domains in the context of the study, both conventional and intervention groups were compared in terms of their self-efficacy. Though both groups achieved a high level of learning independence, competence and interaction, students taught using the ILA improved their independence (Mean= 7.89 ± 1.78), compared to those under EOT (Mean= 7.47 ± 1.59). Moreover, the intervention group also (Mean= 7.38 ± 2.35) has comparably higher competence rating than the conventional group (Mean= 7.04 ± 2.01). In view of their level of interaction, the latter group (Means= 8.01 ± 1.68 ; 7.98 ± 1.91 ; 8.17 ± 1.74) showed higher levels of interaction in three domains compared to the former (Means= 7.84 ± 1.75 ; 7.76 ± 2.12 ; 8.00 ± 2.05). Overall, it is shown that those students exposed to ILA have comparably higher self-efficacy levels than the EOT group, albeit both groups increased their self-efficacy levels after the quarter.
6. The use of Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) in Biology has been assessed by students to be highly favorable (“High Extent”) based on the results of evaluation before class (Mean= 3.79 ± 0.87) During class (Mean= 3.91 ± 0.86); and After class (Mean= 3.91 ± 0.90) sessions. Thus, it means the entire phase of the intervention has been effective in application.
7. There were four (4) themes that were generated from the Focus Group Discussions and Interviews among the participants, to further explore their experiences when taught using the Inverted Learning Approach. The themes include a) *Developing into active and reflective learners*, which

supports inquiry, reflection, and sharing of information; b) *Enabling students to engage and collaborate more freely*, which involves learning teams or groups and that encompasses innovation in terms of content and style; c) *Establishing for a flexible, seamless, and nonpressuring space for learning*, which is open and technologybased that renders almost limitless opportunities to grow; and d) *Becoming disciplined and responsible for one's own learning*, which can be the result of students' self-direction and self-accountability of their own learning.

Conclusion

It was found out that the conceptual understanding of students in Biology between those who are taught with EOT and ILA is comparable. Posttest scores of students in both groups show a significant increment; however, students exposed to ILA (Mean= 28.54 ± 8.28 ; and Mean= 28.18 ± 7.52) have significantly higher mean scores in Posttest test and Retention test than those taught using the EOT (Mean= 25.82 ± 6.91 ; and Mean= 17.49 ± 6.60). In other words, the intervention group has higher level of direct and deferred conceptual understanding compared to those in the conventional group. Moreover, post hoc analysis revealed that there were significant differences between the pretest, posttest, and retention test scores of EOT group. There was observed significant increment between pretest and posttest and between pretest and retention test; however, there was a significant decrement of gain mean scores between posttest ($g = 0.33$) and retention test ($g = 0.10$). On the other hand, for ILA group, there were also significant increase of gain mean scores between pretest and posttest; and between pretest and retention test; but there was

no significant difference between the posttest ($g = 0.41$) and retention test scores ($g = 0.39$). Thus, it can be concluded that ILA can affect the deferred conceptual understanding of students; thus improving retention.

ILA can really promote deeper learning and engagement among students compared to EOT. By having students engaged with the learning resources before joining the class, they have more time to process the information, ask queries, and create their views and concepts. This can lead to more substantive class discussions and processes, as students are better equipped to participate and share. While it is true that EOT can also improve student performance, ILA offers several advantages that can make it a more effective instructional approach for teachers to consider, such as it 1) makes students become more self-directed thinkers and doers; 2) fosters deeper understanding of concept by students as they interact with the content ahead of time, which can lead to better retention of knowledge and learned inquisitiveness; 3) leverages students' differential needs and interests; 4) gives chance to students to succeed through flexible learning space and time; and, finally, 5) cultivates important skills for their future academic and professional endeavors.

In view of the self-efficacy levels, students exposed to ILA have comparably higher self-efficacy levels than the EOT group, albeit both groups increased their self-efficacy levels after the quarter. The use of Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) in Biology has been assessed by students to be highly favorable or satisfactory ("High Extent") based on the results of evaluation before class (Mean= 3.79 ± 0.87); during class (Mean= 3.91 ± 0.86); and after class (Mean= 3.91 ± 0.90) sessions.

Even there were significant increment of the levels of direct and deferred conceptual understanding and self-efficacy among students receiving the ILA compared with EOT group, it was revealed that their conceptual understanding and

self-efficacy have weak/low significant positive relationship. Thus, reflexive thematic analysis was done to explore and further understand the experiences of STEM students who were taught using the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA). Based on the themes that emerged from the gathering and processing of qualitative information, it was substantiated that the Inverted Learning Approach has become effective in learning Biology among students because it develops learners into becoming active and reflective; enables them to engage and collaborate more freely with other students, establishes a flexible, seamless, and nonpressuring space for learning, and makes learners become disciplined and responsible for their own learning.

For teachers, ILA can present opportunities to personalize learning for their students by allowing them to design activities to meet the individual needs and interests of their students. It likewise frees up class time for more participatory and engaging activities, which can help to keep students excited and inspired in the lesson. For students, this approach provides a more flexible and independent learning experience because they can access their lessons on their own schedule and at their own pace. This can be especially beneficial for students who may find it hard to keep up with the pace of a conventional design or who may have other commitments or extracurricular activities outside of school. Ultimately, ILA gives students ownership of their learning and helps them cultivate important skills such as creative thinking, cooperation, and communication.

Overall Implications

The use of the ILA suggests a timely and applicable approach to the new normal teaching-learning process. In this approach, the roles of teachers and students are reversed, causing students to become more actively involved and be at

the core of the learning process. Having a sufficient amount of time to self-study instructional videos or online materials outside of class, students may cultivate their inquisitiveness, confidence, and higher order thinking skills.

ILA contributes to the development of evidence-based educational practice. It enables teachers to deliver content more effectively by focusing on appropriate, engaging, contextualized, and real-life applications of concepts in the classroom. It also helps to address the congested learning competencies in the existing curriculum guide.

The approach is based on Gen Z learners' preferred learning environment, which is virtual or cyberspace. ILA considers one domain or dimension that allows these students to be more motivated and comfortable while learning because they are already accustomed to this type of environment and may have been innate with this technological advantage. ILA also enables personalized and flexible learning experiences. Students can self-pace, rewind or review content as needed, and the approach accommodates several types of learning styles and preferences, promoting self-direction and selfaccountability.

ILA raises student performance to the level of the content and performance standards set by the Department of Education (DepEd). ILA can bring students to that level and even beyond. ILA likewise helps to democratize the learning process. In an era of ICT advancements that promotes online learning as the future of education, learners must become independent and active learners while also being able to collaborate with others. It makes use of technology tools and resources to foster active learning experiences. This helps students become more aware and independent thinkers and problem solvers.

Finally, Inverted Learning Approach also introduces the work of Ryan and Deci (2000), which is the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) as an established theoretical framework that further supports the implementation of the approach. It highlights the intrinsic factors of students to learn, resulting in authentic and better learning.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are deemed imperative:

1. The top-level administration of the school should think about offering different learning modalities such as full online classes, full face-to-face classes, and blended learning to accommodate diverse kinds of learners;
2. The school's top and middle level administration should consider the study's instructional improvement plan in their strategic planning for the next school year;
3. The middle level administrators of the school should employ the Inverted Learning Approach (ILA) to prepare students for hybrid learning modalities offered by their prospect higher educational institutions;
4. The academic council of the school led by the principal should encourage the use of ILA in different subjects/ learning areas to a) maximize instructional time, b) increase student interaction, c) promote independent learning, d) address learning gaps (part of the recovery program), and e) solve congestion in the curriculum guide competencies;
5. Teachers should innovate their pedagogy and consider ILA in challenging/difficult topics that require more time for students to learn/understand, particularly conceptual and computational processes;

6. Tenured and future educators could begin developing and producing quality discussion videos for instruction;
7. Teachers should conduct of Learning Remediation Program for academicallychallenged students and those who have difficulty in coping with the new normal design; and,
8. Teachers should use higher order thinking skills (HOTS) to quarterly assessment that is requiring explanation and creativity among students in their responses and outcomes.

Recommendations for further studies

The following topics are highly suggested to be undertaken:

1. ILA should be applied to social media platforms or applications that are most popular among Gen Z (21st century) learners and are easily accessible for them, such as Instagram, Twitter, FB Reels, Telegram, and Whatsapp. This particular use of various platforms for the implementation of ILA may affect the motivation of students to advance study;
2. The result of this study can provide more information on the appropriateness of ILA as a teaching strategy, especially in the new normal and post-pandemic time.
3. The use of Filipino (or mother tongue) subtitles in the video recorded lecture of the teacher and how the use of these affect students' performance, motivation to study, engagement, etc.
4. The use of collaborative learning tasks - focusing on the challenges in developing them and their impacts on students' performance.

5. Use of ILA in another learning areas, grade level in the JHS, or SHS strands such as HUMSS and ABM.
6. Exploring more on Gen Z motivation, engagement, self-regulation, self-esteem, motivation, or self-handicapping in the new normal learning set-up;
7. Integrating more relatable teaching experience such as using short stories, changing lyrics of a song, other web-based applications, or brain-based strategies in using ILA;
8. Doing qualitative research, like a grounded theory approach to better understand student experiences when classes adopt the inverted learning; and,
9. Doing meta-synthesis and/or meta-analysis on studies that use ILA and Self-Efficacy;

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C. Thesis/ Dissertation

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL FROM RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

Cotabato Regional and Medical Center

VERSION NO: 2
EFFECTIVE DATE:
06/01/2021

Form 2.7

CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL

This is to certify that the following protocol and related documents have been granted approval by the Cotabato Regional and Medical Center Research Ethics Committee for implementation.

REC Protocol No.	2022:008	Sponsor Protocol No.	N/A
Principal Investigator/s	Rolly James F. Cheng	Sponsor	N/A
Title	STEM Students' Direct and Postponed Conceptual Understanding and Self-Efficacy using the Inverted Learning Approach in Biology		
Protocol Version No.	1	Version Date:	July 28, 2022
ICF Version No.	1	Version Date:	July 28, 2022
Members of the research team	1		
Study Sites	Notre Dame of Cotabato (NDC)		
Approved Sample Size (if applicable)	N/A		
Type of Review	<input type="radio"/> Expedited <input checked="" type="radio"/> Full Board	Duration of Approval From (Date) To July 28, 2022 to July 28, 2023	
Meeting date:	Frequency of continuing review:		
July 28, 2022	N/A		
REC Chair Person	Name	Signature	Date
Chair	Scheherazade I. Tan, MD, FPSO-HNS, FPCS		July 29, 2022

Investigator Responsibilities after Approval:

- Submit document amendments for REC approval before implementing them
- Submit SAE and SUSAR reports to the REC within 7 days
- Submit progress report every 6 months
- Submit final report after completion of protocol procedures at the study site
- Report protocol deviation/violation
- Comply with all relevant international and national guidelines and regulations
- Abide by the principles of good clinical practice and ethical research

Received by:			
Name:	ROLLY JAMES FULE CHENG		
Signature:		Date:	29 July 2022

APPENDIX B FORMAL

COMMUNICATION LETTERS TO THE SCHOOL

18 November 2021

ANGELA T. UNDAR, EdD

School Principal

Dear Madam:

Warm greetings!

I respectfully express my intention to field a one-phase pilot trial of my data collection instruments among SHS Grade 12 STEM students. This aims to assess the viability of the tools for the actual conduct of my study next school year, which is concerned with instructional intervention and learning enhancement among Generation Z learners.

The target participants in this study will face no specific physical, physiological, or reducing vulnerability and their participation is entirely voluntary. The results of this pilot run may be used as baseline information and will be published in aggregate; however, their responses are completely confidential, and will not be associated with any of the results or used in any other purpose.

The processes and directions will be channeled and communicated by me through their respective advisers and class presidents, and this is what I humbly request your approval for. If you have any questions or concerns, please contact me at rfcheng@up.edu.ph or +63906 083 1690.

Thank you so much for your support on this endeavor. More power.

Sincerely in Jesus, Mary, and Joseph,

ROLLY JAMES F. CHENG

Researcher

Approved by:
ANGELA T. UNDAR, EdD

School Principal

13 September 2022

ANGELA T. UNDAR, EdD
Principal, Notre Dame of Cotabato

Dear Dr. Undar,

Greetings of peace!

My name is Rolly James F. Cheng, and I am a doctoral student in the Faculty of Education at the University of the Philippines-Open University. At present, I am working on my dissertation, which zeroes in on the use of Inverted Learning Approach and how it affects the learners' direct and delayed conceptual understanding, as well as their self-efficacy in learning Biology.

The study aims to measure the direct and postponed conceptual understanding of students and determine their level of self-efficacy when exposed to the intervention. Thus, this letter seeks for your approval to allow me to conduct the study among Grade 12 STEM students enrolled in the First Semester of the S.Y. 2022-23. These students will be asked to answer tests, complete forms, and participate in focus group discussions (FGDs) about their experiences on the Inverted Learning Approach. They will be asked to share their thoughts after the intervention and how to improve the learning experience when it will be used more extensively.

The study has already been subjected to a full board research ethics review to safeguard potential research participants and already secured a clearance certificate (see attached), which means that the research establishes high ethical standards as to where and how it will be conducted. The study will be from October 2022 to January 2023.

If you have any concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me thru my email, rfcheng@up.edu.ph or by phone at 09060831690. Thank you for your approval and support on this endeavor.

Respectfully in Notre Dame,

ROLLY JAMES CHENG

Endorsed by:

RICARDO T. BAGARINAO, PhD
Dissertation Adviser

okay!

9/14/2022

APPENDIX C

INFORMED CONSENT FORM FOR SURVEYS, INTERVIEWS, AND FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS (FOR PARENTS / GUARDIANS)

Study: STEM STUDENTS' DIRECT AND DEFERRED CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING AND SELF- EFFICACY USING THE INVERTED LEARNING APPROACH IN BIOLOGY: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY

Researcher: Rolly James Fule Cheng

Study Site: Notre Dame of Cotabato

PART I: INFORMATION SHEET

INTRODUCTION

My name is Rolly James F. Cheng, and I am a doctoral student in the Faculty of Education at the University of the Philippines-Open University. I am working on my dissertation under the supervision of Dr. Ricardo T. Bagarinao. This is an invitation to participate in my ongoing research. If you require clarification, please do not hesitate to ask questions at any time thru this mobile number, *0906 083 1690*, or thru my email, rfcheng@up.edu.ph

WHAT IS THE OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH?

The study focuses on the use of inverted or flipped learning and its effect on direct and deferred conceptual understanding in Biology. Similarly, it will determine how well this approach affects how students feel about themselves while learning and doing tasks in the course. This data will be used to develop an instructional improvement plan.

WHAT IS THE RESEARCH INTERVENTION?

Inverted Learning Approach is an instructional intervention, in which students will receive pre-recorded teacher-made discussion videos of the content outside of class prior to the scheduled online class meeting. Thus, they will face no specific physical or physiological risk.

HOW ARE THE PARTICIPANTS CHOSEN?

They have been chosen because they are STEM students, and the study is looking into the effectiveness of a teaching approach in a course (Biology) that is only available in STEM.

HOW WILL THEY TAKE PART?

Their participation in this study is entirely voluntary. There will be no grade implications or consequences if they choose not to participate in or withdraw from the study at any time. If they choose to participate, they will be asked to fill out survey forms and some may take part in focus group discussions (FGD) about their online class experiences that may last for 60 minutes. They will also be asked to provide feedback on how the approach has worked and how to improve the learning experience when the intervention is used in class. Answering the forms will take about 15 minutes. They can choose to skip any questions they do not want to answer. However, they may opt to accomplish the instrument at home when they are most comfortable or during one of their offline classes.

WHAT ARE THE PROCEDURES?

They will be in class where a particular intervention called an Inverted Learning Approach will be applied. This will span for the entire second quarter of the First Semester. They will be receiving the intervention and their performance will be monitored. They may be possibly asked or invited to be part of the focus group discussions (FGDs) and/or interviews moderated by the teacher-researcher.

For FGDs and interviews, there will be no questions, issues, or discussions which may be sensitive for them or potentially cause them embarrassment. The Focus Group Discussion focuses on their first-hand experience, objective thoughts, honest opinions, ideas, and recommendations to improve the instructional approach. It may further explore on their perspectives in terms of how they learn, how their teacher teaches, and how they relate with their classmates during the biology course. They may opt not to participate in FGDs and interviews.

Focus Group Discussions (FGD)

The FGD will be conducted online. Only students who are available and willing to participate will be included in the activity. This, too, has no grade implications. There will be fewer than ten students scheduled for their FGD. It will be led by the teacher-researcher himself, so they will not feel awkward sharing their experiences and open-ended responses with anyone they do not know. This will be recorded, and only the teacher-researcher will have a copy of the file for the sole purpose of research, which will not be shared with any other groups. The records will be temporarily stored for the duration of the study, and for analysis purposes only. They can respond either orally or in writing. They may not need to open their cameras when sharing in an online meeting. You as parents/guardians will sign a waiver indicating whether you want your son's or daughter's responses cited in part or included in the data for analysis. An FGD will be held for sixty (60) minutes only.

Interviews

To obtain more detailed information about their responses to Inverted Learning, selected students will be asked to participate in a one-on-one interview with the teacher-researcher. To ensure confidentiality and safety on their part, you may decide if you wish to accompany them during the online interview at your most convenient schedule. They (students) have the option of responding orally, in writing, or not at all. They may not need to open their cameras when sharing your answers. An interview will be held for a maximum of 30 minutes.

Survey questionnaire

Self-Efficacy survey will be administered online, thru the MS Teams. They may skip to the next question if they do not feel comfortable answering any of the questions. Because it will be given online, they will have the option to not participate if they are unable to access the materials due to an internet connection problem, emergency activities, and/or sickness. All information will be kept confidential, including their name and any of their identification, which may not be required at all. They may be given access to a copy of their own responses as well as the aggregate results if they so wish. Accomplishing the forms may take them 15 minutes maximum.

HOW LONG WILL THE STUDY LAST?

The actual research, that is, with the participation of the students, will span the entire second quarter of the S.Y. 2022-2023, including preparation and follow-up. This period will last from 01 September 2022 to 30 January 2023. The entire duration of the study, including the analysis and writing process, is from March 2022 March 2023.

WHAT MAY BE THE RISKS (IF ANY)?

Because the Inverted Learning Approach is apparently novel to them as students, selected topics in the first quarter will be flipped for them to adjust to the full exposure of the approach in the second quarter. Formative assessments are typically recorded but not graded; this will be determined during the first week of classes. The grading basis or components will remain consistent with the school grading policy reflected in the DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015 [Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 basic

Education Program]. As a result, there will be no changes and no source of bias in grading.

There will be no discussion of sensitive or personal issues that make the students feel uneasy. Overall, there will be no associated risk in their participation in the study. That means they will face no specific physical, physiological, or reducing vulnerability. In addition, the intervention will be implemented to students under the control or conventional group to address the issue of fairness since they did not receive this treatment during the actual study.

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF THEIR INVOLVEMENT?

The primary goal of the study is to improve science teaching and learning; however, they will benefit either indirectly or directly because of this. As an intervention, the

Inverted Learning Approach may benefit them by advancing their study time and making them more productive in class. Because course materials/lessons are delivered outside of class time and ahead of the week, they will be more prepared and informed for scheduled synchronous meetings. Thus, their academic performance may improve.

WHAT ARE THE ALTERNATIVES TO PARTICIPATION?

If the student belongs to the intervention group and prefers not to participate, they will still have access to the materials given for the intervention and will just continue their classwork in the same manner as they have all year. His/her data will not be included and processed in the analysis.

WILL THERE BE REIMBURSEMENTS?

Since their participation is entirely voluntary, they will not be compensated for taking part in the study. Likewise, they will not pay or reimburse any costs associated with their participation in the study.

HOW WILL THE DATA/RESULTS BE HANDLED?

The findings of the study may be published, but all their responses are strictly confidential, and their identity will not be associated with any of the results or used in any way. They may be aware of the consequences of disclosing their own experience or understanding, or lack thereof, when using the inverted learning approach, as an explanation for their level of ability. As participants in the FGD, they are highly encouraged to respect one another's ideas, experiences, and thoughts.

HOW WILL THE RESULTS BE SHARED?

The results of the study will be shared or disclosed in aggregate following the final defense of the paper. They may be informed about the findings, which may then be disseminated widely, through a school-level research colloquium, publications, and paper conferences.

DO THEY HAVE THE RIGHT TO REFUSE OR WITHDRAW?

Their participation is entirely voluntary, and they may withdraw at any time by not responding to the survey tools or participating in the focus group discussions and/or interviews. They also have the right to see their own responses and decide whether they should be included in the data.

HOW WILL THE DATA BE MANAGED?

Data will be temporarily stored in the researcher's up email's Google Drive. Should the teacher-researcher's device be unable to respond to the account, the up email is synced across two devices, protected by passcodes that only the teacher-researcher has the access too. The files will be kept only for the duration of the study and will be destroyed three (3) years right after the will be completed.

WHO WILL BE CONTACTED?

If you require further clarification about the study, please do not hesitate to reach out Rolly

James F, Cheng, thru mobile number, +63 906 083 1690, or thru email, rfcheng@up.edu.ph

The researcher's dissertation supervisor is Dr. Ricardo T. Bagarinao. He is the incumbent Dean of the Faculty of Education at UPOU, as well as the Project Director of the DOSTSEI Capacity Building Program in Science and Mathematics Education. He can be reached thru ricardo.bagarinao@upou.edu.ph

If you have about the rights of the human participants or wish to lobby a research-related problem or inquiry, contact the Cotabato Regional and Medical Center (CRMC)- Research Ethics Committee thru this mobile number, +63 966 665 0825, or thru email, crmcrsrch20@gmail.com

PART II: CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I, the parent/guardian of _____, agree and understand that his/her participation in the study entails sharing personal information, experiences, and performance, which may be processed in aggregate and published in accordance with data protection policies.

I also agree that all such information will be held or stored in the researcher's UP email account's google drive for as long as the purposes for which it is being processed are not satisfied.

As a participant, I understand that my son/daughter has the right to withdraw at any time, refuse to participate in the research, be informed about how his/her feedback and relevant data are being processed, and lobby a complaint with the National Privacy Commission.

I further acknowledge that I have read and understand fully the contents of this consent form. I consent voluntarily my son/daughter to be a participant in this study.

Signature of Parent/ Guardian: _____

Print Name of Parent/ Guardian: _____

Name of son/daughter: _____

Date: _____

STATEMENT BY THE RESEARCHER OR PERSON TAKING CONSENT

I read the information sheet to the potential participant accurately and, to the best of my ability, ensured that the parent/guardian understands that the following will be done:

1. **All of the preceding information will be strictly adhered to.**
2. **By signing this document, you allow your son/daughter to participate in this study.**
3. **If you have any questions about the study after signing this document, please contact the teacher-researcher using the information provided above.**
4. I confirm that the parent/guardian/participant was given the opportunity to ask questions about the study, and that all questions were answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual was not pressured into consenting, and that the consent was given freely and voluntarily.

ROLLY JAMES FULE CHENG

Date: _____

APPENDIX D

ASSENT FORM FOR SURVEYS, INTERVIEWS, AND FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS (FOR STUDENT PARTICIPANTS)

Study: STEM STUDENTS' DIRECT AND DEFERRED CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING AND SELF- EFFICACY USING THE INVERTED LEARNING APPROACH IN BIOLOGY: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY

Researcher: Rolly James Fule Cheng

Study Site: Notre Dame of Cotabato

PART I: INFORMATION SHEET INTRODUCTION

My name is Rolly James F. Cheng, and I am a doctoral student at the University of the Philippines-Open University's Faculty of Education. I am working on my dissertation under the supervision of Dr. Ricardo T. Bagarinao. This is an invitation to participate in my ongoing research. If you require clarification, please do not hesitate to ask questions at any time. If you require clarification, please do not hesitate to ask questions at any time thru this mobile number, 0906 083 1690, or thru my email, rfcheng@up.edu.ph

WHAT IS THE OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH?

The study focuses on the use of inverted or flipped learning and its effect on direct and deferred conceptual understanding in Biology. Similarly, it will determine how well this approach affects how you feel about yourself while learning and doing tasks in the course. This data will be used to develop an instructional improvement plan.

WHAT IS THE RESEARCH INTERVENTION?

Inverted Learning Approach is an instructional intervention, in which you will receive prerecorded teacher-made discussion videos of the content outside of class prior to the scheduled online class meeting. Thus, you will face no specific physical or physiological risk.

HOW AM I SELECTED?

You have been chosen because you are STEM students, and the study is looking into the effectiveness of a teaching approach in a course (Biology) that is only available in STEM.

HOW WILL I TAKE PART?

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. There will be no grade implications or consequences if you choose not to participate in or withdraw from the study at any time. If you choose to participate, you will be asked to fill out survey forms and some may take part in focus group discussions (FGD) about their online class experiences that may last for 60 minutes. You will also be asked to provide feedback on how the approach has worked and how to improve the learning experience when the intervention is used in class. Answering the forms will take about 15 minutes. You can choose to skip any questions you do not want to answer. However, you may opt to accomplish the instrument at home when you are most comfortable or during one of your offline classes.

WHAT ARE THE PROCEDURES?

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Interviews

To obtain more detailed information about your responses to Inverted Learning, selected students will be asked to participate in a one-on-one interview with the teacher-researcher. To ensure confidentiality and safety on your part, you may decide if you wish to be accompanied by your parent or guardian during the online interview.

at your most convenient schedule. You have the option of responding orally, in writing, or not at all. You may not need to open your cameras when sharing your answers. An interview will be held for a maximum of 30 minutes.

Survey Questionnaire

Self-Efficacy survey will be administered online, thru the MS Teams. You may skip to the next question if you do not feel comfortable answering any of the questions. Because it will be given online, you will have the option to not participate if you are unable to access the materials due to an internet connection problem, emergency activities, and/or sickness. All information will be kept confidential, including your name and any of your identification, which may not be required at all. You may be given access to a copy of your own responses as well as the aggregate results if you so wish. Accomplishing the forms may take you 15 minutes maximum.

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WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF MY INVOLVEMENT?

The primary goal of the study is to improve science teaching and learning; however, you will benefit either indirectly or directly as a result of this. As an intervention, the Inverted Learning Approach may benefit you by advancing your study time and making you more productive in class. Because course materials/lessons are delivered outside of class time and ahead of the week, you will be more prepared and informed for scheduled synchronous meetings. Thus, your academic performance may improve.

WHAT ARE MY ALTERNATIVES TO PARTICIPATION?

If the student belongs to the intervention group and prefers not to participate, they will still have the access to the materials given for the intervention and will just continue their classwork in the same manner as they have all year. His/her data will not be included and processed in the analysis.

WILL THERE BE REIMBURSEMENTS?

Since your participation is entirely voluntary, you will not be compensated for taking part in the study. Likewise, you will not pay or reimburse any costs associated with your participation in the study.

HOW WILL THE DATA/RESULTS BE HANDLED?

The findings of the study may be published, but all of your responses are strictly confidential, and your identity will not be associated with any of the results or used in any way. You may be aware of the consequences of disclosing your own experience or understanding, or lack thereof, when using the inverted learning approach, as an explanation for your level of ability. As participants in the FGD, you are highly encouraged to respect one another's ideas, experiences, and thoughts.

HOW WILL THE RESULTS BE SHARED?

The results of the study will be shared or disclosed in aggregate following the final defense of the paper. You may be informed about the findings, which may then be disseminated widely, through a school-level research colloquium, publications, and paper conferences.

DO I HAVE THE RIGHT TO REFUSE OR WITHDRAW?

Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time by not responding to the survey tools or participating in the focus group discussions and/or interviews. You also have the right to see your own responses and decide whether they should be included in the data.

HOW WILL THE DATA BE MANAGED?

Data will be temporarily stored in the researcher's up email's Google Drive. Should the teacher-researcher's device be unable to respond to the account, the up email is synced across two devices, protected by passcodes that only the teacher-researcher has the access too. The files will be kept only for the duration of the study and will be destroyed three (3) years right after the will be completed.

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If you require further clarification about the study, please do not hesitate to reach out Rolly James F, Cheng, thru mobile number, +63 906 083 1690, or thru email, rfcheng@up.edu.ph

The researcher's dissertation supervisor is Dr. Ricardo T. Bagarinao. He is the incumbent Dean of the Faculty of Education at UPOU, as well as the Project Director of the DOSTSEI Capacity Building Program in Science and Mathematics Education. He can be reached thru ricardo.bagarinao@upou.edu.ph

If you have about the rights of the human participants or wish to lobby a research-related problem or inquiry, contact the Cotabato Regional and Medical Center (CRMC)- Research Ethics Committee thru this mobile number, +63 966 665 0825, or thru email, crmcrsrch20@gmail.com

PART II: CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I agree and understand that my participation in the study entails sharing my personal information, experiences, and performance, which may be processed in aggregate and published in accordance with data protection policies.

I also agree that all such information will be held or stored in the researcher's UP email account's google drive for as long as the purposes for which it is being processed are not satisfied.

As a participant, I understand that I have the right to withdraw at any time, refuse to participate in the research, be informed about how my feedback and relevant data are being processed, and lobby a complaint with the National Privacy Commission.

I further acknowledge that I have read this assent form and fully understand its contents. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: _____

STATEMENT BY THE RESEARCHER OR PERSON TAKING CONSENT

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the

I read the information sheet to the potential participant accurately and, to the best of my ability, ensured that the participant understands that the following will be done:

1. All the preceding information will be strictly adhered to.

2. By signing this document, you agree to participate in this study.
3. If you have any questions about the study after signing this document, please contact the teacher-researcher using the information provided above.

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant were answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual was not pressured into consenting, and that the consent was given freely and voluntarily.

ROLLY JAMES FULE CHENG

Date: _____

APPENDIX E

OUTLINE OF TOPICS FOR THE SECOND QUARTER IN GENERAL BIOLOGY 1

Week No.	Topic	Competencies
1	ATP-ADP Cycle	<i>#1. Explain coupled reaction processes and describe the role of ATP in energy coupling and transfer [STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-1].</i>
2-3	Photosynthesis and the Role of Pigments	<i>#3. Explain the importance of chlorophyll and other pigments [STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-3]</i>
3	Light-Dependent Reactions	<i>#4. Describe the patterns of electron flow through light reaction events STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-4</i> <i>#11. Compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-11</i>
4	Light-Independent Reactions (Calvin Cycle)	<i>#5. Describe the significant events of the Calvin cycle STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-5</i> <i>#11. Compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-11</i>
5	Cellular Respiration and the Role of the Mitochondrion	<i>#7. Explain the major features and sequence the chemical events of cellular respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-7</i> <i>#8. Distinguish major features of glycolysis, Krebs cycle, electron transport system, and chemiosmosis STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-8</i>
6	Aerobic Respiration: Glycolysis	<i>#6. Differentiate aerobic from anaerobic respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-6</i> <i>#9. Describe reactions that produce and consume ATP STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-9</i> <i>#11. Compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-11</i>

Week No.	Topic	Competencies
6	Aerobic Respiration: Krebs Cycle	<p>#6. Differentiate aerobic from anaerobic respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-6</p> <p>#9. Describe reactions that produce and consume ATP STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-9</p> <p>#11. Compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-11</p>
7	Aerobic Respiration: Chemiosmosis and Electron Transport Chain	<p>#6. Differentiate aerobic from anaerobic respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-6</p> <p>#9. Describe reactions that produce and consume ATP STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-9</p> <p>#10. Describe the role of oxygen in respiration and describe pathways of electron flow in the absence of oxygen STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-10</p> <p>#11. Compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-11</p>
8	Anaerobic Respiration	<p>#6. Differentiate aerobic from anaerobic respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-6</p> <p>#9. Describe reactions that produce and consume ATP STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-9</p> <p>#10. Describe the role of oxygen in respiration and describe pathways of electron flow in the absence of oxygen STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-10</p> <p>#11. Compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-11</p>

Week No.	Topic	Competencies
9	Comparing Photosynthesis and Cellular Respiration	<p><i>#2. Describe the major features and chemical events in photosynthesis and respiration [STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-2]</i></p> <p><i>#7. Explain the major features and sequence the chemical events of cellular respiration</i> STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-7</p>
9	ATP Count in Photosynthesis and Cellular Respiration	<p><i>#11. Compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration</i> STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-11</p>
10	Advantages and Disadvantages of Fermentation and Aerobic Respiration	<p><i>#12. Explain the advantages and disadvantages of fermentation and aerobic respiration</i> STEM_BIO11/12- Ila-j-12</p>

APPENDIX F

Flexible Instruction Delivery Plan (FIDP) and Curriculum Map (CM)

Grade: **12**

Specialized Subject Title: **General Biology 1**

Semester: **First**

No. of Hours/Semester: **40 hours/ 10 weeks per Quarter**

Specialized Subject Description: This subject is designed to enhance the understanding of the principles and concepts in the study of biology, particularly life processes at the cellular and molecular levels. It also covers the transformation of energy in organisms.

Culminating Performance Standard: The learner shall be able to prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce products like wine or vinegar via microorganism, and/or plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.

What to Teach?				Why Teach?				How to Assess?		How to Teach?	
Content	Content Standards	Most Essential Topics	Performance Standards	Learning competencies				Highest Thinking Skill to Assess		Highest Enabling Strategy to Use in developing the Highest Thinking Skill to Assess	
				Complete	KUD Classification	Most Essential	KUD Classification	RBT Level	Flexible Assessment Activities (FAA) Performance Checks	Enabling General Strategy	Flexible Learning Strategies (FLS)
SECOND QUARTER											
	The learners demonstrate an understanding of:		The learners shall be able to:								
Energy Transformation	ATP-ADP Cycle	ATP ADP Energy Metabolism	make a <i>week-long Meal Plan, indicating calorie and ATP counts, and suggested food intake/meal program.</i>	1. explain coupled reaction processes and describe the role of ATP in energy coupling and transfer (STEM_BIO11/12-11a-j-1)	U	explain coupled reaction processes and describe the role of ATP in energy coupling and transfer	U	Analyzing	Discussion Forum	Communication	Think-Pair-Share

What to Teach?				Why Teach?				How to Assess?		How to Teach?	
Content	Content Standards	Most Essential Topics	Performance Standards	Learning competencies				Highest Thinking Skill to Assess		Highest Enabling Strategy to Use in developing the Highest Thinking Skill to Assess	
				Complete	KUD Classification	Most Essential	KUD Classification	RBT Level	Flexible Assessment Activities (FAA) Performance Checks	Enabling General Strategy	Flexible Learning Strategies (FLS)
SECOND QUARTER											
	The learners demonstrate an understanding of:		The learners shall be able to:								
Energy Transformation	Photosynthesis	Leaf Chloroplast Chlorophyll Light Light-dependent reaction Calvin Cycle	prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microbes; or make a <i>week-long Meal Plan, indicating calorie and ATP counts, and suggested food intake/meal program.</i>	2. describe the major features and chemical events in photosynthesis and respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-11a-j-2)	K	explain the importance of chlorophyll and other pigments	U	Understanding	Concept Mapping	Communication	Graphic Organizer
				3. explain the importance of chlorophyll and other pigments (STEM_BIO11/12-11a-j-3)	U			Applying	Oral Recitation	Connection	Discussion
				4. describe the patterns of electron flow through light reaction events (STEM_BIO11/12-11a-j-4)	K			Understanding	Picture/Video Analysis	Representation	Breakout Room Discussion
				5. describe the significant events of the Calvin Cycle (STEM_BIO11/12-11a-j-5)	K			Understanding	Quick Responses	Representation	Web-based Interaction (Kahoot and Menti.com)

What to Teach?				Why Teach?				How to Assess?		How to Teach?	
Content	Content Standards	Most Essential Topics	Performance Standards	Learning competencies				Highest Thinking Skill to Assess		Highest Enabling Strategy to Use in developing the Highest Thinking Skill to Assess	
				Complete	KUD Classification	Most Essential	KUD Classification	RBT Level	Flexible Assessment Activities (FAA) Performance Checks	Enabling General Strategy	Flexible Learning Strategies (FLS)
SECOND QUARTER											
Energy Transformation	The learners demonstrate an understanding of: Cellular Respiration	Glycolysis Pyruvate Oxidation Krebs Cycle Electron Transport Chain/ System Fermentation	The learners shall be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microbes; or <i>make a week-long Meal Plan, indicating calorie and ATP counts, and suggested food intake/ meal program.</i>	6. differentiate aerobic from anaerobic respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-6) 7. explain the major features and sequence the chemical events of cellular respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-7) 8. distinguish major features of glycolysis, Krebs cycle, electron transport system, and chemiosmosis. (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-8) 9. describe the reactions that produce and consume ATP (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-9)	K U K K		U	Understanding Analyzing Remembering Understanding	Discussion Forum Constructed Response Short Quiz Q and A	Representation Communication Representation Representation	Think-Pair-Share Discussion Labeling Peer discussion

What to Teach?				Why Teach?				How to Assess?		How to Teach?	
Content	Content Standards	Most Essential Topics	Performance Standards	Learning competencies				Highest Thinking Skill to Assess		Highest Enabling Strategy to Use in developing the Highest Thinking Skill to Assess	
				Complete	KUD Classification	Most Essential	KUD Classification	RBT Level	Flexible Assessment Activities (FAA) Performance Checks	Enabling General Strategy	Flexible Learning Strategies (FLS)
SECOND QUARTER											
Energy Transformation	The learners demonstrate an understanding of: Cellular Respiration	Glycolysis Pyruvate Oxidation Krebs Cycle Electron Transport Chain/ System Fermentation	The learners shall be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microbes; or <i>make a week-long Meal Plan, indicating calorie and ATP counts, and suggested food intake/ meal program.</i>	10. describe the role of oxygen in respiration and describe pathways of electron flow in the absence of oxygen (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-10) 11. compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-11) 12. explain the advantages and disadvantages of fermentation and aerobic respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-12)	K U U		U	Understanding Analyzing Evaluating	Mind Mapping Game/ Short Quiz Constructed Response	Representation Communication Reasoning and Proof	Graphic Organizer Collaborative Learning Breakout Room Discussion

CURRICULUM MAP

MONTH	CONTENT	CONTENT STANDARD	PERFORMANCE STANDARD	FORMATION STANDARDS	LEARNING COMPETENCIES	ASSESSMENT	ACTIVITIES / RESOURCES OR MATERIALS		INSTITUTIONAL CORE VALUES
							OFFLINE	ONLINE	
OCTOBER- NOVEMBER	Energy Transformation	The learners demonstrate an understanding of: ATP-ADP Cycle	The learners should be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microorganism; and/or, plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.	The learners become: contributors to community development by proposing ways to boost the economy thru supporting local businesses; and/or finding ways to improve the well-being of people thru observing healthful lifestyle/ choices/ practices.	A1. Describe the coupled reaction processes and describe the role of ATP in energy coupling and transfer.	A1. Concept Mapping A1. Lab Activities: a. The structure of ATP (by pair) – 11 pts b. ATP Decomposition (by pair)- 10 pts c. ATP Synthesis (by pair)- 10 pts A1. Short Quiz	ACQUISITION		Humane Excellent Adaptive Responsive
							A1. Teacher-made and curated power point presentations 2- ATP-ADP Cycle 3- Redox Concept		

MONTH	CONTENT	CONTENT STANDARD	PERFORMANCE STANDARD	FORMATION STANDARDS	LEARNING COMPETENCIES	ASSESSMENT	ACTIVITIES / RESOURCES OR MATERIALS		INSTITUTIONAL CORE VALUES
							OFFLINE	ONLINE	
	Energy Transformation	The learners demonstrate an understanding of: Photosynthesis	The learners should be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microorganism; and/or, plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.	The learners become: contributors to community development by proposing ways to boost the economy thru supporting local businesses; and/or finding ways to improve the well-being of people thru observing healthful lifestyle/ choices/ practices.	A2. Describe the major features and chemical events in photosynthesis and respiration [STEM_BIO11/12- Iia-j-2] A3. Describe the patterns of electron flow through light reaction events STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-4 A4. Describe the significant events of the Calvin cycle STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-5	A2. Concept Mapping A2. Venn Diagram A3. Short Quiz A4. Question and Answer	ACQUISITION		Excellent Responsive
							A2/3/4. Teacher-made and curated power point presentations 4- Photosynthesis de 5- Chloroplast; Light; 6- Stages of Photosynthesis		

MONTH	CONTENT	CONTENT STANDARD	PERFORMANCE STANDARD	FORMATION STANDARDS	LEARNING COMPETENCIES	ASSESSMENT	ACTIVITIES / RESOURCES OR MATERIALS		INSTITUTIONAL CORE VALUES
							OFFLINE	ONLINE	
ACQUISITION									
	Energy Transformation	The learners demonstrate an understanding of: Respiration	The learners should be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microorganisms; and/or, plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.	The learners become: contributors to community development by proposing ways to boost the economy thru supporting local businesses; and/or finding ways to improve the well-being of people thru observing healthful lifestyle/choices/practices.	A5. Differentiate aerobic from anaerobic respiration STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-6 A6. Distinguish major features of glycolysis, Krebs cycle, electron transport system, and chemiosmosis STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-8 A7. Describe reactions that produce and consume ATP STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-9 A8. Describe the role of oxygen in respiration and describe pathways of electron flow in the absence of oxygen STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-10	A5. Venn Diagram A6. Concept Mapping A7. Oral Recitation A8. Question and Answer A5/6/7/8. Short Quiz	A5/6/7/8. Teacher-made and curated power point presentations 	Excellent Adaptive Responsive Transformative	

MONTH	CONTENT	CONTENT STANDARD	PERFORMANCE STANDARD	FORMATION STANDARDS	LEARNING COMPETENCIES	ASSESSMENT	ACTIVITIES / RESOURCES OR MATERIALS		INSTITUTIONAL CORE VALUES
							OFFLINE	ONLINE	
MAKE MEANING									
NOVEMBER - DECEMBER	Energy Transformation	The learners demonstrate an understanding of: ATP-ADP Cycle	The learners should be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microorganisms; and/or, plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.	The learners become: contributors to community development by proposing ways to boost the economy thru supporting local businesses; and/or finding ways to improve the well-being of people thru observing healthful lifestyle/choices/practices.	M1. Explain coupled reaction processes and describe the role of ATP in energy coupling and transfer [STEM_BIO11/12- Iia-j-1].	M1. Discussion Forum M1. Lab Activity, ATP/ADP Cycle (individual) M1. Short Quiz	M1. Teacher-made and curated power point presentations 	Excellent Adaptive Responsive	

MONTH	CONTENT	CONTENT STANDARD	PERFORMANCE STANDARD	FORMATION STANDARDS	LEARNING COMPETENCIES	ASSESSMENT	ACTIVITIES / RESOURCES OR MATERIALS		INSTITUTIONAL CORE VALUES
							OFFLINE	ONLINE	
MAKE MEANING									
	Energy Transformation	The learners demonstrate an understanding of: Photosynthesis	The learners should be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microorganisms; and/or, plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.	The learners become: contributors to community development by proposing ways to boost the economy thru supporting local businesses; and/or finding ways to improve the well-being of people thru observing healthful lifestyle/choices/practices.	M2. Explain the importance of chlorophyll and other pigments [STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-3]	M2. Video Analysis M2. Discussion Forum M2. Journal review/ Lab Activity M2. Short Quiz	M2. Teacher-made and curated power point presentations 	Excellent Responsive	

MONTH	CONTENT	CONTENT STANDARD	PERFORMANCE STANDARD	FORMATION STANDARDS	LEARNING COMPETENCIES	ASSESSMENT	ACTIVITIES / RESOURCES OR MATERIALS		INSTITUTIONAL CORE VALUES
							OFFLINE	ONLINE	
MAKE MEANING									
	Energy Transformation	The learners demonstrate an understanding of: Respiration	The learners should be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microorganisms; and/or, plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.	The learners become: contributors to community development by proposing ways to boost the economy thru supporting local businesses; and/or finding ways to improve the well-being of people thru observing healthful lifestyle/choices/practices.	M3. Explain the major features and sequence the chemical events of cellular respiration STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-7 M4. Compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-11 M5. Explain the advantages and disadvantages of fermentation and aerobic respiration STEM_BIO11/12 - Iia-j-12	M3. Oral Recitation M4. Discussion Forum/ Activity: Complete the Table M5. Constructed Response M3/4/5. Short Quiz	M3/4/5. Teacher-made and curated power point presentations 	Excellent Adaptive	

MONTH	ESSENTIAL QUESTION	ESSENTIAL UNDERSTANDING	PERFORMANCE STANDARD	FORMATION STANDARDS	LEARNING COMPETENCIES	ASSESSMENT	ACTIVITIES / RESOURCES OR MATERIALS		INSTITUTIONAL CORE VALUES
							OFFLINE	ONLINE	
					TRANSFER				
DECEMBER	<i>Essential Question: How can appropriate and healthful diet program help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health/well-being?</i>	<i>Essential Understanding: Students will understand that appropriate dietary program helps people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health/well-being.</i>	The learners should be able to: prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce wine or vinegar via microorganisms; and/or, plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.	The learners become: contributors to community development by proposing ways to boost the economy thru supporting local businesses; and/or finding ways to improve the well-being of people thru observing healthful lifestyle/choices/practices.	T1. Make of a week-long Meal Plan, indicating calorie and ATP counts, and suggested food intake/ meal program that can help people with specific nutrition-related problems improve their overall health/well-being.	T1. Performance Task with a rubric for scoring	T1. Scaffold Activities		Humane Responsive

PERFORMANCE TASK (2nd Quarter)

[G]: You will monitor the patient’s food plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help him or her improve his or her overall health. This may include checking the calorie counts associated with food and drink to determine the recommended daily calorie intake based on age, sex, size, and activity level.

[R]: You are a member of a health care team consisting of health professionals who work together to coordinate your patients’ medical and dietary needs, providing them with a proper diet or nutrition program to improve their well-being.

[A]: Patients suffering from general health problems (obesity, malnutrition, etc...)

[S]: Consuming a healthful diet throughout one’s life helps in the prevention of malnourishment in all of its forms, as well as a variety of diet-related noncommunicable medical conditions (WHO, 2019). However, increased processed food consumption and changing lifestyles have resulted in a shift in dietary patterns. People are eating more foods high in energy, fats, free sugars, or salt/sodium, and many do not consume enough fiber-rich fruits, vegetables, and whole grains. Following Wahl, Villinger, König, Ziesemer, Schupp, and Renner (2017), healthful food choices such as eating fruits and vegetables have not only physical but also mental health benefits, and this understanding of healthy diet (Mötteli, Keller, Siegrist, Barbey, & Bucher, 2016) may promote healthy eating and a long-term investment in better future health. People become more susceptible to health-related diseases and disorders as a result of unhealthy dieting, poor eating patterns, and poor food choices (Rounsefell, Gibson, McLean, Blair, Molenaar, Brennan, & McCaffrey, 2020), as well as the sedentary lifestyle most people lead.

References:

1. Mötteli, S., Keller, C., Siegrist, M., Barbey, J., & Bucher, T. (2016). Consumers’ practical understanding of healthy food choices: a fake food experiment. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 116(3), 559-566.
2. Rounsefell, K., Gibson, S., McLean, S., Blair, M., Molenaar, A., Brennan, L., ... & McCaffrey, T. A. (2020). Social media, body image and food choices in healthy young adults: A mixed methods systematic review. *Nutrition & Dietetics*, 77(1), 19-40.
3. Wahl, D. R., Villinger, K., König, L. M., Ziesemer, K., Schupp, H. T., & Renner, B. (2017). Healthy food choices are happy food choices: Evidence from a real life sample using smartphone based assessments. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 1-8.
4. World Health Organization. (2019). *Healthy diet* (No. WHO-EM/NUT/282/E). World Health Organization. Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean.

[P]: Making of a week-long Meal Plan, indicating calorie and ATP counts, and suggested food intake/ meal program

Steps:

1. Set the desired weight (reduce, maintain, or gain), go to <https://www.calculator.net/calorie-calculator.html>
2. Express height in cm and your weight in kg. For unit conversion, go to www.calculator.net/conversion-calculator.html
3. Determine the number of calorie equivalent of the food you eat; you may research it directly, <https://www.webmd.com/diet/healthtool-food-calorie-counter>
4. A template below is provided as a sample. Strictly no unnecessary arts required.

⊕ Name: _____ Height: _____ Weight: _____ Age: _____
 Target Weight: _____ Sex: _____

5-day Meal Plan

Day	Breakfast <i>[You may change this and indicate or specify your eating time]</i>	Lunch	Dinner	TOTAL
1	<i>Indicate the quantity of the food (kcal count)</i>			
2				
3				
Calorie Count				
ATP Count				

[S]: Accuracy/ Content (40 pts); Originality and Completeness (20 pts); and Presentation (15 pts)

Criteria	Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good
Accuracy/ Content (40 points)	Information is inaccurate, and very limited.	Information is accurate but limited.	Information is accurate and substantial.	Information is accurate, with pictures/evidence, and substantial data.
Originality and Completeness of Data (20 points)	The meal plan is originally made. The plan/menu covers one (1) to two (2) days.	The meal plan is originally made. The plan/menu covers three (3) to four (4) days.	The meal plan is creatively and originally made. The plan/menu covers five (5) days.	The meal plan is creatively and originally made. The plan/menu covers six (6) to seven (7) days.
Presentation/ Explanation of the plan (15 points)	The meal plan and the recommendations are supported by figures but no discussions and references.	The meal plan and the recommendations are supported by figures but have limited discussions and references.	The meal plan and the recommendations are supported by figures and are thoroughly discussed and referenced.	The meal plan and the recommendations are supported by figures and are thoroughly discussed and referenced including the risks and claims.

APPENDIX G

JMJ
MARIST BROTHERS
NOTRE DAME OF COTABATO
COTABATO CITY

TEACHING GUIDE

Grade: **12**

Teacher: **Rolly James Fule Cheng, MSciEd**

Specialized Subject Title: **General Biology 1**

Specialized Subject Description: This subject is designed to enhance the understanding of the principles and concepts in the study of biology, particularly life processes at the cellular and molecular levels. It also covers the transformation of energy in organisms.

Semester: **First**

No. of Hours/Semester: **40 hours/ 10 weeks per Quarter**

SECOND QUARTER

Unit:	Energy Transformation
Topic:	ATP-ADP Cycle and Redox Concepts
Content Standards:	The learner demonstrates understanding of ATP- ADP Cycle, Photosynthesis, and Respiration.
Performance Standards:	The learner shall be able to prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce products like wine or vinegar via microorganism, and/or plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health.
Learning Competency/ies:	The learners explain the coupled reaction processes and describe the role of ATP in energy coupling and transfer (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-1); and describe reactions that produce and consume ATP (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-9).
Materials:	Powerpoint Presentation, Drawing Tab
Resources:	Quipper Online Content, Teacher-made discussion videos

03-07 October 2022

WEEK 0	
A. Administration of Pretest B. Presentation of the Culminating Performance Task in GRASPS Form- 2 nd Quarter	
10-14 October 2022	
WEEK 1	
MEETINGS 1 & 2	FOR INTERVENTION
Specific Learning Outcomes: The learners can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> describe the role of ATP as an energy currency of the cell; and, describe the importance and mechanism of energy transformation in cells. 	Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.

Values To Be Integrated:	Adaptivity, Excellence, and Environmental Awareness	
Motivation/ Introduction:	What do these pictures have in common? How does the concept of energy transformation become useful in organisms? 	
Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	How is chemical energy utilized in different cellular processes? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy is defined as the ability to do work or bring about a change, allowing organisms to carry out different life processes, including growth, development, metabolism, and reproduction. How do the laws of thermodynamics differ from one another? Energy is not created by the plants, but rather, they obtain it from sunlight and convert it into a form that can be stored in chemical bonds of biomolecules. A portion of the solar energy absorbed by the plant becomes heat when glucose is utilized during respiration. How does entropy affect cellular mechanisms? Entropy is used to indicate the relative amount of disorganization of a system. It is the measure of randomness. The more disordered a system is, the higher is its entropy. The second law of thermodynamics can be shown in the breakdown of glucose and the movement of ions across the cell membrane. These processes naturally tend to proceed into a state of greater entropy.	Determine the possible consequences should the following events take place. Discussion thru breakout rooms. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Two objects have the same rate of movement of their atoms or molecules. Conservation of energy is not possible anymore for the biosphere. The three phosphate groups of ATP are stable and cannot be easily broken down.
Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:	I learned that _____; but I find _____ difficult to understand.	Identify the terms being described by each of the following statements. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> It is defined as the ability to do work or bring about a change. It is a stored energy whose capacity to accomplish work is not being used at the moment. It is a type of kinetic energy associated with the random movement of atoms or molecules

MEETINGS 3 & 4		FOR INTERVENTION
Specific Learning Outcomes:	The learners can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> describe the structure and function of adenosine triphosphate; and, explain the mechanism of reaction coupling involving adenosine triphosphate. 	Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.
Values To Be Integrated:	Adaptivity, Excellence, and Environmental Awareness	
Motivation/ Introduction:	How are the terms metabolism, kinetic energy, and potential energy related to ATP?	<p>Describe the picture in one or two sentences. *Administration of entry tickets (thru google forms)</p>
Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	<p>What is ATP? What are the roles of ATP?</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 45%;"> <p>Functions of ATP</p> <p>What are the roles of ATP?</p> <p>The triphosphate tail of ATP is the portion that provides energy for cellular work.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each is negatively charged. Repel each other Breaking the bonds releases energy. </div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 45%;"> <p>Functions of ATP</p> <p>What are the roles of ATP?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ATP energizes other molecules in cells by transferring phosphate groups to those molecules. ATP is also responsible for mechanical, transport and chemical functions. </div> </div>	<p>The structure of ATP (by pair) – 11 pts</p> <p>ATP consists of 3 parts: 1 adenine molecule, 1 ribose sugar molecule, and 3 phosphate molecules. Energy is stored in the bond that is found between the 2nd and 3rd phosphate groups.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> COLOR & LABEL the following in the ATP molecules below: (10 pts) adenine – green, ribose – pink; phosphate groups – alpha (yellow); beta (blue); gamma (red) BOX the area that represents the HIGH ENERGY bond. (1 pt)
Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:	Figure out why is a mitochondrion considered as the powerhouse of the cell? I learned that....	Making of learning log

3

MEETINGS 1 & 2		FOR INTERVENTION
Specific Learning Outcomes:	The learners can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> describe the the coupling process of ATP-ADP cycle. 	Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.
Values To Be Integrated:	Excellence, Responsiveness, and Self-care	
Motivation/ Introduction:	<p>One must have a constant supply of energy to be able to perform tasks daily. The energy that we use to execute tasks sometimes gets exhausted that we need to replenish it constantly for cells to keep functioning. To regain energy in the form of ATP, we consume healthful and nutritious food, which can be oxidized to release energy. Having a constant supply of energy makes our cells function at optimum for maintenance and survival.</p> <p>How do cells regenerate the energy that they constantly need?</p>	<p>How is ATP used to drive various cellular processes?</p>
Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	<p>How is ATP used to drive various cellular processes?</p>	

4

		<p>ATP Synthesis (by pair)- 10 pts ATP molecules are constantly being rebuilt from ADP and lone phosphate groups. This ensures that cells always have a source of energy. However, it takes energy to make ATP. The energy to make ATP comes from a carbohydrate called GLUCOSE. Glucose is a monosaccharide, or simple sugar. Its chemical formula is $C_6H_{12}O_6$. Plants produce glucose during photosynthesis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>COLOR & LABEL</i> the following in the energy molecule below: (8 pts) adenine – green; ribose – red, first two phosphate groups – blue, lone phosphate group – green. <i>COLOR</i> the energy absorbed – orange. (1 pt) <i>NAME</i> the molecule. (1 pt)
Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:	A short quiz will be given.	Making of learning log
MEETINGS 3 & 4		FOR INTERVENTION
Specific Learning Outcomes:	The learners can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> explain the mechanism and importance of the ADP-ATP cycle. 	Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.
Values To Be Integrated:	Excellence, Responsiveness, and Self-care	
Motivation/ Introduction:	Students will be asked of what information they can give about ATP.	Administration of entry tickets (thru google forms)

Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	<p>Mechanisms of ATP Synthesis</p> <p>Substrate-level phosphorylation is the process of producing ATP by combining ADP and a phosphate group from a phosphorylated molecule instead of an inorganic phosphate. Oxidative phosphorylation is an ATP synthesizing mechanism that utilizes the energy derived from the transfer of electrons in an electron transport system to combine ADP and inorganic phosphate. Photophosphorylation is driven by the proton motive force generated during the flow of electrons in the light reaction stage. The protons flow through the ATP synthase enzyme complex, which triggers ATP synthesis.</p> <p>How do endergonic reactions differ from exergonic reactions?</p> <p>ATP (+ water) → ADP + Pi (hydrolysis/ dephosphorylation) – energy is released for cellular work / metabolic pathway – Exergonic rxn</p> <p>ATP ← ADP + Pi (phosphorylation/ dehydration synthesis)- energy from the food we eat. Energy is absorbed- Endergonic rxn</p> <p>Note: 3 bonds (high energy); 2 bonds (low energy)</p>	<p>ATP/ADP Cycle</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Label ATP and ADP molecules Label Adenine, Ribose, Phosphate Groups (1, 2, 3) → both on the ATP & ADP molecule Color entire ATP → GREEN Color Energy Released → ORANGE Color Lightning Bolt → PURPLE Color Lone Phosphate in ADP → YELLOW Color entire ADP → BLUE Color Energy Absorbed → RED Rearrange the image/s showing the ATP/ADP cycle. <i>Start</i> with ATP on the top. <i>ADD ARROWS</i> to show that this process is a continuous cycle. Give the cycle a title: ATP/ADP Cycle
Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:	Students will play, "Who wants to be a millionaire?" game.	<p>Identify the term being described by the following statements.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> This nucleotide is composed of an adenine base, a ribose sugar, and three phosphate groups. This process transfers a phosphate group from an ATP to another molecule. This portion of ATP provides the energy needed by various cellular processes.

WEEK 3		FOR INTERVENTION
MEETINGS 1 & 2		
Specific Learning Outcomes:	The learners can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify common electron carriers; and, describe the oxidation-reduction reaction process. 	Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.
Values To Be Integrated:	Critical Thinking and Intellectual Honesty	17-21 October 2022
Motivation/ Introduction:	A meme will be shown to give students easy way to remember the redox description. 	
Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	Electron carriers are compounds that can easily accept (i.e., be reduced) or lose electrons (i.e., be oxidized). As a result, they play an important role in energy production. Electron carriers allow for a controlled flow of electrons, which makes it possible for the production of ATP. The cell would stop working if there will be no electron carriers. Source: https://www.jove.com/science-education/10744/electron-carriers 	
Lesson Closure/ Evaluation:	An oral recitation will be done as an exit ticket (Part 1)	I learned that...

MEETINGS 3 & 4		FOR INTERVENTION
Specific Learning Outcomes:	The learners can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> explain how electron carriers become reduced or oxidized. 	Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.
Values To Be Integrated:	Critical Thinking and Intellectual Honesty	
Motivation/ Introduction:	Getting to know/ re-know hydrogen, its atomic structure, as a diatomic element, and as an ion. 	
Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	There are so many redox reactions that happen during metabolism. Redox reactions fundamentally require the transfer or removal of electrons in order to reduce or oxidize a specific substrate or molecule. As a result, we require electron carriers capable of undergoing electron transfer. These are the coenzymes we discussed in the previous slides. Please keep in mind that the redox rxns of these coenzymes are always coupled, which is why oxidized and reduced forms of our electron carriers can coexist, or say they exist at the same time.	Students-led discussion will be facilitated by the teacher thru breakout rooms.
Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:	An oral recitation will be done as an exit ticket (Part 1)	I learned that _____; but I find _____ difficult to understand.

Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:

What are stomata?

They are the minute pores that facilitate gas exchange.
Water loss from the plant's body through the stomata is known as transpiration.

Plants have a paired guard cells on each side of the stomata to regulate the opening and closing of the pore.

Moving Materials Inside Plants

(How do materials move through plants?)

> Xylem- a vascular tissue in most plants that transports water and minerals from roots to the different parts like stems and leaves

> Phloem- a vascular tissue that moves dissolved nutrients/liquid sugar that the plants have produced through photosynthesis to flow in all directions within the plant

Plant's roots → xylem → all parts of the plant stems/leaves
Food or Sugar → phloem → flows to all plant cells

The structure determines the function. As you can see, the leaf has cuticle above and below it. Upper and lower epidermal layers (flat, irregularly shaped cells) are also observable. The waxy cuticle produced by epidermal cells protects the leaf and regulates the rate of transpiration in plants. The pore known as a stoma is shown below (or stomata in plural form). A pair of guard cells surround this tiny pore. Water and CO₂ channels [transpire]. You can also see that the majority of the internal tissue of the leaf, known as the mesophyll, which is divided into two types:

Palisade mesophyll is, of course, made up of palisade cells. [well arranged or packed together to allow for effective light capture, because here we can see most of the chlorophyll molecules in the leaves.] Spongy mesophyll is made up of spongy cells. [have open spaces that allow for efficient material transport within the leaves]

Finally, there are also the vascular tissues, which are the xylem and phloem. The xylem, in particular, is the vascular tissue that transports water and minerals from the roots to the stems or leaves where water is required for food production.

Discuss the terms you see in the box.

C	A	R	B	O	N	C	C	D
A	B	J	I	H	G	F	U	E
K	L	M	A	M	O	R	T	S
X	S	N	O	P	Q	R	I	S
Y	I	W	N	V	U	T	C	L
L	M	X	E	Y	Z	A	L	E
E	R	D	G	C	B	Y	E	A
M	E	E	Y	F	H	G	H	E
N	D	M	X	P	L	K	J	I
O	I	P	O	Q	R	S	T	U
C	P	S	T	O	M	A	T	A
D	E	B	A	Z	Y	X	W	V
M	E	F	G	W	A	T	E	R

Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:

Students will participate in the asynchronous discussion forum via MS Teams.

Making of learning log

WEEK 5

MEETINGS 1 & 2

FOR INTERVENTION

Specific Learning Outcomes:

- The learners can
- explain the functions of photosynthetic pigments;
 - describe chloroplasts, and light as requirements for photosynthesis; and,
 - distinguish principal photosynthetic pigments from accessory photosynthetic pigments.

Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.

24-28 October 2022

Values To Be Integrated:

Open-mindedness and Excellence

Motivation/ Introduction:

Why do most plants appear green?

Provide brief answers and explanations to the following questions.

How can one distinguish the accessory pigments from the principal pigment?

Chloroplast is a double-layered membrane, revealing its outer and inner membranes. Each thylakoid disk, or thylakoid membrane, is arranged in a stack known as granum (plural is grana). Grana are linked together by stromal lamellae, which are extensions that run from one granum to another through the stroma, and into another. The surrounding environment containing dissolved substances and copies of the chloroplast genome, that fills the space is the stroma. To clarify, chloroplasts have their own DNA that replicates independently.

1. What could be the effect of stressful conditions such as drought and high temperature on chloroplasts of a plant?
2. How do carotenoids protect the cell from harmful oxidative molecules?
3. How are pigments important to photosynthetic cells?

Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:

Chloroplast is a double-layered membrane, revealing its outer and inner membranes. Each thylakoid disk, or thylakoid membrane, is arranged in a stack known as granum (plural is grana). Grana are linked together by stromal lamellae, which are extensions that run from one granum to another through the stroma, and into another. The surrounding environment containing dissolved substances and copies of the chloroplast genome, that fills the space is the stroma. To clarify, chloroplasts have their own DNA that replicates independently.

Green plants are green due to the presence of a pigment called chlorophyll. Chlorophyll molecules are found in chloroplasts.

Light is made up of photons with a wavelength and a frequency (though only the wavelength is indicated in this image). [The wavelength of light is represented by the Greek letter lambda (λ); it is equal to the speed (v) of a wave in a medium of propagation divided by its frequency (f): $\lambda = v/f$. Wavelength is the distance between two consecutive crests (high points) or troughs / troughs (low points). We learned that waves carry energy.

Activity

- Determine the possible consequences should the following events take place.
1. A farmer accidentally treated his plant with a substance that degrades chlorophyll.
 2. Chlorophyll degradation fails to occur in preparation for winter.
 3. The chloroplast gene that synthesizes chlorophyll a becomes mutated.
 4. Plants that normally produce xanthophylls and carotene suddenly failed to synthesize them.
 5. Red algae suddenly needed to rely solely on its chlorophyll a.

	<p>Light is a type of electromagnetic energy, also known as radiation energy. It also has a particle-like characteristic. The longer the wavelength, the lower the frequency, and thus the lower the energy it carries. Going back to visible light, red light has a longer wavelength (700 nm) than violet light (400 nm). That is, red light has less energy than violet light.</p>	
<p>Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:</p>		<p>After the discussion the students will be asked to identify the term being described in each statement.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This biological process primarily takes place in the leaves, and it harnesses solar energy to produce an organic by-product. 2. These organic molecules selectively absorb light of specific wavelengths, and they are built into the thylakoid membranes of chloroplasts. 3. This pigment participates directly in light reactions which absorbs mainly blue, violet, and red colors of visible light.
<p align="center">MEETINGS 3 & 4</p>		<p align="center">FOR INTERVENTION</p>
<p>Specific Learning Outcomes:</p>	<p>The learners can</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify the essential cellular component that allows an organism to undergo photosynthesis; and, • describe the general equation of the food-making process. 	<p>Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.</p>
<p>Values To Be Integrated:</p>	<p>Open-mindedness and Excellence</p>	

<p>Motivation/ Introduction:</p>	<p>Do you still remember how to balance a chemical equation? How about identifying redox reactions?</p>	<p>The students will be asked to identify the term being described in each statement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This pigment absorbs mainly blue and orange light but does not participate directly in light reactions, but rather it conveys absorbed energy to chlorophyll for use in the photosynthetic pathway. • These pigments absorb mainly violet, blue, and green light, and they absorb and dissipate excess light energy that would otherwise damage chlorophyll. <p>*Administration of entry tickets (thru google forms)</p>
<p>Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:</p>	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Reduction</p> $6CO_2 + 6H_2O \rightarrow C_6H_{12}O_6 + 6O_2$ <p>Oxidation</p> </div> <p>A teacher-led discussion will be done such as Identifying the reactants, products, balancing the chemical equation, and which has been reduced or oxidized.</p>	<p>Inside our home, some of us love the kitchen the most. The kitchen is where most of the food are prepared. We all know that plants make their own food as well, but through the use of sunlight. How is this possible?</p>
<p>Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:</p>	<p>A google form quiz will be sent thru MS Teams.</p>	<p>I learned that _____; but I find _____ difficult to understand.</p>
<p align="center">MEETINGS 1 & 2</p>		<p align="center">FOR INTERVENTION</p>
<p>Specific Learning Outcomes:</p>	<p>The learners can</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • describe the processes of light-dependent reactions during photosynthesis; • describe the flow of electrons during light reactions; and, • discuss the processes that take place during the light-dependent reaction. 	<p>Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.</p>
<p>Values To Be Integrated:</p>	<p>Appreciation, Curiosity, and Resourcefulness</p>	

24-28 October 2022

<p>Motivation/Introduction:</p>	<p>Light is also considered a renewable source of energy that humans can benefit from. Sun is the primary source of light energy on our planet. Plants utilize all the colors of light except green when they photosynthesize. This reflection of light makes the color of plants green.</p> <p>How do light-dependent reactions occur during photosynthesis?</p>	<p>The photosynthetic pathway in autotrophs can be summarized by having carbon dioxide and water on the reactants side, and with light energy input, sugar (in the form of glucose) and oxygen molecules are produced.</p> <p>How do light-dependent reactions occur during photosynthesis?</p> <p>*Administration of entry tickets (thru google forms)</p>
<p>Instruction/Lesson Delivery:</p>		

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	<p>As the electrons continue to move in the electron transport chain, their energy is used to pump protons (H⁺) from the stroma across the membrane into the thylakoid lumen or space. The diffusion of H⁺ will rotate the ATP synthase, which drives the production of ATP molecules. Photosystem I functions as much as photosystem II does. The reactive chlorophyll molecule ejects electrons to an electron carrier molecule in the second electron transport chain in the thylakoid membrane. The boosted electrons in photosystem I are then replaced with electrons passing down from the first electron transport chain from photosystem II. The second electron transport chain passes the electrons to a molecule of NADP⁺, reducing it to NADPH.</p>	<p>Provide brief answers and explanations to the following questions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> How do light-dependent reactions produce ATP molecules? How do electrons move or flow during light-dependent reactions? How do electrons move via the cyclic pathway?
<p>Lesson Closure/Enrichment/Evaluation:</p>	<p>Identify the terms being described by the following statements.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> This process involves the breakdown or decomposition of a molecule by using light energy. This photosynthetic pathway involves two photosystems working together to synthesize ATP. This photosynthetic pathway involves only the photosystem I and the electron transport chain. 	<p>Write TRUE if the statement is correct and FALSE if otherwise.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Photosynthetic organisms are autotrophic organisms because they can produce their own food. Carbon dioxide in the air enters a leaf through small openings called stomata. As electrons move in the electron transport chain, their energy is used to pump protons (H⁺) across the membrane into the thylakoid space. The pigment in photosystem II absorbs the light to excite electrons, which will make it highly stable. Electrons from the noncyclic pathway immediately enter an electron transport chain in the thylakoid membrane.
MEETINGS 3 & 4		FOR INTERVENTION
<p>Specific Learning Outcomes:</p>	<p>The learners can</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> describe the different phases of the Calvin cycle; and, discuss the processes that take place during the light-independent reaction. 	<p>Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.</p>
<p>Values To Be Integrated:</p>	<p>Appreciation, Curiosity, and Resourcefulness</p>	
<p>Motivation/Introduction:</p>	<p>Have you ever wondered whether photosynthesis persists in the absence of light?</p>	<p>Compute for the following as they relate to light-dependent reactions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> How many oxygen molecules are formed from twelve water molecules? How many ATP molecules are formed from 48 ADP molecules? How many inorganic phosphate molecules are needed to produce 64 ATP molecules?

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	<p>Source: https://images.app.goo.gl/5HL47RuEgXyomKJ9</p>	<p>4. How many NADP + molecules are reduced to form 55 NADPH molecules?</p> <p>5. How many water molecules are needed to produce 24 oxygen molecules?</p>
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<p>Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:</p>	<p>How does the Calvin cycle occur during photosynthesis in plants?</p> <p>The light-independent reactions (Calvin cycle) are named so because energy from photons is not directly required for the chemical reactions to proceed. The light-independent reactions run on the ATP and NADPH molecules generated from light-dependent reactions. Carbon dioxide comes from the atmosphere via the stomata of leaves. The light-independent reactions ultimately produce glucose, a sugar, in the fluid-filled stroma of chloroplasts.</p> <p>How are the three main phases of the Calvin cycle different from each other?</p> <p>Answer the following questions by showing your solutions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How many CO₂ molecules are needed to produce six molecules of glucose? 2. How many ATP molecules are needed to synthesize four molecules of glucose? 3. How many NADPH molecules are required to produce six molecules of glucose? 	<p>Provide brief answers and explanations to the following questions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How does the Calvin Cycle function in the absence of light? 2. How does the carbon fixation phase produce 3-phosphoglycerate? 4. How are ATP and NADPH molecules used during the chemical reaction that involves 3-phosphoglycerate? 3. How does the third phase of the Calvin cycle regenerate RuBP? 5. How many molecules of ATP and NADPH were used during the Calvin cycle? 6. Differentiate the number of ATP used per carbon dioxide input from the number of NADPH used per carbon dioxide input.
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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. How many glucose molecules can be produced from 128 ATP molecules? 5. How many glucose can be produced from 108 NADPH molecules? 	
<p>Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:</p>	<p>A short quiz will be given.</p>	<p>Identify the terms being described by the following statements.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This phase of light-independent reactions includes the reaction between phosphoglycerate and NADPH. 2. This phase aims to resynthesize RuBP to prepare for succeeding carbon fixation reactions. 3. This molecule is produced after the reaction of PGA with ATP and NADPH.

<p>Unit: Topic: Content Standards: Performance Standards: Learning Competency/ies:</p>	<p>Energy Transformation Aerobic and Anaerobic Respiration The learner demonstrates understanding of ATP- ADP Cycle, Photosynthesis, and Respiration. The learner shall be able to prepare simple fermentation setup using common fruits to produce products like wine or vinegar via microorganism, and/or plan and recommend an appropriate dietary program to help people with nutrition-related problems improve their overall health. The learners distinguish major features of glycolysis, Krebs cycle, electron transport system, and chemiosmosis (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-8); explain the major features and sequence the chemical events of cellular respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-7); differentiate aerobic from anaerobic respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-6); compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-11); describe the major features and chemical events in photosynthesis and respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-2); describe the role of oxygen in respiration and describe pathways of electron flow in the absence of oxygen (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-10); and, explain the advantages and disadvantages of fermentation and aerobic respiration (STEM_BIO11/12-IIa-j-12).</p> <p>Materials: Powerpoint Presentation, Drawing Tab Resources: Quipper Online Content, Teacher-made discussion videos</p>
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WEEK 7		
MEETINGS 1 & 2		FOR INTERVENTION
<p>Specific Learning Outcomes:</p>	<p>The learners can</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • describe cellular respiration and the role of mitochondria in cellular respiration; • distinguish the important events that take place during cellular respiration. • determine the reactants and products of cellular respiration. 	<p>Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.</p> <p style="text-align: center; border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;">21 October- 11 November 2022</p>
<p>Values To Be Integrated:</p>	<p>Patience, Focus, and Academic Honesty</p>	
<p>Motivation/ Introduction</p>	<p>You may already have felt exhausted after accomplishing piles of work several times in your life. Have you ever wondered why you can do such things?</p>	<p>Compare and contrast aerobic and anaerobic respiration. Use a Venn diagram.</p>

Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	<p>Eating is one of the best things to do to regain our strength. It is an essential part of our lives because it is one of the ways that we can survive. To carry out numerous and varieties of activities, our cells need energy. The energy used by our body cells is obtained and processed from the food we eat.</p> <p>How can energy be produced from food? Where is it produced?</p> <p>Answer the following questions and explain your answers.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Why do larger organisms produce more energy compared to microscopic organisms? How does the amount of oxygen in the air affect the rate of respiration? Why do you think dieticians' advice people who want to lose weight to lessen their sugar intake? What activities can increase the rate of respiration? 	

Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation	<p>Identify the term described in each item.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> It is the process of producing energy without the presence of oxygen. An electron carrier that is involved in glycolysis One of the by-product of cellular respiration that is expelled through the lungs. 	<p>5. Why do humans take in more oxygen during exercise?</p> <p>Write TRUE, if the statement is correct, and false if otherwise. If false, explain the inaccuracy in the statement.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Organisms living in an oxygen-deprived environment are not capable of producing energy. The electron carriers of cellular respiration NAD⁺ and FADH₂. During exercise, the rate of cellular respiration decreases.
MEETINGS 3 & 4		FOR INTERVENTION
Specific Learning Outcomes:	<p>The learners can</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> trace the pathways of cellular respiration; explain the process of glycolysis; differentiate between the energy-investment and energy-harvesting phases; and, compute for the products of glycolysis. 	<p>Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.</p>
Values To Be Integrated:	<p>Patience, Focus, Academic Honesty</p>	
Motivation/ Introduction	<p>Do you have a sweet tooth? Is eating sweets a part of your daily routine?</p>	
Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	<p>Although overconsumption of sugar may cause diabetes, its importance to the many biological reactions that take place in our bodies should not be neglected. How do cells maximize the energy that can be liberated from sugar molecules?</p>	<p>Write true if the statement is correct, and false if otherwise. If false, explain the inaccuracy in the statement.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Organisms living in an oxygen-deprived environment are not capable of producing energy. The electron carriers of cellular respiration are NAD⁺ and FADH₂. During exercise, the rate of cellular respiration decreases.

How is glucose broken down to produce energy during glycolysis?

GLYCOLYSIS OR GLYCOLYTIC PATHWAY OR ALSO KNOWN AS [THE EMBDEN-MEYERHOF PATHWAY]

Glucose is converted into glucose-6 phosphate (G6P), a form of blood glucose, with the help of hexokinase. 1- Glucose is phosphorylated with the help of two ATP molecules. After glucose-6 phosphate is formed, it is converted by phosphoglucose isomerase into fructose-6-phosphate, which is then converted by phosphofruktokinase into fructose-1,6-bisphosphate. / or diphosphate.

Glycolysis

During glycolysis, each glucose molecule is broken down into two pyruvate molecules. The redox reactions also yield ATP molecules in the process.

A group discussion and game will be made via breakout rooms.

STEPS OF GLYCOLYSIS

CARBON STRUCTURE	MOLECULE NAME	ENZYME
6	glucose	hexokinase
6	glucose-6-phosphate	phosphoglucose isomerase
6	fructose-6-phosphate	phosphofruktokinase
6	fructose 1,6-bisphosphate	aldolase
3	DHAP	GAP dehydrogenase
3	1,3-bisphosphoglycerate	phosphoglycerate kinase
3	3-phosphoglycerate	phosphoglyceromutase
3	2-phosphoglycerate	enolase
3	phosphoenolpyruvate	pyruvate kinase
3	pyruvate	

Then, Aldolase is the enzyme that catalyzes the conversion of fructose 1-6-bisphosphate to DHAP or G3P. The G3P dehydrogenase then converts G3P to 1,3-bisphosphoglycerate, then to be converted into 3-phosphoglycerate (PGA) by the enzyme phosphoglycerate kinase, then to 2-phosphoglycerate by the phosphoglyceromutase. Enolase converts 2-phosphoglycerate into phosphoenolpyruvate then to become pyruvate by the pyruvate kinase.

Why does the energy-investment phase utilize ATP?

How much energy is produced during glycolysis?

Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation

A short quiz via google forms will be given.

Identify the term described in each item.

1. It is the process of producing energy without the presence of oxygen.
2. An electron carrier that is involved in glycolysis.
3. One of the by-products of cellular respiration that is expelled through the lungs.

WEEK 8

MEETINGS 1 & 2

FOR INTERVENTION

Specific Learning Outcomes:

- The learners can
- compare aerobic and anaerobic cellular processes; and
 - explain the mechanism of pyruvate oxidation.

Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.

21 October- 11 November 2022

Values To Be Integrated:

Appreciation and Critical Thinking

Motivation/ Introduction:

How are processes considered aerobic? Anaerobic?

Aerobic processes occur when oxygen is present, whereas anaerobic processes occur when oxygen is low, poor, insufficient, or absent in the cell.

Compare and contrast the energy-investment and energy-harvest phases of glycolysis by using the Venn diagram below.

		<p>*Administration of entry tickets (thru google forms)</p>
Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	<p>Assuming that oxygen is available, or that the oxygen level is sufficient, the pyruvate molecules will go through Pyruvate Oxidation first before proceeding to the Krebs Cycle. May transition pa. We expect the formation of Acetyl CoA from Pyruvate oxidation, which bridges the stages of Glycolysis and the Krebs Cycle.</p> <p>A carrier protein in the mitochondrial membrane transports pyruvate molecules from the cytosol to the mitochondrion. Please keep in mind that a CO₂ molecule is removed from the 3-C pyruvate, transforming it into a 2-C Acetyl. Then, a coenzyme A will join the process and attach to the acetyl group, forming Acetyl Coenzyme A or Acetyl-CoA.</p>	<p>Identify the term described in each of the following items.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> This is the number of ATP molecules used in the energy-investment phase. This molecule is produced at the end of glycolysis. This electron carrier is reduced in glycolysis. <p>To best represent the pyruvic acid oxidation, the illustration shows that one C-atom is removed from the 3-C pyruvic acid in the form of CO₂.</p>

	<p>Source: https://images-app.goo.gl/ug8M6TmZK9B9JUTA</p>	<p>The electron carrier, NAD⁺, is reduced to NADH + H ion as part of the process. The 2C pyruvate molecule then combines with coenzyme A to form acetyl coenzyme A, or Acetyl CoA, which enters the Krebs Cycle.</p> <p>Because we have two pyruvate molecules from the glycolysis of one molecule of glucose, we should also get two molecules of Acetyl CoA. As a result, these two Acetyl CoA molecules will be directed to the Krebs Cycle as the next metabolic pathway.</p>
Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation	<p>A short quiz via google forms will be given.</p>	<p>Making of learning log</p>
MEETINGS 3 & 4		FOR INTERVENTION
Specific Learning Outcomes:	<p>The learners can</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> explain the mechanism of the Krebs cycle; determine the products of oxidation of molecules in the Krebs cycle; and, compute for the products of the Krebs cycle. 	<p>Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.</p>
Values To Be Integrated:	<p>Appreciation and Critical Thinking</p>	
Motivation/ Introduction:	<p>Do you often connect the word "citrus" with its ability to boost our immune system? Is the word "sour" the first thing that pops into your thought balloon?</p>	<p>Share your thoughts about this image:</p>

The previous lesson discussed glycolysis as the first step during cellular respiration, which yields two pyruvate molecules. **What happens to these molecules?**

**Instruction/
Lesson
Delivery:**

Citric acid is responsible for the “sour” taste of citrus fruits. But beyond this, citric acid plays a crucial role in the production of energy.

What processes should pyruvate molecules go through to generate more energy?

The pyruvate molecules will now proceed to the Krebs Cycle after being oxidized into Acetyl CoA. As you can see, Acetyl CoA will now enter the cycle. The Krebs cycle will turn twice because there are two molecules of Acetyl-CoA produced from the pyruvate oxidation.

The acetyl CoA, a 2-C molecule) will bind with the already present or previously formed 4C molecule known as oxaloacetic acid. As a result of their binding, a 6C molecule called citrate or citric acid is formed.

Citrate or Citric Acid will be converted into Isocitric Acid as it is formed from the attachment of Acetyl-CoA and Oxaloacetate. Then, as a waste product, 1-C in the form of CO₂ will be removed from Isocitric acid to form α-Ketoglutarate, accompanied by the reduction of NAD⁺ to NADH.

Enzymes will break down this 5-C α-ketoglutaric acid to produce succinic acid (4C), forming NADH and ATP as well as

Citric acid is the first intermediate product of the cycle. Because of this, the Krebs Cycle is also known as the Citric Acid Cycle.

CO₂ as a waste product. The 4C molecule succinate rearranges to form fumarate, which is then converted into malic acid or malate, where NAD and FAD are reduced to NADH and FADH₂, respectively.

When the H⁺ ion is removed from Malic Acid, a 4-C oxaloacetic acid is formed, which will be used to combine or to bind with another Acetyl CoA to enter the cycle. As a result, at the end of the cycle, Oxaloacetate will always be regenerated or restored, indicating that it is a cycle. or the cycle begins again.

**Lesson
Closure/
Enrichment/
Evaluation**

Complete the table below:

Processes	Enzymes	Products
succinyl-CoA to succinate	1.	2.
oxidation of malate to oxaloacetate	3.	4.
oxidation of α-ketoglutarate to succinyl-CoA	5.	6.

A short quiz via google forms will be given.

Identify the terms described in each of the following statements.

- This electron carrier receives the hydrogen molecules from the oxidation of succinate.
- This process generally refers to the loss or release of electrons.
- This sulfur-containing compound that reacts with acetate during the transition reaction.

WEEK 9

MEETINGS 1 & 2

FOR INTERVENTION

**Specific
Learning
Outcomes:**

- The learners can
- explain the mechanisms of the electron transport chain and chemiosmosis; and
 - differentiate the protein complexes involved in the electron transport chain.

Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.

14-28 November 2022

**Values To Be
Integrated:**

Looking into details and Perseverance

**Motivation/
Introduction:**

You have probably experienced commuting on your way to school or to your house, and it must have become a part of your daily routine. All vehicles share one thing in common—they drive you to your destinations by harnessing the energy that can be generated from burning fuel.

Entry tickets will be given via google form.

**Instruction/
Lesson
Delivery:**

The role of vehicles in transporting passengers can be compared to a necessary process that our bodies need to perform—energy production. The role of electron carriers can be compared to that of utility vehicles, where the “passengers” are the electrons.

NADH and FADH₂ are oxidized to release electrons into the protein complexes. These electrons pass through protein complexes and cause the pumping of hydrogen ions from the matrix to the intermembrane space.

	<p>How can electron carriers help generate energy?</p> <p>How do protein complexes differ from each other?</p>	
<p>Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation</p>	<p>A short quiz via google forms will be given.</p>	<p>Identify the following terms described in each of the following items.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This region of the mitochondrion consists of embedded multiprotein complexes. 2. This mobile protein transfers electrons from complexes I and II to complex III. 3. This enzyme transports hydrogen ions from the intermembrane space to the matrix.
MEETINGS 3 & 4		
<p>Specific Learning Outcomes:</p>	<p>The learners can</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • determine the ATP yield of the electron transport chain and chemiosmosis; • calculate the total number of ATPs produced during the cellular respiration; and • distinguish photosynthesis and respiration in terms of their location in the cell where they take place, needed reactants, products, and chemical equation. 	<p>FOR INTERVENTION</p> <p>Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.</p>

<p>Values To Be Integrated:</p> <p>Motivation/ Introduction:</p>	<p>Looking into details and Perseverance</p> <p>How do hydrogen ions help in the production of ATP?</p>	<p>Determine the event that immediately follows in each of the following items.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubiquinol transfers the electrons to cytochrome b. 2. Hydrogen ions pass through the ATP synthase. 3. Flavin mononucleotide receives electrons from the oxidation of NADH. <p>*Entry tickets will be given via google form.</p>
<p>Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:</p>	<p>The electrons gathered from the previous pathways in the NADH and FADH₂ molecules will be used to generate more ATP molecules in the processes that take place in the electron transport chain. This pathway happens right in the mitochondrion's inner membrane, where oxygen pulls electrons from the electron carriers down the chain to a lower energy state. Thus, without O₂, aerobic respiration cannot proceed. This pathway generates 90 percent of the ATP in the body.</p>	

Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:	How do these two biochemical processes vary?	Students will accomplish their learning logs.																																					
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>In terms of:</th> <th>PHOTOSYNTHESIS</th> <th>CELLULAR RESPIRATION</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>FUNCTION</td> <td>Capture energy and store it in sugars.</td> <td>Release energy that was stored in sugars.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LOCATION</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>REACTANTS</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>PRODUCTS</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>EQUATION</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	In terms of:	PHOTOSYNTHESIS	CELLULAR RESPIRATION	FUNCTION	Capture energy and store it in sugars.	Release energy that was stored in sugars.	LOCATION			REACTANTS			PRODUCTS			EQUATION			<p>Let's Sum It Up! Quizzer</p> <p>The table below summarizes the net ATP yield for the whole aerobic respiration process.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Stages</th> <th>Net Direct Products</th> <th>Net ATP Equivalent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="2">Glycolysis</td> <td>2 ATP</td> <td>2 ATP</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 NADH</td> <td>6 ATP</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">Transition Reaction</td> <td>2 NADH</td> <td>6 ATP</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 ATP/GTP</td> <td>2 ATP</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="3">Krebs Cycle</td> <td>6 NADH</td> <td>18 ATP</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 FADH₂</td> <td>4 ATP</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Maximum ATP Yield: 38 ATP molecules</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Stages	Net Direct Products	Net ATP Equivalent	Glycolysis	2 ATP	2 ATP	2 NADH	6 ATP	Transition Reaction	2 NADH	6 ATP	2 ATP/GTP	2 ATP	Krebs Cycle	6 NADH	18 ATP	2 FADH ₂	4 ATP	
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WEEK 10

MEETINGS 1 & 2 **FOR INTERVENTION**

Specific Learning Outcomes:	The learners can <ul style="list-style-type: none"> explain the process of anaerobic respiration; determine the products of anaerobic respiration and fermentation; and, describe the process of fermentation. 	Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.
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14-28 November 2022

Values To Be Integrated:	Creativity and Responsiveness	
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Motivation/ Introduction	<p>Have you heard that wine and beer stored for a longer time taste better than those which were stored for a short period of time?</p>	
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Instruction/ Lesson Delivery:	<p>What do baking bread and winemaking have in common? Why are these processes related to each other?</p> <p>Let's Sum It Up! Quizzer</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Anaerobic Respiration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 40%;"> <p>Lactic Acid Fermentation</p> <p>Lactic acid is produced as a byproduct</p> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 40%;"> <p>Alcoholic Fermentation</p> <p>Alcohol is produced as a byproduct</p> </div> </div> <p>The two main types of anaerobic respiration</p> </div> <p>In the event when the supply of oxygen becomes insufficient, low, or absent, cells use anaerobic processes such as fermentation to obtain energy. The fermentative process takes place in the cytosol and is classified into two types: a) lactic acid fermentation and b) alcoholic fermentation.</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>FERMENTATION</p> <p>It is a reaction that eukaryotic and prokaryotic cells can use to obtain energy from food when oxygen levels are low / absent and/or insufficient.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occurs in a cell cytoplasm, not in mitochondria. Occurs when O₂ is NOT present (anaerobic) Called Lactic Acid fermentation in muscle cells (makes muscles tired) Called Alcoholic fermentation in yeast (produces ethanol) Nets only 2 ATP <p style="text-align: right;"><i>When and where does fermentation happen?</i></p> </div>	<p>Anaerobic respiration uses less energy (or produces less ATP) than aerobic respiration.</p> <p>Fermentation is an anaerobic process that breaks down pyruvic acid molecules without the use or expenditure of oxygen.</p> <p>As shown, here is a conceptual flow of glycolysis leading to the fermentation process.</p> <p>Below also are some examples of fermentation products.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>GLUCOSE</p> <p>↓ Glycolysis</p> <p>Pyruvic acid</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>↙ Anaerobic bacteria</p> <p>Lactic acid fermentation</p> <p>Aspergillus → Lactic acid (i.e. Soy Sauce)</p> <p>Lactobacillus → Lactic acid (i.e. Cheese & Yoghurt)</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>↘ Yeast</p> <p>Alcohol fermentation</p> <p>Saccharomyces → Ethanol + CO₂ (i.e. Beer)</p> <p>Ethanol + CO₂ (i.e. Wine)</p> <p>Ethanol + CO₂ (i.e. Bread)</p> </div> </div> </div>
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Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation:	A short quiz via google forms will be given.	<p>Identify the terms described in each of the following items.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> It is the process by which glucose is broken down to produce energy in the absence of oxygen. It is the type of bacteria that produces lactic acid as its only by-product. It is the product of decarboxylation of pyruvate.
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MEETINGS 3 & 4 **FOR INTERVENTION**

Specific Learning Outcomes: The learners can

- differentiate alcoholic from lactic acid fermentation;
- describe some applications of fermentation; and,
- list down some products and processes of fermentation, and their benefits and risks.

Teacher-made discussion video/s had been uploaded last week.

14-28 November 2022

Values To Be Integrated: Creativity and Responsiveness

Motivation/ Introduction: How do breads become fluffy and soft when they were made of a mixture of flour and water that results in thick, sticky, and compact consistency?

Entry ticket via google form will be given.

Instruction/ Lesson Delivery: Anaerobic respiration uses less energy (or produces less ATP) than aerobic respiration. Fermentation is an anaerobic process that breaks down pyruvic acid molecules without the use or expenditure of oxygen. As shown, here is a conceptual flow of glycolysis leading to the fermentation process. Below also are some examples of fermentation products.

Discussion thru learning teams will be done. Q and A about the processes shown by the figures below will be highlighted.

In lactic acid fermentation, pyruvate does not release a CO₂ molecule. The 3C molecule is usually converted into lactic acid in muscle cells. Muscles respire aerobically, but if you do a lot of work and other strenuous activities to maintain muscle contraction, lactic acid levels rise, causing fatigue or muscular pain. When this happens, you must take some time to rest and relax so that more oxygen can be delivered to your muscles to replace the lost or needed O₂. As a result, lactic acid decreases and is transported to your liver, where it will be oxidized to generate energy as lactic acid will be converted back into glucose.

In alcoholic fermentation, however, the pyruvic acid releases CO₂, and the remaining 2C molecule which is an alcohol is the final product. Ethanol is a type of 2-C alcohol.

Wine and beer are examples of alcoholic fermentation; additionally, the use of yeasts in the production of bread to cause the dough to rise is also an example of a fermentation product.

Lesson Closure/ Enrichment/ Evaluation: A short quiz via google forms will be given.

- Arrange the following events in alcoholic fermentation using letters A-E, with A being the first step and E being the last.**
- Alcohol dehydrogenase adds the hydride group from NADH to acetaldehyde.
 - The carboxyl group is removed from the pyruvate molecule.
 - A hydrogen ion is added to acetaldehyde.
 - Acetaldehyde is converted to ethanol.
 - Pyruvate is converted to acetaldehyde.

02-03 December 2022 **Second Quarterly Assessment**

Checked by:

MRS. CHRISTINE VEN ACUÑA
Science Department Chair

APPENDIX H

TABLE OF SPECIFICATIONS (TOS) of RBAT

Quarter: Second

Course: General Biology 1

Grade Level: 12

Competencies	No. of days taught	No. of Items	Knowledge	Processes	Item Allocation
[1] explain coupled reaction processes and describe the role of ATP in energy coupling and transfer	4	5	2	3	<i>K: 32, 35</i> <i>P: 10, 36, 44</i>
[2] describe the major features and chemical events in photosynthesis and respiration	7	9	5	4	<i>K: 03, 06, 08, 09, 26</i> <i>P: 02, 43, 49, 50</i>
[3] explain the importance of chlorophyll and other pigments	2	3	2	1	<i>K: 22, 23</i> <i>P: 15</i>
[4] describe the patterns of electron flow through light reaction events	4	5	3	2	<i>K: 13, 14, 24</i> <i>P: 01, 07</i>
[5] describe the significant events of the Calvin cycle	2.5	3	0	3	<i>K:</i> <i>P: 16, 17, 48</i>
[6] differentiate aerobic from anaerobic respiration	2.5	3	2	1	<i>K: 11, 37</i> <i>P: 47</i>
[7] explain the major features and sequence the chemical events of cellular respiration	4	5	4	1	<i>K: 05, 20, 21, 27</i> <i>P: 40</i>
[8] distinguish major features of glycolysis, Krebs cycle, electron transport system, and chemiosmosis	5	6	5	1	<i>K: 12, 29, 30, 31, 33</i> <i>P: 19</i>
[9] describe reactions that produce and consume ATP	2	3	3	0	<i>K: 25, 34, 46</i> <i>P:</i>

[10] describe the role of oxygen in respiration and describe pathways of electron flow in the absence of oxygen	2	2	1	1	K: 45 P: 04
[11] compute the number of ATPs needed or gained in photosynthesis and respiration	2	2	1	1	K: 28 P: 41
[12] explain the advantages and disadvantages of fermentation and aerobic respiration	3	4	2	2	K: 18, 42 P: 38, 39
TOTAL	40	50	30	20	

APPENDIX I

RESEARCHER-VALIDATED BIOLOGY ACHIEVEMENT TEST (RBAT)

GENERAL DIRECTIONS:

This 50-item test is prepared to measure your conceptual understanding about the topics covered during the second quarter for the School Year 2022-2023. From among the options that follow each question, choose the correct answer. Answer the best you can all the items within sixty (60) minutes. You may now begin.

- 01 What are the products of the light-dependent reaction in this figure? (C#4-P)

- chloroplasts and light
- oxygen and energy carriers**
- proteins and lipids
- water and sugars

- 02 Which of the following statements about Photosynthesis is not true? (C#2-P)
Photosynthesis has three different stages/ phases.

Light-dependent stage requires photons.
 Light-independent reaction can happen in the absence or presence of light.
 The light-independent reaction or Calvin Cycle takes carbon dioxide and fixes it in three-carbon molecules which will eventually be generated into glucose.

- 03 What term describes the process of water removal from the plant's body as depicted in the figure below? (C#2-K)
 Source: <https://images.app.goo.gl/GjBvRZ78hsWWrm9C9>

- evaporation
 - transformation
 - respiration
 - transpiration**
- 04 Photosynthesis provides oxygen. What is the main function of oxygen in aerobic respiration? (C#10-P)

As it moves down the respiratory chain, it produces energy in the form of ATP.
It acts as an acceptor of electrons and hydrogen, resulting in the formation of water.
 CO₂ is created when oxygen and carbon join together.
 Pyruvate is made when pyruvate and lactate combine.

- 05 What are the reactants of the cellular respiration? (C#7-K)
 chlorophyll and light
carbohydrates and oxygen
 carbon dioxide and water
 high-energy electrons and air

- 06 Which internal part of the leaf shown in the figure below is made up of cells packed together, which cells are arranged in such a way for an effective light absorption? (C#2-K)
 Source: <https://images.app.goo.gl/NUfozSZJgJpmhfFZ8>

palisade mesophyll spongy mesophyll epidermis cuticle

- 07 What is the source of oxygen produced from photosynthesis? (C#4-P)
 hydrogen **water** carbon dioxide glucose
- 08 Where are most stomata located in the leaf? (C#2-K)
 in the blade in the stalk above the leaf **underside of the leaf**
- 09 What are these structures in the figure below that regulate the pores where CO₂ enters and O₂ exit? (C#2-K)
 Source: <https://images.app.goo.gl/maV7XjE2GpYoBL7r8>

guard cell chloroplast lenticel stomata

- 10 ADP can be converted to ATP by adding a phosphate group. ADP and a phosphate group require energy to form an ATP molecule. (C#1-P)
Both statements are true.
 Both statements are false.
 The first sentence is true. The second sentence is false.
 The first sentence is false. The second sentence is true.
- 11 Which of the following organisms does not photosynthesize? (C#6-K)
animals plants bacteria protists
- 12 Which stage of cellular respiration is also referred to as the Citric Acid Cycle? (C#8-K)
 Calvin Cycle Light-independent reaction **Krebs Cycle** ATP-ADP Cycle

- 13 What is TRUE about the Photosystems? (C#4-K)
 They are composed of pigments that gather photons that is used to excite electrons that will pass thru the Citric Acid Cycle.
Photosystems were named in the order of which they were discovered, which is opposite of how electrons flow through them.
 PSII has an absorption peak of 700 nm so its reaction center is P700. PS I has an absorption peak of 680 nm and its reaction center is P680.
 These are densely packed protein and enzyme clusters in the stroma of the chloroplast.
- 14 The light reaction occurs in which part of the chloroplast? (C#4-K)
 Cristae matrix stroma **thylakoid**
- 15 Why do the leaves of the rice plant, *Oryza sativa* appear green? (C#3-P)
 Because its chlorophyll absorbs both blue and green light.
 Because its chlorophyll reflects both blue and green light.
 Because its chlorophyll absorbs green light.
Because its chlorophyll reflects green light.
- 16 What is NOT true about the light-dependent reaction? (C#5-P)
 It involves RuBP.
It involves Oxaloacetate.
 It happens in day and night.
 It utilizes carbon dioxide to produce sugar.
- 17 What does not happen during the Calvin Cycle? (C#5-P)
 A Carbon from CO₂ is added to the 5-C RuBP, creating an unstable 6-C sugar.
Water is split into hydrogen and oxygen.
 The 5-C RuBP is regenerated.
 There are two 3-C sugar molecules that are used in the metabolic cycle.
- 18 Where in the cell does fermentation happen? (C#12-K)
Cytoplasm
 Nucleus
 Mitochondrion
 Chloroplast
- 19 Which of the following events does not take place in the formation of Acetyl-CoA? (C#8-P)
 Pyruvate is oxidized.
 A CO₂ is removed from pyruvate – making a 2-C compound.
 Coenzyme A is attached to the acetyl group.
NADH is reduced to NAD⁺.
- 20 Which of the following concepts in respiration is not true? (C#7-K)
Cellular respiration includes the processes of glycolysis, citric acid cycle and electron transport chain that most often all take place in the cytosol of the cell.
 NADH and FADH₂ are carrier molecules that are used in the electron transport chain to generate ATP.
 Glycolysis takes place in the cytosol and does not require the presence of oxygen.
 Glycolysis breaks down glucose into pyruvates that undergo oxidation to form acetyl -CoA.
- 21 What does not happen during glycolysis? (C#7-K)
 Glucose split into two molecules of Pyruvate.
 NAD⁺ has been reduced to NADH.
 There is a net gain of 2 ATP molecules.
Oxygen participates in the reaction.
- 22 Which pigment is most crucial in photosynthesis? (C#3-K)
 xanthophyll
 carotenoid
chlorophyll a
 chlorophyll b

- 23 What wavelengths do chlorophyll absorb the most? (C#3-K)
 blue and green
blue and red
 yellow and green
 yellow and orange
- 24 Where do the light-independent reactions occur? (C#4-K)
 thylakoid
 granum
stroma
 intermembrane space
- 25 Which ion concentrations across from intermembrane space to the matrix causes ATP synthase to spin and make ATP? (C#9-K)
hydrogen sodium potassium oxygen water
- 26 Which part of the plant undergoes the most photosynthesis? (C#2-K)
 stems
 roots
leaves
 flowers
- 27 What is the order of the four stages of aerobic cellular respiration? (C#7-K)
 glycolysis, fermentation, Krebs cycle
 glycolysis, Krebs cycle, light dependent reaction, light independent reaction
glycolysis, Krebs cycle, electron transport system
 glycolysis, electron transport system, Krebs cycle
- 28 What is the net amount of ATP generated during glycolysis? (C#11-K)
 2 6 34 38
- 29 Which organelle of the cell generates ATP? (C#8-K)
 chloroplast golgi body **mitochondrion** nucleus
- 30 In which stage of cellular respiration is glucose converted to pyruvate? (C#8-K)
 Fermentation **glycolysis** Krebs cycle Electron Transport Chain
- 31 Which compound enters the Krebs Cycle? (C#8-K)

Source: <https://images.app.goo.gl/tV8wKxijdDbuSdbG6>

Carbon dioxide **Acetyl-CoA** Pyruvic Acid Oxaloacetate

- 32 What molecule acts as the short-term energy source of the cell? (C#1-K)
ATP NADP+ NAD+ FAD+

- 33 What are the first products of glucose breakdown during respiration? (C#8-K)
 lactic acid
 ethanol
pyruvic acid
 ADP
- 34 Which of the following molecules aids in the transport of hydrogen atoms to the electron transport system during aerobic cellular respiration? (C#9-K)
 carbon dioxide
 water
 FADH₂
NADH
- 35 What is the connection between ADP and ATP? (C#1-K)
 They are identical except for the fact that ADP has more energy.
 ADP has one more phosphate group than ATP and more stored energy.
 Unlike ATP, ADP contains the sugar ribose.
ATP has one more phosphate group and much more stored energy.
- 36 Where is the chemical energy in ATP stored? (C#1-P)
 adenine derivatives **bonds between phosphate groups** adenosine molecule ribose sugar
- 37 Which part of the cell does Glycolysis take place? (C#6-K)
cytosol mitochondrial matrix inner membrane of mitochondrion outer membrane of mitochondrion
- 38 Which of the following conditions could cause some of your body's cells to produce lactic acid? (C#12-P)
 after extended periods of sleep
 following a high-sugar meal
 following a period of hunger
following extended periods of exercise
- 39 Which concept about the fermentative process is true? (C#12-P)
 Alcohol is formed in muscles causing fatigue and pain.
 Pyruvic acid gives up oxygen during alcoholic fermentation.
Wine, bread, and beer are some products of fermentation.
 It releases more energy (or more ATP) than the oxidative phosphorylation via electron transport chain.
- 40 What is the correct chemical equation for cellular respiration? (C#7-P)
 Water + carbon dioxide → sugar + oxygen + ATP
sugar + oxygen → water + carbon dioxide + ATP
 sugar + water → carbon dioxide + oxygen + ATP
 sugar + carbon dioxide → water + oxygen + ATP
- 41 How many ATPs can be produced from 10 NADH molecules? (C#11-P)
 10 **25** 12 20
- 42 What reaction that eukaryotic and prokaryotic cells can use to obtain energy from food when oxygen levels are low/ insufficient/ or absent? (C#12-K)
 Glycolysis Krebs Cycle Oxidative Phosphorylation **Fermentation**
- 43 Which of the following statements about photosynthesis is FALSE? (C#2-P)
Photosynthetic rates in animals and plants are the same.
 The carbon from dioxide carbon is used to make sugar.
 Light energy is converted by plants to chemical energy.
 As a byproduct, oxygen is released.

Zoom

- 44 What is TRUE about Catabolism? (C#1-P)
 It uses simple molecules within the organism to create more complex and specialized compounds.
 It creates a product from a series of components.
 It makes polymers from the monomers.
It releases energy for the body cells to use.

- 45 Which of the following statements about cellular respiration is NOT TRUE? (C#10-K)

The reactants are glucose and oxygen, and the products are carbon dioxide, water, and ATP
 Glucose and oxygen are required to run this process, as a result carbon dioxide and water are waste, and ATP is an energy produced.
 This process is aerobic resulting to carbon dioxide and water as waste and ATP its end-product.
This is an aerobic respiration that gives off six molecules of oxygen gas and gains ATP as energy.

- 46 What high-energy bonds connect the phosphate groups of the ATP? (C#9-K)
 Phosphodiester bond **Phosphoanhydride bond** Glycosidic linkage Ether linkage

- 47 Which is NOT the product of the two types of fermentation? (C#6-P)

Alcohol in wine
Formation of acetyl-CoA
 Lactic acid in muscle cells
 Rising of bread dough during baking

- 48 How many molecules of CO₂ are produced from the oxidation of one glucose molecule? (C#5-P)
 one two three **six**

- 49 How would the parts of a plant's physiological processes be affected if its leaves developed so its vascular tissue only includes xylem? (C#2-P)
 Because chloroplasts are found in most parts of the plant, the plant's cells would function normally without the need for sugars from the leaves.
 Photosynthesis would be halted because the carbon dioxide required for photosynthesis would not be absorbed and shuttled to the leaf cells.
The sugar generated during photosynthesis in the leaf cells would not be likely to access the rest of the plant, and the plant's other cells' cellular respiration would cease.
 The ground tissues of the plant would still be capable of carrying water and nutrients from the roots to the rest of the plant.

- 50 What best describes a chloroplast? (C#2-P)
 an external membrane with stomata on the inside
 grana are composed of stroma membrane - enclosed.
grana consisting of thylakoid discs occupied by fluid stroma and an outer membrane
 stomata with thylakoid discs made of grana, stroma, and a membrane within it .

END OF THE TEST

APPENDIX J

ONLINE CLASSROOM OBSERVATION FORM (For Conventional Group)

Teacher: _____ Learning Area: _____

Date and Time of Observation: _____ Class: _____

Rating Scale:

- 4- Performance of this indicator is excellently done.
- 3- Performance of this indicator is satisfactorily done.
- 2- Performance of this indicator is fairly done.
- 1- Performance of this indicator is poorly done.
- 0- Performance of this indicator is not observed at all.

INDICATORS (Based on Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction)

1	Hooking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher employs an activity to create a psychological state in each student that hopes to learn what the teacher intends to teach. This creates a connection/ rapport with the students and a sense of direction that is established throughout the session. 	4	3	2	1	0
2	Informing the Learning Targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher communicates the learning competency and learning objectives for the meeting. This is intended to help students in setting their own goals and managing their focus to what information and skills they are expected to learn and perform. 	4	3	2	1	0
3	Activating Prior Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher connects the past and present topics. This clearly expresses the students' level of preparedness by enabling them to make conceptual connections and establish prerequisite knowledge (and skills) for learning the next competency/content. 	4	3	2	1	0
4	Presenting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher implements appropriate instructional methods in discussing the learning materials/ resources. This allows students achieve the learning targets thru active and engaging activities/ tasks provided. 	4	3	2	1	0
5	Scaffolding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher provides specific support to students, such as unlocking the difficulties, modeling, chunking the topics, slowing down the process, describing thru logic and mind-mapping as they develop understanding of the new concept or skill. This entails management of online class environment and materials to prepare students for the transfer of understanding. 	4	3	2	1	0

6	Applying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher conducts drills and practice. This provokes critical thinking and questioning of students and improves their understanding and skills in sharing their ideas, clarifying some concepts, and proposing solutions to real-life problems. 	4	3	2	1	0
7	Feedbacking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher provides students with genuine feedback or a concept and practical check considering their performance in relation to the learning targets. This is intended to point out areas where students can improve or become better at completing the tasks/activities assigned to them. 	4	3	2	1	0
8	Assessing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher monitors and measures students' learning and success by carrying out various forms of assessments. This encourages students to deepen their understanding and become more engaged in the learning process as they receive feedback on how they fare and perform in the class. 	4	3	2	1	0
9	Generalizing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher wraps up the topic for the meeting and assigns relevant homework. This helps students to validate their knowledge and retain what they have learned, as well as encourages them to apply their gained concepts in a variety of situations. 	4	3	2	1	0

COMMENTS:

Observed by:

ONLINE CLASSROOM OBSERVATION FORM (For Intervention Group)

Teacher: _____ Learning Area: _____

Date and Time of Observation: _____ Class: _____

Rating Scale:

- 4- Performance of this indicator is excellently done.
- 3- Performance of this indicator is satisfactorily done.
- 2- Performance of this indicator is fairly done.
- 1- Performance of this indicator is poorly done.
- 0- Performance of this indicator is not observed at all.

INDICATORS (Based on Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction)

1	<p>Hooking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher employs an activity to create a psychological state in each student that hopes to learn what the teacher intends to teach. This creates a connection/ rapport with the students and a sense of direction that is established throughout the session. 	4	3	2	1	0
2	<p>Informing the Learning Targets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher communicates the learning competency and learning objectives for the meeting thru an entry ticket. This is to assess what students already know after viewing the pre-deployed discussion videos. 	4	3	2	1	0
3	<p>Activating Prior Knowledge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher establishes a link between previous and ongoing activities. This overviews the summary of the insights from the entry ticket conducted as self-assessment. This shows the students' level of preparedness and establishes the initial information needed to accomplish the task for the meeting. 	4	3	2	1	0
4	<p>Presenting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher implements appropriate instructional methods to process the results of the self-assessment and to deepen the discussion of the concepts. This determines whether students can go on to perform and apply their understanding based on the learning objectives. 	4	3	2	1	0
5	<p>Scaffolding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The teacher provides specific support to students, such as unlocking the difficulties, modeling, chunking the topics, slowing down the process, describing thru logic and mind-mapping as they develop understanding of the new concept or skill. This is done in smaller groups (breakout rooms) with process-based, guided activity to prepare students for the transfer of understanding. 	4	3	2	1	0

6

Applying

- The teacher conducts drills and practice. This provokes critical thinking and questioning of students and improves their understanding and skills in sharing their ideas, clarifying some concepts, and proposing solutions 4 3 2 1 0 to real-life problems.

7

Feedbacking

- The teacher provides students with genuine feedback or a concept and practical check considering their performance in relation to the learning targets. This is intended to point out areas where students can improve or become better at completing the tasks/activities assigned to them.

4 3 2 1 0

8

Assessing

- The teacher monitors and measures students' learning and success by carrying out various forms of assessments. This encourages students to deepen their understanding and become more engaged in the learning

process as they receive feedback on how they fare and perform in the class.

2

4 3
1 0

9

Generalizing

- The teacher wraps up the topic for the meeting and directs students to accomplish their learning logs. This helps students to validate their knowledge and retain what they have learned by participating in the discussion forum, and it also encourages them to apply their gained concepts in a variety of situations.

4 3 2 1 0

COMMENTS:

Observed by:

APPENDIX K

DISCUSSION VIDEO VALIDATION TOOL (FOR SCIENCE TEACHERS ONLY)

Adopted from Acedo, E., & Robles, A. C. M. O. (2019). Development and Validation of Educational Video Tutorials for 21st Century Secondary Learners. Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 2(2), 42-49.

Please rate the teacher-made discussion videos in terms of the following criteria and indicators on a scale of **1 (least extent) to 5 (very high extent)**:

Least Extent **1** **2** **3** **4** **5 Very High Extent**

A. Acceptability ($\alpha = .870$)

1. The contents of the video are suitable since they provide systematic explanations which are aligned in the curriculum guide.
2. The explanations in the video tutorial are acceptable and suitable to students' level of understanding as it enhances students' 21st-century skills.
3. The concepts in the video tutorials are appropriately and accurately explained. They are free from grammatical errors.
4. The overall video tutorial captures the main objective and is acceptable to students with different learning styles.
5. Overall, the video tutorial is a creative approach that allows the viewer to understand vital concepts worth remembering.

B. Relevance ($\alpha = .716$)

1. The contents of the video are essential to students since they provide relevant discussions on the subject matter.
2. The video can be considered as an essential tool to achieve better retention of students' learning.

3. The video is relevant because it reinforces or supplements concepts necessary for mastery.
4. The overall discussion in the video tutorial provides a substantial explanation and gives an explicit discussion of the subject matter.
5. In general, the objective/s of the video tutorial is/are relevant and aligned with the skills and competencies in the curriculum guide.

C. Usability ($\alpha = .791$)

1. The video is an innovative material used to reinforce students' learning.
2. The video tutorial may be used to maximize students' learning, beneficial in enhancing their 21st-century skills.
3. The content of the video may be used as a tool in helping the viewers understand a series of concepts worth remembering.
4. The message of the video is comprehensive and is useful to enhance students' learning.
5. The video tutorial is suitable for students' learning styles and preferences. Hence, it is helpful to both students and teachers.

D. Appropriateness ($\alpha = .838$)

1. The contents of the video will help students understand their current lesson better.
2. The video is appropriate to aid the students in developing their critical thinking skills.
3. The video presented is a useful supplementary material for reinforcement and application of new learning.
4. The overall quality of the video presented is effective and free from grammatical errors.
5. The video is considered valid, effective, relevant, and useful to both students and teachers.

APPENDIX L

SELF-EFFICACY INSTRUMENT

The purpose of this study is to investigate how the use of inverted learning approach improves students' conceptual understanding and academic self-efficacy in learning Biology in an online learning environment.

Self-Efficacy Questionnaire for Online Learning (SeQoL)

Scale Development (30 items):

Shen, D., Cho, M. H., Tsai, C. L., & Marra, R. (2013). Unpacking online learning experiences: Online learning self-efficacy and learning satisfaction. The Internet and Higher Education, 19, 10-17.

Validity and Reliability Information (25 items):

Tsai, C. L., Cho, M. H., Marra, R., & Shen, D. (2020). The Self-Efficacy Questionnaire for Online Learning (SeQoL). Distance Education, 41(4), 472-489.

CFI = .90, SRMR = .06, RMSEA = .05

This inquires about your self-belief in learning the course General Biology remotely. It focuses on five (5) factors identified by Tsai, Cho, Marra, and Shen (2020) & Shen, Cho, Tsai, and Marra (2013):

On a scale of 0 (cannot do at all) to 10 (highly confident can do), how confident are you in completing the following tasks in the online/remote Biology course?

0 Cannot do at all	1	2	3	4	5 Moderately confident can do	6	7	8	9	10 Highly confident can do
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Domain 1: Self-efficacy to complete an online course/ subject ($\alpha = 0.914$)

1. Willing to face challenges
2. Create a plan to complete the given assignments
3. Willingly adapt my learning styles to meet course expectations
4. Understand complex concepts
5. Keep up with course schedule
6. Evaluate assignments according to the criteria provided by the instructor

7. Complete an online course with a good grade

Domain 2: Self-efficacy to interact socially with classmates ($\alpha = 0.921$)

8. Pay attention to other students' social actions

9. Initiate social interaction with classmates

10. Apply different social interaction skills depending on situations

11. Develop friendship with my classmates

Domain 3: Self-efficacy to handle tools in a CMS ($\alpha = 0.819$)

12. Send email to others with or without attached files

13. Reply to others' messages in a discussion board

14. Post a new message in a discussion board

Domain 4: Self-efficacy to interact with instructors in an online course ($\alpha = 0.925$)

15. Clearly ask my questions to instructor

16. Seek help from instructor when needed

17. Timely inform the instructor when unexpected situations arise

18. Initiate discussions with the instructor

19. Express my opinions to instructor respectfully

Domain 5: Self-efficacy to interact with classmates for academic purposes ($\alpha = 0.911$)

20. Actively participate in online discussions

21. Effectively communicate with my classmates

22. Respond to other students in a timely manner

23. Request help from others when needed

24. Express my opinions to other students respectfully

25. Provide help to other students when assistance is needed

APPENDIX M

FEEDBACK ON THE USE OF INVERTED LEARNING APPROACH

In the paper of MacKinnon (2015), the Flipped Learning Network (FLN) describes inverted (flipped) learning as an approach in which lecture discussion or expository instruction shifts from the group learning space to the individual learning space, allowing for a more dynamic, interactive, and engaging learning environment (Chang & Hwang, 2018). This approach generally aims to create more in-class time for activities that enhance student learning, while moving some content delivery outside the classroom using short videos or doing practical works through student and teacher discussion/peer collaboration (Barral et al, 2018; González-Gómez, Jeong, & Rodríguez, 2016).

This asks for your feedback on the approach and recommendations for its application and/or adoption in the teaching-learning process. Remember, there are no right, or wrong answers here simply give the most honest answer you can. First part is a 20-item survey to rate from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree), and the second part contains open-ended questions.

Strongly Disagree	1	2	3	4	Strongly Agree
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Using the Inverted Learning Approach, students ...

BEFORE CLASS

1. watch the previously deployed discussion videos.
2. connect with their teachers and class mates.
3. improve their relationship with teachers and class mates.
4. handle well their time and self-pace their learning.
5. are presented with expected course competencies ahead of schedule.

DURING CLASS

6. maximize in-class time for learning.
7. are more involved than in a traditional classroom approach.
8. participate in more collaborative activities.

9. are provided with more learning opportunities.
10. are given more attention for assessment/ monitoring of performance
11. are provided with differentiated instruction and activities.
12. learn the concepts and skills expected of them.
13. are given time to express and respond freely to the activities.
14. are welcome to ask for clarifications.
15. receive honest feedback on their work/progress.

AFTER CLASS

16. rewatch the videos for remediation/ review.
17. participate in self-evaluation exercises.
18. consider the approach to be an effective approach in teaching Biology.
19. look forward to studying next/ more topics.
20. become more confident doing the post-class activities/ tasks.

OPEN-ENDED GUIDE QUESTIONS

- A. How did the inverted learning approach affect the following aspects in your learning experience? In terms of:
 - a. your teacher's preparation?
 - b. your learning style and level of involvement?
 - c. your classmates' reactions/participation?
 - d. instruction and tasks?
 - e. assessment and evaluation?
- B. Based on your observations, provide at least three (3) specific advantages and three (3) disadvantages of the inverted learning approach.
- C. What other insights and thoughts maybe you want to suggest for the improvement of the inverted learning approach/intervention?

APPENDIX N

FGD AND INTERVIEW QUESTION GUIDE

1. How did you find the discussion videos presented before the synchronous classes?
2. What do you think about the activities and how they are done in online meeting?
3. How has using the inverted learning been for you? How has it affected you in terms of your:
 - a. learning style?
 - b. study time?
 - c. academic/ class performance?
 - d. attitude or behavior towards studies/ finishing a task?
 - e. teacher's preparation and instruction?
 - f. class engagement or involvement?
 - g. interaction with classmates?
 - h. assessment of learning?
4. What are specific advantages of inverted learning approach? specific disadvantages? Why.
5. What specific recommendations you suggest for the improvement of the inverted learning approach/intervention? In STEM (other courses if any)
6. Will you recommend this approach for use? In Biology? In other subjects? Specify. Why?
7. What is your anticipated performance grade for this class this quarter?

APPENDIX O

DATA EXTRACTS FROM FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS AND INTERVIEWS

A. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>FGD-F-1 mahirap sya... baka masanay din ako na ganito sa Bio sa mga gagawin</i>	It is challenging, but I believe I will be used to this approach.	Challenging Novel	Reflection Innovation (Content and Style)	Competence Interaction
<i>F- challenging na sya..</i>	It is hard.	Hard	Reflection	Competence
<i>F- mahirap po</i>	It is challenging.	Challenging	Reflection	Competence
<i>F- Bio is interesting; grabe nya kahirap; minsan nag ooverthink ako if makaya ko ba ito</i>	Biology is interesting; however it is a difficult learning area.	Interesting	Reflection	Competence
<i>M- mahirap po pero intersting po</i>	Hard subject but interesting to learn about.	Challenging	Reflection	Competence
<i>F- interesting man pero mahirap; pero ma gets man sir pag intindihin lang yun mga sinasabi</i>	Challenging but interesting subject; the concepts can be learned when you focus really.	Increased focus	Self-Study	Independence
<i>F- parang mabalance ko ung time ko kasi nasa bahay ako</i>	I can make use of my time wisely at home.	Time management	Self-Accountability	Independence

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>F- mas madali sa akin yung discussion vid kasi kasadalasan po mahiya po ako mag tanong, at pwede ko maulit ulitin ung video, if meron akong ndi maintainidhan, pwede ako mag research. If wala na talga sa internet, mas confident po akong mgatnong po thru PM. Tapos mas madali saakin, kasi nagsusulat ako ng reviewer.</i>	I am used to the approach. As a shy type of a person, most often I research over the internet the questions I have in mind about the concepts in the discussion videos presented. If I am not satisfied with what I researched, I directly message the teacher. Also this allows me to put down my thoughts and make reviewers.	Helpful for study and review	Self-Accountability	Independence
<i>F- mas nag recitation na ako, mas confident na ako</i>	I am much confident to recite	Confidence to participate in class	Inquiry	Competence
<i>F- ndi need mag rush, lahat ng oras namin ay hawak namin</i>	No need to rush in since we self-pace our activities	Self-pacing	Self-Pacing	Independence
<i>F- convenience po. Maayos namin masyado ang dapat gawin.</i>	It is convenient. We can do well our activities.	Convenience and effectiveness	Self-Accountability	Independence

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>M- anytime pwede ireview ung videos sa mga students na ndi nakapasok sa klase nila</i>	Students can review or rewatch the videos; especially those who could not attend the online meetings or absent.	Help for those who cannot attend to class	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction
<i>M- in physics and bio</i>	Can be done in Physics and Biology subjects	Recommended for use in other learning areas	Technology	Learning Environment
<i>F- DV since pwede sya mabalik balikan at mag take down notes; no need to rush sa pag take down notes</i>	No need to rush in since we can replay and rewatch the discussion videos; we can take down notes too.	Convenience when studying/ reviewing	Self-Accountability	Independence
<i>F- ndi lang sa physics and bio, sa ibang subjects... or pwedeng recorded class meeting</i>	Other courses or learning areas can also do discussion videos or recorded meetings.	Recommended for use in other learning areas	Self-Accountability	Independence
<i>F- makaincrease ng performance if ever may parts na ndi maintindihan</i>	Conceptual understanding (academic performance) may be increased.	Increased performance	Reflection	Competence
<i>M- mahirap sya pero masaya po.</i>	It is challenging and fun.	Challenging and Fun	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>F- sakin po nabago nya ako kasi naging mas confident ako sa recitations; mas nahelp nya ako mag prepare sa face to face</i>	I become more confident during recitations; a form of help in preparing for the face-to-face sessions.	Develop confidence	Flexibility	Learning Environment
<i>F- ..mahirap sya generally pero pagfocus ka talaga sa thinking na gusto mo maintindihan yun gi-lesson, masaya po sir..parang ano sya maka overwhelm if naintindihan mo yung lesson.</i>	Hard but when you focus, you will grab the concept really.	Increased performance	Self-Accountability	Independence
<i>F- mahirap po; interesting po sya na subject.</i>	Hard but interesting subject	Challenging and interesting	Reflection	Competence
<i>M- honestly sir, minsan pag ndi ako makahabol sir, balik balikan ko lang yung vids, para maintindihan ko</i>	Sometimes I can not cope, but I can review and rewatch the videos for me to keep in track.	Keeping up	Self-Pacing	Independence
<i>M- paggamit ng technology ngayon, mas prefer namin kasi sa own.</i>	Technology is utilized.	Technology integration	Technology	Learning Environment

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>F- personally, helpful sya para maka keep up, kesa sa ppt lang ang basehan</i>	It is helpful for me to keep up, rather just relying on the slides.	Keeping up	Self-Pacing	Independence
<i>F- ma-control ko po ung pacing ko., mabalik balikan ko po...</i>	I can self-pace my learning by rewatching or replaying the videos.	Self-pacing	Self-Pacing	Independence
<i>F- changes ... before pandemic, mas owned learning less use of apps, parang mas naga rely na kami dun... naga rely sa usage of different sites, mas nadiscover namin yung mga websites</i>	Much reliant on digital applications or websites instead of having it alone especially in accomplishing tasks.	Dependence on online apps	Technology	Learning Environment
<i>F- pag online, usu thru PM ...shy type shy type esp sa mga groupings, ndi talag makaya magsalita sa mic kay may kaba</i>	Group communication is done thru private messaging, esp among shy ones and afraid to speak using the microphones.	Group communication is observed	Shared Information	Competence
<i>M- pwedeng balik balikan ung mga videos</i>	You can review and replay the videos.	Accessibility	Flexibility	Learning Environment

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>F- messaging apps ..not all ay online esp sa grouping, esp may sari sariling struggle, ayaw lang ng iba mag strive...</i>	Communicate thru messaging apps; everyone struggles; some don't really give it a try/ don't just strive.	Online group chat	Learning Teams/ Group	Interaction
<i>F- helpful po yung discussion video para mabalikan ung topic</i>	Discussion videos allows one to rewatch/ relearn the concepts	Accessibility	Limitless Information	Learning Environment
<i>M- recommend it kasi ma mnage namin yung time ng mabuti, at mapanood namin sya anytime, anywhere</i>	I recommend it because it helps us manage our time and provides us more access.	Time-Management Accessibility	Flexibility	Learning Environment
<i>M- lahat ng subjects, kasi mapanood at maintindihan namin ung mga lessons na ndi namin maintindihan sir...</i>	I recommend [this approach] to all subjects so we can watch and understand the topics.	Recommended in use for other learning areas	Technology	Learning Environment
<i>M- pag discussion vids , ndi maiwasan yung mga distractions</i>	When watching the discussion videos, distractions (from the place/ environment) may not be avoided.	Distractions while watching	Self-Accountability	Independence
<i>F- madali ma distract kasi sa attention span</i>	Distractions can affect the attention span of the students.	Distractions affecting attention span	Reflection	Competence

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>M- hawak namin yung time; less interaction sa mga tao</i>	We manage our own time; however when watching the discussion videos, we have less interaction.	Time management	Flexibility	Learning Environment
<i>M- medyo tiring po ang learning</i>	Learning may be tiring.	Challenging	Reflection	Competence
<i>M- exciting</i>	It is exciting.	Exciting	Reflection	Competence
<i>M/F medyo mabigat (Bio lang) pero makaya rin</i>	Biology is a difficult subject; but we can still manage.	Difficult but manageable	Reflection	Competence
<i>M- kapag energetic or magaling magturo... (gana mag study)</i>	It is motivating to learn when the teacher shows enthusiasm in what he does.	Teacher factor Motivation	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction
<i>M- easier to learn by listening... I tend to learn when discuss with classmates</i>	I tend to learn by listening and when discussing with classmates	Shared knowledge	Shared Information	Competence
<i>F- sabay sabay ang task; usap usap muna kada week ito muna ibigay na specific task; mahirap mag sabay sabay lahat magbibigay</i>	It is more challenging when tasks from all learning areas will be deployed and given to students; some cannot cope with.	Challenging to do tasks	Self-Accountability	Independence

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>F- maganda po yung may discussion videos para may mabalikan ka</i>	Discussion can help us review the topics.	For review	Self-Study	Independence
<i>M- pwede kong ipause para may matake down notes;</i>	I can pause the videos when I want to take down important notes, and play it to resume.	Self-pacing/ independence Convenience	Self-Pacing	Independence
<i>M- very helpful as compliment sa notes sa meeting; ndi masulat lahat; may basehan for review</i>	The videos can compliment the notes we had; esp those that have not taken notes. This becomes are bases too in making our reviewers.	Improved learning/ study style	Flexibility	Learning Environment
<i>F- esp sa Physics and Bio M- if may time parin</i>	Physics and Bio subjects may use discussion videos	Recommended for use in other subjects	Technology	Learning Environment
<i>M- improved performance compared to pre-pandemic set-up; mataas ung expectation to reach</i>	My performance improved this time compared to the pre-pandemic set-up;	Better academic performance	Inquiry	Competence

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>M- nag improve po ako sir...nung prepandemic (pandemic years) ginagawa ko lang nagakopya, pahayahay lang.</i>	My academic performance improved this year; unlike before that I sometimes cheat and just careless.	Better class performance	Inquiry	Competence
<i>F- nung OL class, naging mas productive po ako,, kung may assignments ginagawa ko po agad.</i>	During the online meeting, I feel very productive; I do the assignments right away to avoid piling up.	Productivity	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction

B. Interviews

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
I-F-Niwair				
<i>mahirap talaga sya (subject) sir, pero kelangan po talaga syang intindihin.</i>	It is hard but we have to understand the topics.	Challenging but need to understand	Self-Accountability	Independence
<i>sa room, medyo distracted. Sa bahay, may time talaga ako na manuod sa discussion videos, mag take down notes, word by word...</i>	In the classroom, bit distracted. At home, we have more time to watch and take down information.	Convenience	Flexibility	Learning Environment
<i>Sa school, may mga topics na ndi na matackle f2f; andun na lahat sa discussion videos;</i>	Discussion videos cover topics not anymore taught in the class.	Maximization of class hours	Flexibility	Learning Environment
<i>ndi sya ma-download kung wala ka internet.</i>	Discussion cannot be downloaded if no internet.	Internet-requiring	Technology	Learning Environment
<i>kelangan talaga panuroin ang discussion videos kung may quiz or exam (review)</i>	A need to watch (or rewatch) the discussion videos in preparation for the exam or quiz	Accessibility	Limitless Information	Learning Environment

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>online set-up is mas challenging; kasi nabigla tayo</i>	Online set-up is challenging since we are not accustomed to it.	Novelty /New normal set-up	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction
<i>sa internet; mahirap talaga kasi hindi lahat financially-able</i>	Not all are financially capable to have consistent or constant internet connection	Internet-requiring	Technology	Learning Environment
<i>there are students in the class that cant focus; discussion videos ay makatulong talaga sa kanila pag mag study; may time talaga na nakakalimutan yung disussion ng teacher</i>	Some students cannot focus in the actual classes; Discussion videos are of big help for them to study.	New normal learning style	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction
<i>discussion videos ay parang like guide; or help na rin para maremember yung lesson.</i>	Discussion videos are like guides to remember the lessons	Lesson guide	Limitless Information	Learning Environment
<i>parang mas magustuhan ko yung teacher to make discussion videos; nag e-effort yung teacher para matulungan yung students na ma-learn yung subject</i>	I enjoy the discussion videos and see the effort of teachers making them for students to learn from their subject.	Teaching effectiveness	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>satisfied po ako sa the way you teach us po...grabe ka detailed sir, ma-gets talaga namin...</i>	I am satisfied with the approach. So detailed.	Satisfaction	Reflection	Competence
I-F-Ansuh				
<i>it definitely lessens the chance of students having social anxiety</i>	This learning approach decreases social anxiety	Reduced social anxiety	Reflection	Competence
<i>they are scared of saying the wrong things; not just from the teacher but about the reactions of classmates</i>	Students are scared of the reactions from classmates in actual classes if they have wrong responses	Reduced social anxiety	Reflection	Competence
<i>I describe myself as the one as a loner or that prefers to study alone; but in reality I really like studying with others;</i>	I prefer to study alone; but I like studying with others.	Self-paced and group study	Learning Teams/ Group	Interaction
<i>I like studying Biology by taking down of what is giving; esp when I don't undertand it at first; I try to find related videos; not necessarily taking down notes</i>	I study not necessarily by taking down notes but to find related biology videos	New normal learning style	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
I-F-Nepmam				
<i>Slow learner lang po ako... yung mga discussion videos, nakakatulong po talaga.</i>	Discussion videos are helpful really.	Helpful	Inquiry	Competence
<i>kaya kong bagalan, meron po kasing option dun... sinusulat ko pa kaagad</i>	I can adjust the speed (low or fast) the discussion videos	Convenience / Control	Self-Pacing	Independence
<i>kapag online recitation, nag reready ako ng script.</i>	Online recitation allows me to make script before answering	Control / Confidence	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction
<i>for review po talaga, esp sa exam.</i>	It can be for review before assessment	Comfort	Self-Accountability	Independence
<i>may mas confidence ako this time; not consistent ako mag study; usually nag cramming</i>	I become more confident; usually I don't have consistent study habits	Confidence	Self-Accountability	Independence
<i>blended kasi may time na makausap mo personal ung iba; and online para may time ka po sa sarili mo, balance lang po.</i>	I want blended to have time to be with other students; and to have time for oneself as well (online).	New Normal learning style	Collaboration	Interaction

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>may prefer ko po ang online kesa sa face to face</i>	I prefer online rather than face to face	Online Learning / New learning habit	Technology	Learning Environment
<i>I recommend the discussion videos para makatulong sa mga slow learners na katulad ko, nababalik balikan nila ung video, at maiintindihan [ang topics] ng dahan dahan</i>	I recommend the discussion videos to help academically-challenged students by allowing them to replay / rewatch the videos and control their learning pace.	Independent learning Control Convenience	Self-Accountability	Independence
I-M-Htirah				
<i>When I do get or understand the lesson, it's kinda enjoyable.</i>	When I got the concept, I enjoy it.	Satisfaction / Self-gratification	Reflection	Competence
<i>there are students who cant pick up or catch up easily ; can help them in the lesson</i>	There are students who cannot pick up easily the lesson right away.	Challenge	Self-Study	Independence
I-F-Beejan				
<i>blended para sa akin maganda syang experience</i>	Blended learning is a good experience	New normal learning set-up	Innovation (Content and Style)	Interaction
<i>malaking tulong po, pwedeng panuorin ung videos again any time</i>	It is a big help that students can watch the discussion videos again and again	Convenience	Self-Study	Independence

Emic Transcription	Etic Transcription	Code	Pattern/ Category	Theme
<i>kelangan ko may kasama, kasi nagatanong tanong</i>	I need people who I can ask questions with	Collaboration	Learning Teams/ Group	Interaction
<i>mas maganda kung group study, para magtanon tanong kung ndi magets</i>	I prefer group study so I can ask questions	Group study	Learning Teams/ Group	Interaction
<i>nagatanong lang po ako sa class mates kung ndi ko magets</i>	I ask my class mates when I have questions	Sharing knowledge	Shared Information	Competence
<i>...ginasulat ko rin po sir, para may guide</i>	I also write or take down notes from the discussion videos, as for my guide	Guide Information	Limitless Information	Learning Environment
<i>....sa physics and research po recommended</i>	I recommend making of discussion videos in Physics and Research	Recommended in use for different subjects	Technology	Learning Environment

APPENDIX P

INSTRUCTIONAL IMPROVEMENT PLAN TEMPLATE/GUIDE

Challenges/ Issues	How to address	Objective/s	Indicator/s of Success	Linkage/s	Remark/s
A. Teacher's Preparation/ Performance					
B. Teacher's Experience					
C. Student's Feedback/ Performance/ Behavior					
D. Learning Activities in both Synchronous and Asynchronous phases					
E. Assessment of learning (Formative and Summative)					

APPENDIX Q

DATA ANALYSIS CONSULTATION

This certifies that the undersigned have been consulted in the statistical processes and analysis of the paper entitled, "*STEM Students' Direct and Deferred Conceptual Understanding and Self- Efficacy using the Inverted Learning Approach in Biology: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed- Methods Study*" by Rolly James Fule Cheng for the degree PhD in Education- Major in Biology Education of the University of the Philippines Open University.

For reference only.

JERICK IVAN A. PALOMAR, PhD

ALVIN B. BARCELONA, PhD

APPENDIX R

VALIDATION OF QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

This certifies that the undersigned have been requested to audit trail the qualitative report using the Reflexive Thematic Analysis of the study by Mr. Rolly James F. Cheng entitled, *“STEM Students’ Direct and Deferred Conceptual Understanding and Self- Efficacy using the Inverted Learning Approach in Biology: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed- Methods Study”*.

For reference only.

CHEERY VIC D. PANGARAL, MAELT

Qualitative Research Teacher

RONA MARIE B. DONTON, MAELT

SHS Language Teacher

ANNA MARIE D. PIODENA, MA

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APPENDIX S

DOCUMENTATION

Administration of Tests

Pretest

(11 October 2022)

Posttest

(03 December 2022)

Retention Test

(06 January 2023)

Conduct of online FGDs and live interviews

Focus Group Discussions

(December 12, 13, 20, 2022)

Interviews

(December 12-13, 2023)

Quantitative and Qualitative Data Analysis Training Attended by the researcher

Sample Discussion Videos

Can I Ask Some Super Fantastic Memes On Krebs Cycle

Source: <https://images.app.goo.gl/0qf5r7D05c92cm16>

Source: <https://images.app.goo.gl/18D7vAAABvumf4a6>

Why is this considered a cycle?

Source: <https://images.app.goo.gl/0Qwv9mKCR6Cv3A>

Source: <https://images.app.goo.gl/8hm6m8Q2aroverY87>